

Design System of Revising Technology Adoption for IoT-Based Smart Campuses: A User-Centered Approach

A Report

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ABSTRACT

Everything will soon transition to smart apps thanks to the government of India's effort under the "Smart India" programme. This will be accomplished using the information technology platforms. With fewer features needed than in a smart city, the ideas of a smart city will be applied in a smart campus. All resources on a traditional campus are manually monitored and controlled, but on a smart campus, everything is digitalized. In terms of reducing operating expenses, enhancing efforts, and being timely, digitization will significantly improve. We designed "Smart Campus-Green Environment" to solve all these problems. For this proposed method, we developed a problem-solving application of plant in terms of Energy efficiency, water conservation, and a speedy sprinkler system for the plant. The operating principle of this technology is based on the process of generating a digital representation of the vegetable, called a model. This model is used to measure and evaluate the micro-plasma impact of the vegetable in order to identify factors that may be associated with potential health risks. A new technology built on the principles of smart cities is the smart campus. With fewer features needed than in a smart city, the ideas of a smart city will be applied in a smart campus. All resources on a traditional campus are manually monitored and controlled, but on a smart campus, everything is digitalized. In terms of reducing operating expenses, enhancing efforts, and being timely, digitization will significantly improve. Higher education institutions that use this cutting-edge technology to automatically monitor and manage campus infrastructure will undoubtedly provide the greatest services to their employees and students.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

MAC	-	Media Access Control
RFID	-	Radio-Frequency IDentification
IoT	-	Internet of Things
AVR	-	Advanced Virtual Reduced Instruction Set Computer
LCD	-	Liquid Crystal Display
pH	-	Potential of Hydrogen
FSR	-	Force Sensitive Resistors
NFC	-	Near Field Communication
BLE	-	Bluetooth Low Energy
GPS	-	Global Positioning System
RSSI	-	Received Signal Strength Indicator
SIG	-	Special Interest Group
Wi-Fi	-	Wireless Fidelity
COVID-19	-	COronaVirus Disease of 2019
DTH11	-	Digital Temperature And Humidity Sensor
ESP	-	Electronic Stability Program
SRAM	-	Static Random Access Memory
IDE	-	Integrated Development Environment
PWM	-	Pulse Width Modulation
USB	-	Universal Serial Bus

SYNOPSIS

IOT IMPLEMENTATION OF SMART CAMPUS - A DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION FOR GREEN ENVIRONMENT

ABSTRACT: Everything will soon transition to smart apps thanks to the government of India's effort under the "Smart India" programme. This will be accomplished using the information technology platforms. With fewer features needed than in a smart city, the ideas of a smart city will be applied in a smart campus. All resources on a traditional campus are manually monitored and controlled, but on a smart campus, everything is digitalized. In terms of reducing operating expenses, enhancing efforts, and being timely, digitization will significantly improve. We designed "Smart Campus-Green Environment" to solve all of these problems. For this proposed method, we developed a problem-solving application of plant in terms of Energy efficiency, water conservation, and a speedy sprinkler system for the plant. The operating principle of this technology is based on the process of generating a digital representation of the vegetable, called a "model". This model is used to measure and evaluate the micro-plasma impact of the vegetable in order to identify factors that may be associated with potential health risks.

Keywords: Smart Campus, Internet of Things, Digitalization of attendance, Green environment, Fire management and Energy Efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

The term "Internet of Things" (IoT) refers to the global network of "things" that have electronics, software, and network connectivity so that they may collect and transmit data and communicate with other devices and systems online (Abuarqoub et al.,2017). Everything from everyday household goods to cutting-edge industrial machinery may be classified as a gadget. More than 7 billion IoT devices are now connected, and this number is expected to grow to 10 billion by 2020 and 22 billion by 2025, according to experts. The Internet of Things (IoT) has quickly become one of the most consequential technologies of the 21st century (Ahmed et.al.,2022). The capacity to connect everyday products to the internet via embedded devices has made continuous communication between people, processes, and things possible. This includes things like refrigerators, cars, thermostats, and baby monitors.

Physical things can now interact and collect data with little human intervention thanks to cheap computers, the cloud, big data, analytics, and mobile technologies. In today's

hyperconnected world, digital technologies can record, monitor, and alter every contact between linked things. The real and the virtual coexist and interact. With the help of the internet of things, people may work and live smarter than ever before and take complete charge of their lives. Smart home automation gadgets are only one application of IoT's importance to the commercial world (Burunkayaet.al., 2022). The Internet of Things (IoT) allows businesses to monitor their systems in real time, providing invaluable insights into everything from the efficiency of their equipment to the effectiveness of their supply chains and logistical operations. With the use of IoT, businesses may be able to automate processes and save costs by reducing the need for human labor. In addition, it improves efficiency, speeds up service, cuts down on production and shipping costs, and is transparent to customers (Chen et.al., 2018).

The use of electronic devices may range from entirely hands-on to fully automated. Using an electronic monitoring system for attendance makes data collection easier, faster, and more accurate. Through the use of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), the Internet of Things (IoT), and cloud computing, this research aims to create a real-time presence system that can alert teachers, parents, and school administrators to student absences so that corrective measures can be taken before the next scheduled class.

Green IoT refers to the Internet of Things' adoption of energy-efficient practices to reduce the environmental effect of existing applications and services. Since 2020, when digital devices were widely available to consumers, the rate at which they are used has expanded substantially (D. Minoli et.al., 2017). Many environmental characteristics, including temperature, humidity, and more, may be tracked in real-time from almost any location with wireless Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensors. Nowadays, flames may rapidly spread. Beyond only price, efficiency, and response time, there are a few more issues that require fixing. Because of these problems, the goal of this project is to develop an Internet of Things–enabled smoke and heat detection system for use in fire alarm systems. The system receives heat and flame data through the Internet of Things, processes it, and then immediately takes the planned actions, such as activating the sprinkler system and alert. When companies that generate and distribute electricity put money into modernization, they aim for more than just smart energy management made possible by the Internet of Things. They reorganized in order to boost automation and decrease payroll costs. IoT-based monitoring systems are used, for instance, to automate costly onsite asset management and improve maintenance operations. Utilities may utilize customer electricity use data to calculate dynamic rates automatically.

LITERATURE SURVEY

A new technology built on the principles of smart cities is the smart campus. With fewer features needed than in a smart city, the ideas of a smart city will be applied in a smart campus. All resources on a traditional campus are manually monitored and controlled, but on a smart campus, everything is digital. In terms of reducing operating expenses, enhancing efforts, and being timely, digitization will significantly improve. Higher education institutions that use this cutting-edge technology to automatically monitor and manage campus facilities will undoubtedly provide their employees and students the highest calibre services (v et.al., 2021). The advantages of IoT applications and services include the creation of an interactive environment with the use of cutting-edge services for the campus community. By saving money and time, good campus monitoring and administration will increase its efficiency. It may also increase campus safety thanks to its quick reaction when alarm and sensing systems are activated (Hongyanet.al., 2011). Recent studies have shown the potential for building a smart campus utilizing the IoT technologies and fundamental architectural layers (Hossain et.al., 2019). The development of wireless and mobile communications facilitated the use of IoT technologies and increased the potential of better services in a Smart environment, such as a smart building city (M. Jain et.al., 2017). Both GPS and non-GPS technologies are employed in object positioning systems. Technologies like RFID (O. Bates et.al 2017), iBeacon (Pandey et.al., 2020), or Wi-Fi (Polin, K et.al., 2023) signals may be employed in the case of non-GPS systems (Sneesi et.al., 2022). Similar to this, smartphones backed by the wireless infrastructure network are often utilized to enhance planning and emergency response systems and appssystems (Sneesi et.al., 2022). An energy-efficient campus management system was put into place by Najim et al. utilizing sensors and microcontrollers to monitor and regulate energy use. This may cut down on energy use and maximize resource usage throughout the university. The IoT services used in a smart campus by Moreno et al. also showed a number of energy-efficient services.

The advantages of IoT applications and services include the creation of an interactive environment with the use of cutting-edge services for the campus community. By saving money and time, good campus monitoring and administration will increase its efficiency (Villegas-Ch et.al., 2019). It may also increase campus safety thanks to its quick reaction when alarm and sensing systems are activated. This may cut down on energy use and maximize resource usage throughout the university. The adoption of IoT technology was aided by the development of

wireless and mobile communications. It increased the likelihood that services would be improved in a smart environment, such as a smart city or building.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The notion of a SMART Campus has been around for a long time, and much effort is currently being done to make teaching and learning settings more efficient and intuitive (Wang et.al., 2014). The smartness did not stop at a single classroom; rather, it spread to make the whole institution SMART by automating features that were not available to the individual unit. With the arrival of IoT, this movement accelerated significantly. On a SMART campus, we will include some of the qualities found in a smart city, as well as a paperless and eco-friendly campus. These Internet of Things elements are incorporated with the existing campus amenities (Zhamanov et.al., 2017). These features will assist Higher Education Institutions in efficiently and successfully managing the campus. Smart Attendance System, Smart Equipment Management System, Smart Green Environment System, as well as smart fire and safety systems, will be integrated in the Smart Campus. The initiative will track energy and the environment, as well as the attendance of staff and students. The project will really implement a Smart room (monitor power, AC, temperature, attendance, occupancy (whether the room is available or not), Smart education, an automated system for watering plants, and an automated fire alarm system.

A.Smart Campus Architecture

In Figure 1, we developed the two applications one is student attendance using the RFID and next green environment, in both we are uploading the values which are updating in the IOT app i.e., BLYNK which stores the information as a database, it acts like a cloud storage system, as a new value is recorded in the sensor it will upload to the blynk app, in this we are using the sensors for irrigation, soil moisture sensor to detect the soil dryness, DHT11 sensor is used to take the humidity and temperature values, ESP8266 this is a Wi-Fi module which is used to provide the internet to upload the updated values, LCD was used to display the temperature humidity values and which student login/logout data like in simple line, all these works will be handled by the Arduino mega 2560 micro controller which works as an Arduino board but the input/output pins are more, it has some conditions when those conditions are satisfied then it will move for the next steps.

Figure. 1. Smart Campus Architecture

In this application after starting the device, after starting it display the "SMART CAMPUS", humidity and temperature values will be taken from the DHT11 sensor and displays on the screen, when we put the RFID card on the card reader it will check for the database if data was matched it will upload the card incoming and upload into the blynk app , when same card was read again it will take it as a student was leaving the campus, dryness of the soil will be measured by the soil moisture sensor if soil is wet than it won't move to the next step if soil is dry then it will check for the water level using the float sensor if the water is available in sufficient level then pump will be turn ON otherwise turn OFF the status of the pump was turn ON/OFF status will be uploaded into the cloud.

1. Arduino Microcontroller: The system (shown in Figure 2) is powered by an Atmega2560 microprocessor. This microcontroller contains 256 KB of memory, 8 KB of which is utilized by the bootloader Flash programme memory and 8 KB of static random-access memory (SRAM). The hardware is separated into four sections: the LCD display interface portion, the RFID module interface section, the soil moisture sensor, and the float sensor. The ATmega2560 microcontroller controls all of these elements, and the software necessary to operate them is the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE). It contains 54 digital I/O pins (14 of which are PWM outputs), 16 analogue I/O pins, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power connector, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It comes with everything you need to support the microcontroller; just connect it to a computer through USB or power it using an AC-to-DC converter or battery to get started. Most shields produced for the Arduino Duemilanove or Diecimila are compatible with the Mega.

2. RFID module: The EM-18 125kHz RFID Reader module is a low-cost option for any RFID-based project. The Reader module has a built-in antenna and requires a 5V supply to function. Turn on the module and connect its transmitted pin to the microcontroller's reception pin. If you

hold your card close enough to the reader, it will read the number and send it to the output. The module's output type may be changed to Weigand if desired.

Figure. 2. Block Diagram of Arduino MEGA2560

3. RFID Tag: The microchip and radio aerial of an RFID tag are attached to a substrate and store a 12-byte identification number.

4 RFID Reader: The microchip and radio aerial of an RFID tag are attached to a substrate and store a 12-byte identification number. A transceiver in an RFID reader generates a radio signal and sends it out through an antenna. This signal is really used to power and activate the tag. The transponder in an RFID tag is triggered when it comes into touch with a signal from a reader. The tag receives power from the reader in the form of an electromagnetic field. The radio signal is converted into usable power by the transponder. When powered, the transponder sends an RF signal to the RFID reader, carrying all of the data stored in it, including the unique ID. This identifying information is then sent as a byte from the RFID reader's serial Tx (transmit) pin. Via UART communication, a computer or microcontroller may use or access this information serially.

5. ESP8266 : The values may be uploaded to the server using this WIFI module, which communicates with the Arduino board. The ESP8266 (or Expressive Systems ESP8266) is a TCP/IP and Serial Protocol-compatible Wi-Fi module that is small, lightweight, and energy efficient. It is the most widely used Wi-Fi module because to its low price and small size, making it ideal for use in Internet of Things (IoT) cloud-based embedded applications. It requires a logic level converter if you are using a 5V supply, since it functions at 3V and can handle a maximum voltage of around 3.6V. Via the Serial Port, the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module may be connected to microcontroller boards like the Arduino UNO. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module is the

basis for a number of different breakout boards (i.e., ESP8266 NodeMCU V3). This is the source of electricity. This jack connects the ground to the transmit and receive pins. The battery powered the gadget at 3.3V. 3.2.7 ESP8266.

FEATURES:

1. 802.11 b/g/n.
2. Integrated 32-bit MCU with minimal power consumption.
3. A 10-bit ADC is included in.
4. TCP/IP protocol stack integrated.
5. TR switch, balun, LNA, power amplifier, and matching network are all integrated. PLL, regulators, and power management units are all integrated.
7. Allows for antenna variety WI-Fi 2.4 GHz with WPA/WPA2 capability.
8. STA/AP/STA+AP operating modes are supported.
9. Smart Link Feature is supported for both Android and iOS smartphones. SDIO 2.0, SPI (H). UART, I2C, I2S, IR Remote Control, PWM, and GPIO are all included. STBC, 1x1 MIMO, 2x1 MIMO. Aggregation of A-MPDU and A-MSDU with 0.4s guard interval.

6. DHT11 : The DHT11 Temperature & Humidity Sensor has a calibrated digital signal output and a temperature & humidity sensor complex. This consists of three pins (VCC, GND, and a data pin coupled to the microcontroller's AD1(23) for humidity and temperature updates) and uses the novel digital-signal-acquisition method and temperature and humidity sensor technologies.

POT: As well as adjusting the voltage to find the unknown voltage, the potentiometer now controls the brightness of the LCD by acting as a voltage divider. Water content of the ground: This is a basic electronic device for measuring soil moisture. The sensor may be easily inserted into the ground to determine the moisture or water level there. When the soil is wet, it gives out a 5V digital output, and when it's dry, it gives off 0V. It has four pins labelled VCC (power), GND (ground), DO (digital out), and AO (analogue out).

7. Float sensor: The level of liquid in a tank may be determined via a float switch. The flipped switch might start a pump, activate an indicator, sound an alarm, or do anything else. Hydroponics, saltwater tanks, freshwater tanks, gardening, aquariums, pet bowls, fish tanks, filtration, heating, pumps, and ponds may all benefit from using them to regulate the power heads of their respective systems.

8. Water pump: The R385 6-12V DC Diaphragm Based Mini Aquarium Water Pump is a great all-around non-submersible pump. With the addition of a nozzle, it may be utilized as a spray system due to its high pressure. This submersible pump may be used to water plants, build a waterfall or fountain, and even clean the water in a fish tank. It generates less than 30 decibels of noise when in operation. The pump is equipped with a filter and a suction cup for stable attachment to flat surfaces.

B. Working Principle

In Figure 3, the microcontroller we used here is an Arduino mega2560 v2, which has 54 digital pins, 16 analogue pins, 4 UART pins, a USB connection, and a power jack. This microcontroller was designed to act as a brain for all the devices such as sensors, a WIFI module that provides internet access to the system, and collects all the data based on the conditions we specified in the programme. ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi module that links to a Wi-Fi/hotspot to provide an internet connection that connects to the Arduino board and uploads attendance, soil moisture value, pump switch ON/OFF state, temperature and humidity values to the IOT server (blynk). To display the strings such as welcome, present your card, temperature, and humidity readings on a screen, we utilized a 16x2 LCD, which is linked to the controller and displays the strings as specified in the software. The DHT11 sensor is used to detect the temperature and humidity in the surrounding environment. This data is sent to the controller, where it is uploaded to the server and displayed on the LCD. The EM 18 RFID reader module is connected to the controller, which has four pins VCC, GND, and Tx for transmitting and receiving data from the reader module to the controller. When the student places the card in the reader, it will read the card using the mutual induction principle. If the server has the card details, it will show the student no, otherwise it will wait for another card reading.

Soil moisture sensor is used to determine the dryness of the soil; if the soil is dry, it will check the water level in the tank; if water is available, it will switch on the pump and water the plants. If the water level falls below a certain level or the earth becomes moist, the pump will be turned off.

Figure. 3. Schematic Diagram

Plant Irrigation:The prediction of micro-plasma impacts in organic vegetables using Deep Learning is an exciting development in the field of food safety technology. By combining the power of artificial neural networks, computational resources and the latest imagery technologies, this technology can be used to give accurate assessments of the micro-plasma impacts in organic vegetables.

In order to measure the interactions, the model utilizes deep learning techniques. By using deep learning, the model is able to evaluate and respond to complex patterns in the data. This allows for more accurate identification of the potential risk associated with different types of micro-plasma. Once the model has been trained, it can be used to identify the potential impacts of various combinations of micro-plasma in the vegetable. By doing this, it can provide more accurate insight into the potential health risks associated with different combinations of micro-plasma in the vegetable. This can then be used to inform the food safety regulations and protocols that are in place to protect consumers from potential health risks.

If the soil moisture is more than 650, we may consider the soil to be dry. It then proceeds to the next stage, which is to check the water level in the tank. If the water level is below the minimum needed level, the controller will switch on the pump, and the float sensor value is 1. The pump will switch off automatically, and the status of pump turn on/off will be uploaded into the IOT app (blynk). If the soil moisture is less than 650, the pump will not check for water level and will not turn on. The flowchart will appear below. The functional flow diagram has shown in Figure 4.

Figure. 4. Flow Chart for green environment

As per conditions, the water supply will be only turn ON when the water is sufficient and if the ground dryness is high as per, we programmed in the code. Here we see a true Smart Campus-A Digital Transformation with the IoT in action.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A.Condition Based Output

When the device is turned on, the LCD displays the smart campus until a Wi-Fi connection is available, at which point it displays the Wi-Fi connection. Then it captures the temperature and humidity readings shown (Fig.5) on the LCD while waiting for the card to be read. Upload the file to the IOT app.

Figure. 5. LCD Displaying Temperature and Humidity values and on IoT app

In Figure 6 and 7, if the soil moisture level is more than 650, the system will verify the float sensor value and, if sufficient water is available, switch on the water pump. If there is insufficient water to pump, the pump will remain in the OFF position. If the soil moisture reading is 450, the pump will shut off. This data will then be uploaded to the IOT app.

Figure. 6. Pump Turned ON when water is available

Figure. 7. Pump is turned OFF when water is not sufficient

Numerical Representation of Input Corresponding Output Element is given in Table 1.

Component	INPUT	OUTPUT
DHT11	Surroundings temperature and humidity	Sent to the cloud and have them shown
Soil moisture	Soil moisture value > 650	The water level should be checked. When sensing an adequate water level, the pump will activate and a corresponding data set will be sent to the server.
Soil moisture	Soil moisture value < 450	It will stop pumping and send a file to the server.

Table 1: Numerical representation of Results

CONCLUSIONS

The final goal of this proposed method was to evaluate and analyses the performance of the constructed system. We completed the testing and assessment, demonstrating the design with satisfaction. Lastly, in this model is created through a series of advanced computer algorithms. These algorithms analyze the various components of the vegetable in order to establish a set of features that are associated with the micro-plasma impact. By doing this, the model can be used to identify trends or patterns in the data and to help make predictions. Once the model has been created, it can be used to detect the interactions between different types of micro-plasma in the vegetable. As, a result, this technology may also be employed at colleges and universities. In addition, we recommend including local hosting with internet since if the internet goes down.

FUTURE SCOPE

Future study will benefit from what we built since it is likely to be more accurate by utilizing additional sensors or a more complex algorithm, but this will only be achievable when microprocessors such as Arduino release new and more powerful variations with improved capabilities.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. INTRODUCTION TO SMART CAMPUS

To establish a secure system for student attendance monitoring and hardware inventory management, the project will leverage Bluetooth technology. Mobile devices will be used to transmit wireless Bluetooth signals, enabling automated identification and data collection with a robust retrieval process. This technology ensures precision and guarantees accurate data entry into the database. Bluetooth's future potential, driven by its affordability and compatibility with mobile phones and tablets, will empower mobile devices to transmit essential information to Bluetooth-enabled devices. The Smart Attendance System using Bluetooth Technology plays a pivotal role in this initiative. It consists of a Bluetooth system positioned at the classroom entrance and a cloud-based database. As students enter the classroom with their Bluetooth-enabled smartphones, a Bluetooth sensor in the classroom captures attendance information, timestamps it, and records it in the cloud database. The system retrieves student details manually registered by the administrator in a Google Sheet stored in the cloud and cross-references this information with the scanned MAC address of the student's phone.

Expanding beyond attendance monitoring, the project's next objective is to manage hardware devices like projectors, printers, and laptops using IoT and Bluetooth technology. This forward-looking approach replaces inefficient traditional hardware management methods, offering the campus an efficient and modern solution. It resolves complex and time-consuming campus management issues, enhances security, facilitates teaching and administration, and improves application flexibility. This accelerates response times and fosters seamless collaboration among intelligent systems. Smart classrooms are often hailed as the future of education, underpinned by an array of advanced technologies, including Bluetooth Smart technology (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. Bluetooth Smart technology has emerged as a tool capable of significantly enhancing precision and efficiency in classroom-related activities. Its core strength lies in its role as an automated and innovative data collection technology (Anand, et al., 2016) [3]. It excels in precision, accuracy, and ensures timely data entry. Bluetooth Smart technology, a relatively recent innovation, is poised for a promising future due to its cost-effectiveness and high compatibility (Abrahamsson, et al., 2017) [1]. Notably, it seamlessly

integrates with various mobile phone brands, tablets, and computers. In essence, Bluetooth Smart technology delivers precise tagged data, promising to improve processes and offer numerous benefits to the academic community and students in the near future (Basiouny, et al., 2017) [6].

Numerous research papers have explored the effective use of Bluetooth technology in lecture attendance management and the enhancement of classroom processes and activities (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. The adoption of Bluetooth Smart technology has resulted in greater efficiency in classroom operations, eliminating wastage of valuable time and improving classroom management (Almudarra, 2015) [2]. Bluetooth Smart technology also plays a pivotal role in automating various classroom-related functions and facilitating active teaching and related activities. Moreover, it aids in attendance tracking and final grading of student performance (Bhalla, 2013) [7]. Overall, Bluetooth Smart technology holds the potential to bring about substantial benefits to classrooms, benefiting students, teachers, and university management at large (Macfarlane, 2013) [30]. System architecture serves as a representation of both current and future systems, offering a generalized and high-level functional overview that progressively evolves into a more comprehensive description. This architectural framework is a valuable tool for conveying information about the system's components, their interrelationships, and the governing rules (Choudhary & Rakesh, 2016) [12]. It encompasses various elements, including hardware, software, manual procedures, documentation, and the roles performed by individuals within the organization and the organization itself (Schmidt, 2016) [45]. In essence, system architecture provides a structured blueprint that guides the design and development of systems, ensuring their functionality and coherence.

Figure. 1.1. Bluetooth based Attendance System.

The high-level architecture depicted in Figure 1.1 illustrates how the proposed model deployment will scan the Bluetooth MAC address of student mobile phones, linking them to student IDs and names. Attendance data will be securely stored on Google Drive, enabling lecturers to access attendance records online through the Google Drive platform. This integrated architecture is well-suited for this system, as it facilitates seamless communication between various systems and cross-platform interactions, enhancing the speed of information flow. Bluetooth Smart technology offers several advantages, such as using the mobile phone's Bluetooth MAC address as an identification card (student ID card), low power consumption, and the ability to read Bluetooth signals during motion without requiring a line of sight for wireless communication between devices. This technology also allows for the management of hardware devices like projectors, printers, and laptops using Bluetooth tags.

Distinguishing between a digital campus and a smart campus, the former encompasses a technical environment involving hardware and network connectivity, while the latter incorporates IoT, cloud computing, RFID, and wireless networks, including Bluetooth. In a digital campus, applications include using Bluetooth tags to access digital resources, distance learning, and digital libraries. In contrast, a smart campus employs intelligent systems with Bluetooth sensors, interoperability through sensors, and sensor-based control. System management is achieved through isolated systems equipped with Bluetooth tags. The smart campus leverages Bluetooth technology for information sharing, intelligence utilization, and information dissemination. With the advent of IoT, smart campuses optimize student and faculty access, benefiting from the proliferation of IoT devices, including Bluetooth-connected devices, cameras, sensors, and machines embedded with smart technology. This transformation makes campuses nationwide smarter and accessible to all students, improving security, student success, and community relations (Kumar, P, 2016) [16].

Figure. 1.2. Network based system architecture.

Figure 1.2, displayed above, presents the network diagram for the proposed solution. This solution employs a centralized cloud-based database, allowing multiple systems to connect to this central repository. It is possible to have a single system for each class while utilizing one shared database for all. The IoT fluid level monitoring system presented here is an innovative solution that informs users about fluid levels and prevents flooding. This system utilizes four containers equipped with ultrasonic sensors to detect fluid levels, comparing them to the containers' depths. The system employs an AVR microcontroller, an LCD screen, a Bluetooth modem for data transmission, and a buzzer powered by a 12V transformer. The LCD screen displays the fluid level status in the containers, and a web page provides users with a graphical representation of the container statuses. The system uses color coding to indicate fluid levels. The buzzer alerts users when the liquid level exceeds a set limit, helping to prevent water wastage by providing real-time information about container fluid levels via a web page (Chopade et al., 2017) [11].

Water is a vital resource, and efficient monitoring systems are essential. This thesis discusses water monitoring systems, including tank water level sensing, water pollution monitoring, and water pipeline leakage sensing (Netto et al., 2018) [36]. By utilizing Wireless Sensor Technology, this proposed model addresses water wastage issues in large apartments and offices. The microcontroller-based water level monitoring system informs agents about tank water levels. Sensor-based water pollution detection checks water quality in real-time by monitoring parameters such as pH level, turbidity, and temperature. Leak detection in water pipelines employs force-sensitive resistors (FSR) to monitor pressure in pipes and detects leaks, triggering LED indicators and audible alerts. This approach leverages everyday devices like laptops or mobile phones (Dong, B. et al., 2018) [14]. Water is a precious resource, but unequal distribution and wastage are common issues. The proposed model aims to ensure equal water distribution and reduce wastage. Unlike traditional methods where employees manually open and close valves, this automated system eliminates the need for human intervention, saving time and effort.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

In this chapter the literature available are reviewed within the purview of the present study. Existing methods of smart campus, which have been taken for further improvement and for comparison of the performance of proposed methods, are discussed.

2.1. RELATED WORK OF SMART CAMPUS

The Internet of Things (IoT) represents a rapidly advancing technology that has found its way into various sectors. In the realm of education, particularly in the context of e-learning, IoT has emerged as a game-changer. While many modern college campuses have seamlessly integrated IoT into their academic activities, traditional campuses have yet to fully harness the potential of this technology in their educational endeavors. The incorporation of IoT on campus grounds is instrumental in enhancing the academic experience. It facilitates the collection of data from various devices and fosters the seamless sharing of these resources to optimize e-learning for a smart campus environment. IoT has expanded its reach beyond conventional applications, extending to everyday objects. These IoT-enabled devices come equipped with a protocol stack that enables efficient communication with users. This connectivity extends to a myriad of gadgets, including smartwatches, projectors, printers, Google Glass, and various sensors. The incorporation of IoT technology is poised to revolutionize the utilization of data generated by these devices, enabling dynamic services catering to teachers, learners, and content developers alike. In the context of a smart campus, IoT is leveraged to make classroom materials readily accessible within the networked environment. This accessibility enhances the overall learning experience, allowing for seamless network access. Smart e-learning encompasses the use of enhanced devices that elevate the student learning environment, archiving subject materials into digital records. This transformative approach also lays the groundwork for developing a robust e-learning architecture, paving the way for the realization of smart classrooms (Yang, C., 2017) [51].

The Internet of Things (IoT) is heralded as a transformative technology poised to revolutionize lives worldwide. In essence, IoT devices are non-standard computing devices designed to wirelessly connect to networks and transmit data (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. These IoT networks often feature a master control dashboard, serving as a centralized hub for

monitoring data transmitted by these devices and enabling remote control (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. One of the most profound arenas where IoT devices are reshaping environments is the classroom. At its core, IoT extends connectivity beyond traditional smart devices (Hannah, 2013) [21]. This means that computing capabilities are not confined to computers alone; even everyday items such as light switches and thermostats can become empowered through IoT (Mohandes, 2017) [35]. IoT devices can seamlessly connect with other devices on the same network, resulting in the emergence of smart classrooms and IoT-equipped schools (Stanca, 2006) [47]. The potential of such smart classrooms is boundless (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. IoT devices have the capacity to revolutionize both the learning experience for students and the functioning of classrooms (Mohandes, 2017) [35].

In the classroom environment, Internet of Things (IoT) devices offer a multitude of capabilities that enhance various aspects of education. These functions encompass attendance tracking, room temperature monitoring, wireless door lock control, bolstering school security, and the provision of highly interactive smart boards, fostering an elevated level of interactive learning (Gomez et al., 2012) [18]. Each of these functions addresses unique challenges within the modern educational system. The concept of a Smart Campus represents a paradigm shift, significantly improving the learning, research, and development capabilities of students through advanced technologies. It establishes a robust educational ecosystem powered by IoT, Near Field Communication (NFC), Arduino, and Cloud computing. In contrast, conventional campuses often struggle to provide integrated information systems that align with modern educational needs. Transitioning from a monolithic network to a more dynamic stereo network is imperative, harnessing smart application services and advanced technologies. This transformation not only revolutionizes faculty interactions but also introduces application flexibility, responsiveness, and intelligent monitoring and modeling criteria (Stanca, L., 2006) [47]. Recognizing that college students spend significant time on campus, there's a growing emphasis on creating comfortable and convenient means to control the campus environment remotely, from anywhere and at any time. This transformative approach ensures that the campus operates more intelligently, catering to the evolving needs of students and faculty alike (Schmidt, 2016) [45].

The implementation of learning applications within a smart campus environment offers a unified, user-friendly, and cost-effective solution for students. This approach enhances student access to collaborative learning opportunities, facilitating rapid access to educational

materials and data. IoT technology plays a pivotal role in benefiting colleges, educators, and students in various ways. Smart classrooms equipped with IoT devices extend the duration of educational access, promoting the concept of a smart campus and contributing to advancements in research and development across disciplines. Smart classrooms can accumulate a wealth of data, with IoT devices facilitating the transfer of e-learning applications, delivering updates, and providing educators and institutions with access to enhance the smart campus and foster research in various fields. The utilization of IoT for Smart Campus initiatives is invaluable for data collection, improving the functionality of devices for e-learning, and integrating e-learning systems into the campus environment. IoT also enables the integration of small microchips within the surrounding environment, enhancing the capabilities of e-learning devices for sensing, observing, reacting, and recording (Saraswat. G., 2016) [44].

Attendance tracking holds a paramount position within the educational system, as emphasized by Apoorv & Mathur (2016) [5]. A robust attendance management system not only streamlines administrative tasks but also enhances institutional security significantly. It empowers stakeholders to make informed decisions based on students' attendance records (Ichimura & Kamada, 2013) [23]. IoT devices play a crucial role in tracking and recording student attendance, with the added capability of automating notifications, such as alerting parents when attendance falls below a certain threshold, thereby contributing to the overall improvement of school attendance (Hannah, 2013) [21]. The Internet of Things (IoT) technology plays a pivotal role in monitoring and managing the internal temperature of classrooms, addressing a critical aspect of the learning environment. Classrooms are susceptible to weather and climate fluctuations, which can significantly impact students' ability to learn comfortably (Tegou et al., 2019) [48]. Research indicates that temperature levels can affect students' cognitive abilities, memory, and overall attitude toward studying (Stanca, 2006). Extreme temperatures, particularly high ones, can lead to a depletion of energy for both students and teachers (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. IoT devices offer a solution by continuously monitoring classroom temperatures and providing alerts to ensure that the learning environment remains at comfortable levels. This proactive approach not only enhances the comfort of students and educators but also contributes to cost savings on utility bills, which can be redirected to important matters like student welfare (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. These devices are effective tools in maintaining conducive temperatures for the learning process. Centralized monitoring of temperature sensors ensures they perform their intended functions (Hameed et al., 2015) [20].

Wireless locks represent another valuable IoT feature that enhances classroom security and operational efficiency (Gomez et al., 2012) [18]. Given the paramount importance of school security, IoT devices offer a wireless solution for locking doors when a silent central panic button is pressed (Jacobsen et al., 2016) [24]. This button can trigger all IoT door locks to engage, swiftly putting the school on lockdown in response to potential threats. Additionally, IoT devices can be equipped with the capability to recognize authorized individuals at the door and grant them access (Saraswat & Garg, 2016) [44]. Furthermore, the entire school security framework, including the principal's office, can be remotely activated or deactivated during lockdowns, all managed through a central dashboard accessible via a mobile device (Ting et al., 2011) [61]. In addition to bolstering physical security measures, the Internet of Things (IoT) devices can play a pivotal role in enhancing school security (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. These devices go beyond improving door locks; they also offer the capability to send emergency notifications in crisis situations, directly reaching those in positions of authority, such as teachers (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. This functionality is especially valuable for ensuring the safety of hearing-impaired individuals and can be further augmented with audio enhancements to cover all students (Basiouny et al., 2017) [6]. IoT devices have the potential to mitigate the catastrophic consequences of security breaches, potentially saving lives (Hannah, 2013) [21]. Moreover, they can provide pre-recorded instructions during emergencies, enabling both students and staff to respond swiftly and effectively to urgent situations (Raj et al., 2019) [42], (Kumar, 2016) [26].

Another significant aspect of IoT in the classroom is the introduction of smart boards, which can replace conventional classroom equipment like chalkboards, considered relics of the past (Kumar, 2016) [26]. Schools are increasingly opting for smartphones as effective tools for delivering lectures (Kumar, 2016) [26]. These smartphones can offer visual aids that significantly enhance students' understanding of various concepts. Additionally, they can display tests, assignments, and coursework, streamlining the learning process (Tegou et al., 2019) [48]. When properly programmed, smartphones can also assist schools in monitoring teacher effectiveness within the classroom, contributing to improved educational outcomes (Paasivaara et al., 2012) [39]. An essential aspect of the Internet of Things (IoT) in the classroom is its role in facilitating interactive learning (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. In the past, schoolbooks primarily consisted of text with sporadic images to engage students (Dong et al., 2018) [14]. However, contemporary education extends beyond traditional paper and

images. Many modern textbooks incorporate web-based platforms that offer supplementary materials to enhance students' learning experiences, allowing them to grasp concepts more effectively (Saraswat & Garg, 2016) [44]. These resources often include video content, graphic animations, and opportunities for critical evaluations, providing students with a comprehensive perspective and a deeper understanding of classroom subjects (Singh, J. et al., 2015) [46].

Historical research has underscored a strong correlation between classroom attendance frequency and academic performance (Hannah, 2013) [21]. Consequently, educational institutions place a significant emphasis on implementing a comprehensive and efficient method for recording student attendance in classrooms. Traditionally, instructors manually handled this process, which posed various challenges and was prone to errors (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. In recent times, systems have been developed to automate attendance tracking within classrooms, harnessing technology to save valuable instructional time and enhance the reliability of student attendance reports (Jacobsen et al., 2016) [24]. Biometric systems, while widely proposed, have not gained significant popularity due to several limitations, including the high installation costs and the time-consuming nature of attendance registration (Lodha et al., 2015) [29]. In such a scenario, technology plays a pivotal role in creating a conducive environment for smart learning. This can be achieved through the integration of interconnected devices and sensors, fostering innovation and enhancing students' learning skills. Technology serves as a means to unlock students' potential and alleviate the burden on teachers, particularly when it comes to labor-intensive tasks like attendance recording (Macfarlane.B., 2013) [30].

Bluetooth, known for its low power consumption and cost efficiency, emerges as one of the most commonly utilized radio frequency technologies for automating student attendance tracking (Gomez et al., 2012) [18]. It is widely integrated into mobile phones, wearable devices, and wireless headsets, functioning as an accessible and on-demand platform that can be used from virtually anywhere (Basiouny et al., 2017) [6]. An examination of relevant literature reveals the significance of class attendance and the technologies employed in recording it among students (Basiouny et al., 2017) [6]. As previously emphasized, class attendance is a crucial factor in terms of academic performance (Saraswat & Garg, 2016) [44]. Higher attendance rates typically correlate with improved academic performance, as evidenced in a study by Stanca (2006) [47], which analyzed a large dataset and found a positive correlation between class attendance and academic achievement. Numerous researchers have also conducted studies highlighting the detrimental effects of absenteeism on academic

performance (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. Consequently, both teachers and school management have a vested interest in ensuring maximum class attendance to enhance students' academic outcomes (Jacobsen et al., 2016) [24].

An effective approach to developing a comprehensive class attendance system involves the utilization of radio frequency identification (RFID) or near field communication (NFC) technology. For example, in a study by Ichimura & Kamada (2013) [23], the application of RFID technology in a class attendance system significantly improved attendance monitoring. The system automatically registered attendance and recorded entries into a database, providing teachers and administrators with a comprehensive overview of attendance trends and enabling them to address issues and enhance attendance (Saraswat & Garg, 2016) [44]. Typically, RFID tags are embedded in students' identity cards, requiring students to present their cards and scan them using a reader (Ichimura & Kamada, 2013) [23]. However, a drawback of this method is that anyone can use the identity cards, making it insufficient for verifying a student's identity solely for attendance recording purposes (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. In a study conducted by Ichimura, students were tasked with scanning either their identity cards or a tag on their smartphones that featured a picture. Researchers devised and implemented a comprehensive Class Attendance Management System utilizing mobile devices and incorporating near field communication (NFC) technology and RFID tags (Ichimura & Kamada, 2013) [23]. However, it's worth noting that one of the drawbacks of class attendance systems using NFC or RFID tags is the need for additional preparation and equipment installation (Hannah, 2013) [21]. More recently, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technology has garnered significant attention from researchers as an effective means of facilitating short-range communication between network nodes (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. It has also been explored as a valuable technology for improving classroom attendance tracking. Consequently, numerous studies have delved into its potential use in attendance systems. For instance, researchers like (Bhalla 2013) [7] have developed student attendance systems based on Bluetooth and RFID technology. In such a system, student information is initially collected using an RFID reader, and an authorized person can then access the attendance records via a desktop or laptop connected to the system. Other researchers, such as (Lodha et al. 2015) [29], have created attendance management system applications using Bluetooth-enabled devices. These systems typically require Bluetooth electronic tags embedded in students' ID cards. This approach enhances efficiency by operating within a wireless network, eliminating the need for students to physically present their cards to a reader (Dong et al., 2018) [14], (Tegou et al., 2019) [48].

Researchers like (Apoorv & Mathur 2016) [5] have developed a system aimed at assisting teachers in generating comprehensive student attendance data within the classroom. In this system, students are required to bring their ID cards to class, which are equipped with sticker beacons. The system leverages Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technology beacons within the classroom to effectively identify students and record their attendance (Raj et al., 2019) [42]. However, teachers still need to manually collect attendance information using an Android application that connects to the BLE beacon and gathers sensor data (Hameed et al., 2015) [20]. Certain attendance systems necessitate the installation of an application on students' mobile devices to collect attendance data (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. Researchers like (Saraswat & Garg 2016) [44] have created an application that employs beacons for faculty administrative tasks. Additionally, during class, the system automatically records student attendance based on their location within the classroom (Mohandes, 2017) [35]. In such a system, a timer operates in the background when a student is in close proximity to the beacon. The intricate processes of the system are then carried out on the students' smartphones (Kumar, 2016) [26]. This places a considerable demand on the processing capabilities of the students' smartphones (Macfarlane, 2013) [30]. However, a significant drawback of this system is the requirement for students to install and maintain an additional application (Saraswat & Garg, 2016) [44]. Essentially, many previous techniques for recording classroom attendance necessitate the use of extra equipment like RFID devices and the installation of additional applications by the students (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. While GPS devices are highly effective for outdoor location tracking, they prove to be unreliable in indoor environments. For the specific task of recording student attendance within university campuses, indoor location tracking is required (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. Consequently, GPS technologies are ill-suited for creating advanced classroom attendance systems. Indoor location tracking has piqued the interest of researchers, leading to the development and utilization of various technologies, including Wi-Fi, RFID, image processing devices, magnetic sensors, and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) devices (Gomez et al., 2012) [18].

However, the associated costs of implementing most of these technologies, except for BLE devices, tend to be relatively high, often necessitating the installation of additional equipment in the target environment (Lodha et al., 2015) [29]. BLE devices, also known as Bluetooth Smart, enable the transmission and reception of Bluetooth signals within personal devices (Lodha et al., 2015) [29]. These devices introduce energy-saving features, ensuring long-lasting functionality. Therefore, Bluetooth Low Energy technology can be successfully

adapted to both personal and mobile devices, serving as a sophisticated and advanced indoor positioning system suitable for use within a university campus (Tegou et al., 2019) [48]. Bluetooth is a preferred technology for indoor positioning for two key reasons (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. Firstly, Bluetooth-capable devices are highly prevalent in contemporary times and are integrated into mobile phones, smart wearable devices such as smartwatches, and Bluetooth tags. Secondly, Bluetooth is capable of transmitting small amounts of data with minimal power consumption (Kumar, 2016) [26]. Since students are required to identify themselves through their personal devices, their physical presence within the classroom is essential (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. The signal strength can vary depending on factors such as the distance and intensity of the signal emitted by the device used for indoor location tracking. Indoor positioning systems often employ fingerprinting-based methods (Saraswat & Garg, 2016) [44]. Trilateration is a technique that estimates distance by interpreting the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). To implement trilateration, a minimum of three Bluetooth reference points are necessary within the same area to calibrate the receiver's location (Raj et al., 2019) [42]. The precise location of these reference points must be defined. However, a significant challenge with this technique is that obstacles within the environment, such as furniture commonly found in classrooms, can interfere with the receiver device's signals (Lodha et al., 2015) [29]. Consequently, accurately modeling an environment with a perfect path loss coefficient becomes challenging in such cases (Tegou et al., 2019) [48]. Fingerprinting is the next technique under discussion, and it comprises two main steps (Anand et al., 2016) [3]. In the first step, receiver signal strength indicator values are collected as vectors from predefined locations throughout the classroom space (Apoorv & Mathur, 2016) [5]. Subsequently, when the receiver detects the receiver signal strength indicator value from a specific device (Macfarlane, 2013) [30], the receiver signal strength indicator vector is compared with the previously recorded vector, and location estimates can be calculated using various algorithms. Fingerprinting, by taking into account variations in receiver signal strength indicator values, is considered a technique well-suited for classroom environments (Lodha et al., 2015) [29]. This technique enhances the accuracy of receiver signal strength indicator collection by considering factors such as the proximity of the device, device movement, and temporal sampling (Tegou et al., 2019) [48].

The key variables in this context are the "Smart Campus" and "IoT" (Internet of Things). The "Smart Campus" refers to a campus environment that aims to attract top students and faculty by providing a digital experience. It enhances safety measures, integrates learning

experiences, and streamlines student services. To achieve this, it may involve upgrading outdated infrastructure to align with modern efforts. The adoption of an IT strategy for the smart campus is driven by long-term goals related to enrollment and reputation objectives. "IoT" or the "Internet of Things" is a technology that converges with various embedded systems, including wireless sensor networks, control systems, and home/building automation systems. IoT enables the control of ecosystems through connected devices, but it also raises concerns about privacy and security, which must be addressed following international standards (Schmidt, C., 2016) [45]. "BLE" or "Bluetooth Low Energy" is a technology designed specifically for IoT. Bluetooth is widely used in everyday devices, and it has transitioned from traditional cable connections to mesh network capabilities. BLE is offered through the Bluetooth Special Interest Group (SIG) and supports both star and mesh connectivity in networks. Bluetooth's connectivity is essential for achieving business objectives in various industries and service sectors, including business operations, industry applications, service usage, space management, and customer/staff operations (Chen, H. 2016) [10].

CHAPTER 3

SMART CAMPUS-A DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION USING IOT

3.1. INTRODUCTION

In this work, the digital transformation of of campus to smart by using IoT devices. Meanwhile, input is having certain outside from all the areas cover in the campus. So in our work enhanced smart campus were. In this section, digital transformation of smart campus system are explained here.

The term "Internet of Things" (IoT) encompasses a vast network of interconnected devices that are equipped with electronics, software, and network connectivity. These devices have the capability to collect and transmit data while communicating with other devices and systems over the internet. The IoT category spans from common household items to advanced industrial machinery, encompassing a wide array of gadgets. Currently, there are over 7 billion IoT devices connected, and experts predict this number will surge to 10 billion by 2020 and a staggering 22 billion by 2025. IoT has rapidly emerged as one of the most transformative technologies of the 21st century, enabling continuous communication among people, processes, and things. This connectivity extends to everyday items like refrigerators, automobiles, thermostats, and baby monitors.

IoT's significance lies in its ability to facilitate the autonomous interaction and data collection of physical objects with minimal human intervention. This is made possible by the convergence of affordable computing, cloud technology, big data analytics, and mobile capabilities. In today's hyperconnected world, digital technologies enable the recording, monitoring, and alteration of interactions between interconnected devices. The boundaries between the physical and virtual realms blur, allowing individuals to live and work more intelligently than ever before, gaining greater control over their lives. While smart home automation is a prominent application of IoT for consumers, its relevance extends to the commercial sector. Businesses can leverage IoT to monitor their systems in real time, gaining invaluable insights into equipment efficiency, supply chain effectiveness, and logistical operations. IoT offers the potential for process automation, cost reduction through reduced

reliance on human labor, improved efficiency, faster service delivery, reduced production and shipping expenses, and enhanced transparency for customers.

Figure 3.1: IOT application diagram

The utilization of electronic devices can span the spectrum from hands-on to fully automated operations. Implementing an electronic attendance monitoring system offers several advantages, including simplifying, accelerating, and enhancing the accuracy of data collection. This research project aims to leverage technologies such as radio frequency identification (RFID), the Internet of Things (IoT), and cloud computing to develop a real-time attendance tracking system. This system is designed to promptly alert teachers, parents, and school administrators about student absences, enabling timely corrective actions to be taken before the next scheduled class. The concept of Green IoT, or Green Internet of Things, pertains to the adoption of energy-efficient practices within the Internet of Things ecosystem to mitigate the environmental impact of existing applications and services. Since 2020, with the widespread availability of digital devices to consumers, the rate of their usage has substantially increased. Wireless Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensors enable real-time monitoring of various environmental parameters, including temperature, humidity, and more, from virtually any location. Given the rapid spread of fires in today's world, addressing these challenges goes beyond considerations of cost, efficiency, and response time. Consequently, the primary objective of this project is to develop an IoT-enabled smoke and heat detection system suitable for integration into fire alarm systems. This system receives and processes heat and flame data

through the Internet of Things, enabling immediate actions such as activating sprinkler systems and issuing alerts.

When companies engaged in the generation and distribution of electricity invest in modernization initiatives, their objectives extend beyond achieving smart energy management facilitated by the Internet of Things. These companies undergo reorganization with the goal of enhancing automation and reducing labor costs. IoT-based monitoring systems play a pivotal role in automating costly onsite asset management and improving maintenance operations. Additionally, utilities can leverage customer electricity consumption data to automatically calculate dynamic rates, thus enhancing their operational efficiency and responsiveness.

3.2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of a smart campus represents a new technological frontier inspired by the principles of smart cities but tailored to the specific needs of an educational institution. While a smart city involves a multitude of features and complexities, a smart campus streamlines these ideas to fit within the confines of an educational environment. Unlike traditional campuses, where resources are manually monitored and controlled, a smart campus operates in a digital realm [61]. This digitization brings about significant improvements in cost reduction, operational efficiency, and timeliness. Educational institutions that embrace these cutting-edge technologies for automated monitoring and management of campus facilities can undoubtedly provide their staff and students with top-tier services [65]. One of the key advantages of implementing Internet of Things (IoT) applications and services in this context is the creation of an interactive environment enriched with state-of-the-art services for the campus community. Efficient campus monitoring and administration not only save time and money but also enhance overall efficiency. Furthermore, IoT can contribute to campus safety by enabling rapid responses when alarm and sensing systems are triggered [69].

Recent studies have highlighted the potential of IoT technologies and their fundamental architectural layers in the development of smart campuses [64]. The evolution of wireless and mobile communications has paved the way for the utilization of IoT technologies and has expanded the possibilities for enhanced services in smart environments like smart buildings and cities [62]. Object positioning systems employ both GPS and non-GPS technologies, with

non-GPS systems utilizing technologies such as RFID, iBeacon, or Wi-Fi signals. Smartphones, coupled with wireless infrastructure networks, play a vital role in enhancing planning and emergency response systems and applications. Researchers have also demonstrated the feasibility of implementing energy-efficient campus management systems using sensors and microcontrollers to monitor and regulate energy consumption. These systems not only reduce energy usage but also optimize resource utilization within the university. In essence, IoT services within a smart campus offer a wide range of energy-efficient services, ultimately contributing to the creation of an interactive and efficient campus environment. Najim et al. [65] implemented an energy-efficient campus management system, employing sensors and microcontrollers to meticulously monitor and regulate energy consumption. This innovative approach has the potential to substantially reduce energy usage while optimizing resource allocation across the university. The integration of IoT technology into this system was greatly facilitated by the progress in wireless and mobile communications, creating an environment conducive to enhancing services in smart settings like smart cities and buildings [67, 58].

3.3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The concept of a SMART Campus has been in development for some time, with ongoing efforts aimed at enhancing the efficiency and intuitiveness of teaching and learning environments. This drive for smartness extends beyond individual classrooms, encompassing entire institutions by automating functionalities that were previously limited to individual units. The advent of IoT has significantly accelerated this transformation. A SMART Campus incorporates qualities akin to those found in a smart city, along with a commitment to paperless and eco-friendly practices. These IoT elements are seamlessly integrated into the existing campus infrastructure, empowering Higher Education Institutions to efficiently and effectively manage their campuses. The Smart Campus encompasses various systems, including the Smart Attendance System, Smart Equipment Management System, Smart Green Environment System, and intelligent fire and safety systems. This initiative monitors energy consumption, environmental conditions, and the attendance of both staff and students. It includes features such as Smart rooms for monitoring power, AC usage, temperature, attendance, and room occupancy. Furthermore, the Smart Campus implements automated systems for plant watering and fire alarms, ushering in a new era of campus management.

Traditional attendance systems, relying on fingerprint or RFID-based access cards, are becoming obsolete in the face of the fourth industrial revolution. IoT technology offers innovative and sophisticated solutions to address this challenge, enabling seamless identification of individuals without the need for physical cards or fingerprint scanning. Many organizations manage their assets using paper-based records or barcodes, often requiring manual data entry to track the movement of assets across various departments. IoT-based smart asset management systems aim to streamline this process, reducing reliance on paper documentation and minimizing human intervention. In pursuit of a green environment, institutions must focus on reducing resource consumption, including personnel, water, and energy. Some campuses employ timers without considering environmental impact, leading to resource wastage. IoT technology provides a smart environmental solution to address these issues, promoting sustainability and efficient resource utilization.

The primary challenges revolve around the manual process of taking attendance, especially considering the reluctance to touch unnecessary surfaces after the COVID-19 pandemic. While biometric technology is effective, it has its drawbacks, such as fingerprint recognition issues due to factors like sweat, system failures, and delays in data uploading. Additionally, there's a need to track the duration of students or staff members' presence on campus. Moreover, creating a green and eco-friendly environment amidst a bustling campus is essential. To address these issues comprehensively, we have conceived "Smart Campus - A Digital Transformation Using IoT." This project aims to provide solutions in four key areas: enhancing energy efficiency, promoting water conservation, preventing fires, implementing a rapid sprinkler system for emergencies, and introducing an RFID-based attendance system. The RFID system functions by assigning each student or staff member a card. Upon entering the building, individuals present their cards to an RFID reader module, which scans the card information and records attendance data accurately and efficiently.

3.3.1. SMART CAMPUS ARCHITECTURE

We are in the process of developing two essential applications: one for student attendance using RFID technology and the other for creating a green environment. Both applications involve uploading data to an IoT platform called BLYNK, which serves as a database and

operates as a cloud storage system. This system continually records and updates sensor data, ensuring real-time information availability. For the attendance application, we employ RFID sensors, while for the green environment aspect, we utilize a soil moisture sensor to monitor soil dryness, a DHT11 sensor to capture humidity and temperature values, and an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module for internet connectivity to upload data. An LCD display is incorporated to showcase temperature, humidity, and student login/logout data. To manage these tasks seamlessly, we rely on the Arduino Mega 2560 microcontroller, which functions similarly to an Arduino board but offers more input/output pins. It operates based on specified conditions, enabling the system to proceed to the next steps when these conditions are met.

Figure 3.2: Smart Campus Architecture

In both of these applications, once the device is initiated, it displays "SMART CAMPUS" along with the current humidity and temperature values retrieved from the DHT11 sensor, which are then shown on the screen. When an RFID card is placed on the card reader, it cross-references the data with the database. If there's a match, it logs the card as an incoming event and uploads this information to the BLYNK app. If the same card is read again, it registers the student as leaving the campus. The soil moisture sensor measures the dryness of the soil. If the soil is sufficiently wet, it won't proceed to the next step. However, if the soil is dry, it checks the water level using the float sensor. If there's an adequate amount of water available, it

activates the pump; otherwise, it deactivates it. The pump's status, whether it's ON or OFF, is also uploaded to the cloud for monitoring.

3.3.2. ARDUINO MICROCONTROLLER

The system is driven by an Atmega2560 microprocessor, which boasts 256 KB of memory. Out of this, 8 KB is allocated for the bootloader Flash program memory, and an additional 8 KB is reserved for static random access memory (SRAM). The hardware is divided into four key sections: the LCD display interface, the RFID module interface, the soil moisture sensor, and the float sensor. All of these components are managed by the ATmega2560 microcontroller, with the necessary software developed in the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE). The microcontroller is equipped with 54 digital I/O pins, including 14 PWM outputs, 16 analog I/O pins, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power connector, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It comes with all the essential components to support the microcontroller, whether you connect it to a computer via USB or power it through an AC-to-DC converter or battery. Additionally, most shields designed for the Arduino Duemilanove or Diecimila are compatible with the Mega.

Figure 3.3: Block Diagram of Arduino MEGA2560

3.3.3. RFID MODULE

The EM-18 125kHz RFID Reader module is an affordable choice for RFID-based projects. This reader module comes with a built-in antenna and operates on a 5V power supply.

To use it, simply power on the module and connect its transmit pin to the microcontroller's reception pin. When you bring your card near the reader, it will read the card's number and transmit it as output. Additionally, the module's output type can be configured to Weigand if necessary. An RFID-based system typically consists of two main components.

3.3.4. RFID TAG

The microchip and radio aerial of an RFID tag are attached to a substrate and store a 12-byte identification number.

Figure 3.4: RFID card

3.3.5. RFID READER

The microchip and radio aerial of an RFID tag are attached to a substrate and store a 12-byte identification number.

Figure 3.5: RFID reader

In an RFID system, a transceiver within an RFID reader generates a radio signal and transmits it through an attached antenna. This radio signal serves the purpose of powering and activating the RFID tag. When an RFID tag enters the proximity of the reader and is exposed to the signal, its transponder is triggered into action. The tag harnesses power from the reader's electromagnetic field, converting the radio signal into usable energy. Once powered, the transponder sends out an RF signal to the RFID reader, carrying all the data stored within it,

including its unique ID. This identifying information is then transmitted as a byte through the RFID reader's serial Tx (transmit) pin, making it accessible to a computer or microcontroller via UART communication.

3.3.6. ESP8266

The values obtained from the sensors can be transmitted to the server via the Wi-Fi module, which communicates with the Arduino board. The ESP8266, also known as Expressive Systems ESP8266, is a Wi-Fi module that is compatible with TCP/IP and Serial Protocol. It is compact, lightweight, and energy-efficient, making it a popular choice for Internet of Things (IoT) applications. Due to its affordability and small size, it's widely used in embedded IoT applications. It operates at 3V and can handle a maximum voltage of around 3.6V, so if you're using a 5V supply, you may need a logic level converter. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module can be connected to microcontroller boards like the Arduino UNO via the Serial Port. There are various breakout boards based on the ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module, such as the ESP8266 NodeMCU V3. Power is supplied through a jack that connects the ground to the transmit and receive pins, and the device operates at 3.3V when powered by a battery.

FEATURES:

1. 802.11 b/g/n.
 2. Integrated 32-bit MCU with minimal power consumption.
 3. A 10-bit ADC is included in.
 4. TCP/IP protocol stack integrated.
 5. TR switch, balun, LNA, power amplifier, and matching network are all integrated. PLL, regulators, and power management units are all integrated.
 7. Allows for antenna variety WI-Fi 2.4 GHz with WPA/WPA2 capability.
 8. STA/AP/STA+AP operating modes are supported.
 9. Smart Link Feature is supported for both Android and iOS smartphones.
- SDIO 2.0, SPI (H).
UART, I2C, I2S, IR Remote Control, PWM, and GPIO are all included.
STBC, 1x1 MIMO, 2x1 MIMO.
Aggregation of A-MPDU and A-MSDU with 0.4s guard interval.

3.3.7. DHT11

The DHT11 Temperature & Humidity Sensor has a calibrated digital signal output and a temperature & humidity sensor complex. This consists of three pins (VCC, GND, and a data pin coupled to the microcontroller's AD1(23) for humidity and temperature updates) and uses the novel digital-signal-acquisition method and temperature and humidity sensor technologies.

POT: As well as adjusting the voltage to find the unknown voltage, the potentiometer now controls the brightness of the LCD by acting as a voltage divider. Water content of the ground: This is a basic electronic device for measuring soil moisture. The sensor may be easily inserted into the ground to determine the moisture or water level there. When the soil is wet, it gives out a 5V digital output, and when it's dry, it gives off 0V. It has four pins labelled VCC (power), GND (ground), DO (digital out), and AO (analogue out).

3.3.8. FLOAT SENSOR

The level of liquid in a tank may be determined via a float switch. The flipped switch might start a pump, activate an indicator, sound an alarm, or do anything else. Hydroponics, saltwater tanks, freshwater tanks, gardening, aquariums, pet bowls, fish tanks, filtration, heating, pumps, and ponds may all benefit from using them to regulate the power heads of their respective systems.

3.3.9. WATER PUMP

The R385 6-12V DC Diaphragm Based Mini Aquarium Water Pump is a great all-around non-submersible pump. With the addition of a nozzle, it may be utilised as a spray system due to its high pressure. This submersible pump may be used to water plants, build a waterfall or fountain, and even clean the water in a fish tank. It generates less than 30 decibels of noise when in operation. The pump is equipped with a filter and a suction cup for stable attachment to flat surfaces.

3.4. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The microcontroller we used here is an Arduino mega2560 v2, which has 54 digital pins, 16 analogue pins, 4 UART pins, a USB connection, and a power jack. This microcontroller was designed to act as a brain for all the devices such as sensors, a WIFI module that provides internet access to the system, and collects all the data based on the

conditions we specified in the programme. ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi module that links to a Wi-Fi/hotspot to provide an internet connection that connects to the Arduino board and uploads attendance, soil moisture value, pump switch ON/OFF state, temperature and humidity values to the IOT server (blynk). To display the strings such as welcome, present your card, temperature, and humidity readings on a screen, we utilised a 16x2 LCD, which is linked to the controller and displays the strings as specified in the software. The DHT11 sensor is used to detect the temperature and humidity in the surrounding environment. This data is sent to the controller, where it is uploaded to the server and displayed on the LCD. The EM 18 RFID reader module is connected to the controller, which has four pins VCC,GND, and Tx for transmitting and receiving data from the reader module to the controller. When the student places the card in the reader, it will read the card using the mutual induction principle. If the server has the card details, it will show the student no, otherwise it will wait for another card reading. Soil moisture sensor is used to determine the dryness of the soil; if the soil is dry, it will check the water level in the tank; if water is available, it will switch on the pump and water the plants. If the water level falls below a certain level or the earth becomes moist, the pump will be turned off.

Figure 3.6: Schematic Diagram

If we display the card to the reader module, it will verify the card number in the database, and if it matches the data in the database, the associated card holder will obtain the attendance; if the details were not matched, the reader will wait for the next card. The attendance will be taken into account, and the time spent by the card holder will be transferred to the IOT app as shown in the flow chart below.

Figure 3.7: Flow Chart for attendance

If the soil moisture is more than 650, we may consider the soil to be dry. It then proceeds to the next stage, which is to check the water level in the tank. If the water level is below the minimum needed level, the controller will switch on the pump, and the float sensor value is 1. The pump will switch off automatically, and the status of pump turn on/off will be uploaded into the IOT app (blynk). If the soil moisture is less than 650, the pump will not check for water level and will not turn on. The flowchart will appear below. As per conditions, the water supply will be only turn ON when the water is sufficient and if the ground dryness is high as per, we programmed in the code.

3.5. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

Here we see a true smart campus-a digital transformation with the iot in action. The BLYNK app, an IoT platform, will receive data from the RFID attendance system and the green environment monitoring system that we developed..

Figure 3.8: Flow Chart for green environment

3.5.1. CONDITION BASED OUTPUT

When the device is turned on, the LCD displays the smart campus until a Wi-Fi connection is available, at which point it displays the Wi-Fi connection. Then it captures the temperature and humidity readings shown on the LCD while waiting for the card to be read. Upload the file to the IOT app.

Figure 3.9: LCD Displaying Temperature and Humidity values and on IoT app

When the student shows the card, the reader reads the card, which contains the 12 digits of code, and the card information are checked in the database; if the card details match, it displays the student details; otherwise, it displays the invalid card and waits for another reading. If the student shows the card before the departure time, it will reflect student departure. The login and logout information will be uploaded to the IOT app.

Figure 3.10: Displaying Student Details

Figure 3.11: Student Leaving

Figure 3.12: Student After Login Data

Figure 3.13: Students Logged Out Data

If the soil moisture level is more than 650, the system will verify the float sensor value and, if sufficient water is available, switch on the water pump. If there is insufficient water to pump, the pump will remain in the OFF position. If the soil moisture reading is 450, the pump will shut off. This data will then be uploaded to the IOT app.

Figure 3.14: Pump Turned ON when water is available

Figure 3.15: Pump is turned OFF when water is not sufficient

3.5.2. NUMERICAL REPRESENTATION OF INPUT CORRESPONDING OUTPUT ELEMENT

Component	INPUT	OUTPUT
RFID reader	Valid card	Verify the records and send the attendance data to the server. Information on the students should be shown.
RFID reader	In Valid card	Verify this with the data bank. Display the invalid card warning
DHT11	Surroundings temperature and humidity	Sent to the cloud and have them shown
Soil moisture	Soil moisture value>650	The water level should be checked. When sensing an adequate water level, the pump will activate and a corresponding data set will be sent to the server.
Soil moisture	Soil moisture value<450	It will stop pumping and send a file to the server.

Table 3.1: Numerical representation of Results

3.6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The final goal of this project was to evaluate and analyse the performance of the constructed system. We completed the testing and assessment, demonstrating the project's

satisfaction. It also demonstrates how important it will be in institutions by increasing student attendance. It can be observed that the initiative met its objectives with excellent results. The limits of this study were examined, as well as how they might be solved, as described in the recommendations and suggestions for future research. Lastly, in this project, a recognition sensor or camera may be utilised to detect faces or iris, which will be more advanced than RFID. Iris recognition has become one of the most essential technologies in mobile phones, and several businesses have already used it for their staff. As a result, this technology may also be employed at colleges and universities. In addition, I recommend including local hosting with internet since if the internet goes down, the local host can register the students. Future study will benefit from what I built since it is likely to be more accurate by utilising additional sensors or a more complex algorithm, but this will only be achievable when microprocessors such as Arduino release new and more powerful variations with improved capabilities. Moreover, the system currently lacks a way for comparing the two results of RFID and IR sensors for in and out detection. The system must offer an interface to transmit a notice if the number of RFID tags is different from the number of students in the class.

CHAPTER 4

AUTOMATIC STREET LIGHT CONTROL USING RTC AND LDR

4.1. INTRODUCTION

An embedded system is a computer system in which software is intricately woven into the hardware. It encompasses both standalone and integrated applications, defining it as a computer equipped with a microcontroller or microprocessor programmed to execute a specific set of functions. The term "embedded" comes from the specialized software tailored for these systems. Essentially, an embedded system is a software-based, real-time control system that relies on microcontroller or microprocessor technology to manage and monitor physical devices. The potential of embedded systems lies in their ability to deliver exceptional performance and automation levels. The breakthrough in autonomous robot development, with applications in daily life, owes much to embedded systems, which have sent ripples through the scientific community. Embedded technologies have already showcased their significance through the widespread adoption and unique appeal of robot companions from leading electronics companies. Given their diverse range of applications and their potential to fuel innovative product creation, embedded systems are poised to be the dominant technology of the future. Currently, the embedded market is undergoing two major shifts.

The driving force behind R&D in embedded programming-based applications is the mutually beneficial collaboration between embedded software providers and Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs). The increasing complexity of embedded applications, demanding more robust and cost-effective hardware along with enhanced connectivity, poses challenges for the Embedded Operating System (EOS) industry and its future growth. Microcontrollers are designed to execute specific tasks, with a clear connection between input and output. These applications necessitate some level of processing and deliver an output based on the input received. Input devices such as keyboards, mice, washing machines, digital cameras, and more fall into this category. Embedding these applications onto a single chip is feasible due to their minimal resource requirements, resulting in reduced size and cost. Figure 4.1 illustrates a typical microcontroller layout.

In contrast, microprocessors excel in general-purpose tasks such as programming, game design, website development, image editing, document creation, and more. In these scenarios, the relationship between input and output is less defined. They require ample storage space, processing power, input/output interfaces, and other resources. Microprocessors typically operate at significantly higher clock speeds compared to microcontrollers. Today's microprocessors can perform complex operations at speeds exceeding 1GHz, while microcontrollers generally operate at speeds ranging from a few megahertz (MHz) up to 30 or 50 MHz.

Figure 4.1: Microcontroller Architecture

Comparing the cost-effectiveness of a microcontroller to a microprocessor leaves no room for doubt—microcontrollers are undoubtedly the more cost-effective choice. However, it's essential to understand that a microprocessor should not be used as a substitute for a microcontroller, as this approach significantly inflates the application's overall cost. A microprocessor alone cannot function effectively. Constructing a system around a microprocessor becomes costly, as it necessitates additional components such as RAM, ROM, buffers, I/O ports, and more.

4.2. LITERATURE REVIEW

To enhance the efficiency of solar energy conversion, the study "Energy Efficient Smart Street Light" [71] examined a streetlight with an automated tracking system. Automation

systems have become integral to our daily lives, enhancing convenience and comfort in everything from ceiling fans to washing machines [72]. Conventional lighting systems typically offer only two settings, on and off, which is inefficient as it results in constant full-power operation, leading to energy wastage. Street lights are a notable source of power loss, but automation offers various ways to conserve both energy and money. One solution involves using a Light Dependent Resistor (LDR) to regulate the lighting system [73]. By 2015, a solar-powered street lighting system based on traffic flow was expected to be fully operational, harnessing solar energy as a renewable resource [74]. LEDs (Light Emitting Diodes) were chosen for their energy efficiency and superior illumination compared to traditional sources like halogen and mercury lamps. The streetlights function autonomously based on light sensors [75]. The study outlines a two-installation case study conducted in Scotland and Wales, highlighting the technology's features and benefits. Installation logs reported that approximately a hundred thousand MINOS devices had been successfully deployed [76]. While electricity has many fascinating applications, few are as vital as street lighting for ensuring pedestrian and driver safety during nighttime hours. However, keeping streetlights on throughout the night consumes significant resources and shortens the lifespan of electrical components like bulbs. Lighting accounts for a substantial portion of a city's energy budget, with streetlights being notorious energy consumers. An intelligent lighting management system has the potential to extend the lifespan of streetlights and reduce costs by up to 70 percent [77]. In some cases, the predetermined on/off schedules of streetlights can cause delays in addressing malfunctions, leading to extended periods of unnecessary illumination, which has environmental implications [78]. Research by Painter (1994) underscores the importance of adequate nighttime illumination on roadways and thoroughfares, as most crimes occur after dark [79].

This study's [80] objective is to propose the use of solar panels to power street lighting in order to reduce energy consumption. The aim is to achieve energy savings through the automation of streetlight on/off switching and the adjustment of light intensity to avoid unnecessary illumination. The proposed system [81] incorporates motion detection sensors to determine whether lights should be brightened or switched off entirely. The research [12] explores the utilization of the Internet of Things (IoT) and wifi/LoRa for monitoring energy-efficient electrical appliances. This system [83] monitors human movement to dynamically adjust light intensity, reducing excessive energy use and cost. It is a cost-effective solution with extensive operational range, capable of replacing more expensive wired network infrastructure.

Ravi Kishore Kodali and Subbachary Yerroju presented a paper on "Energy Efficient Smart Street Light" [84], while Dhiraj Sunehra introduced "Automated Street Light Control with Wireless Sensor Networks" [85]. Prakash developed an IoT-based Intelligent Street Lighting system for smart cities [86].

4.3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Street lighting is an essential aspect of modern society, primarily aimed at ensuring safety and preventing accidents during the night. Illuminating city streets at night is not only a critical duty but also a costly one for municipalities. Lighting expenses can account for a significant portion, ranging from 10% to 38%, of the total energy cost in cities worldwide. Adequate street lighting is highly valued in developing nations as it plays a crucial role in maintaining economic and social stability. The installation of streetlights indirectly contributes to reducing crime rates and accidents in neighborhoods, fostering social cohesion by instilling a sense of security for individuals venturing out at night. However, due to the fast-paced nature of contemporary life, people often forget to manually turn streetlights on or off when necessary, leading to inefficient and costly lighting practices. The utilization of energy-efficient technologies and designs can make street lighting considerably more affordable. Three key factors, namely automation, energy consumption reduction, and cost-effectiveness, are central to technological advancements in this field.

The primary aim of automation in various tasks, achieved through computers and smart technologies, is to reduce reliance on human labor. As the challenges in electricity generation mount, minimizing energy consumption remains a top priority. With increasing demand, the need to design systems that minimize costs becomes even more critical. To address these concerns, we have implemented an automated streetlight control system based on a Real-Time Clock (RTC) and a Light-Dependent Resistor (LDR). In the era of automation, human involvement in manual operations is becoming less practical. This has led to significant advancements in embedded systems, enabling the development of a microcontroller-based automatic street light control system. This system employs an RTC and an LDR to detect the fading daylight below the range of human visual perception, prompting the streetlights to turn on automatically. In our project, we utilized a DS1307 RTC and a light-sensing diode with four pins (VCC, GND, SCL, SDA) connected to a microcontroller. When the RTC matches the

stored time, the system proceeds to determine whether there is sufficient ambient light to justify turning off the streetlights. This approach combines automation, energy efficiency, and cost savings to enhance the effectiveness of street lighting systems.

4.3.1. AUTOMATIC STREET LIGHT ARCHITECTURE

To address shortcomings in previous approaches, we have developed specific strategies for our project. The power supply for our project will be derived from a 230V AC source, which will undergo a step-down transformation process to produce 5V and 12V DC outputs for various circuit components. This configuration is illustrated in the block diagram provided. The Light-Dependent Resistor (LDR) and Real-Time Clock (RTC) modules will be powered by the 5V source, while the LED strips, utilizing the ULN2003 model, require a 12V power supply. The RTC module, equipped with a quartz crystal, will ensure precise timekeeping and provide the current time to the microcontroller. Our microcontroller, a Node MCU v3, receives light intensity data from the LDR and responds by adjusting the conduction rate accordingly. This microcontroller operates on the Arduino platform, and our code is developed within the Arduino software development environment, utilizing embedded C-language code. The IDE and RTC library have been configured for RTC programming, and we have written the code to calculate LDR intensity. Specific microcontroller pins have been allocated for various functions: A0 for Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) readings from the LDR, D1 and D2 for the Serial Clock (SCL) and Serial Data (SDA) lines from the RTC, D3, D4, and D5 for controlling the LED strips, and D6 and D7 for the reset button's operation.

Figure 4.2: Automatic Street Light Architecture

We introduced an innovative approach in this project by incorporating both Light-Dependent Resistors (LDRs) and Real-Time Clocks (RTCs). In previous setups, either LDRs or RTCs were used, but we aimed to address the dynamic nature of the Indian environment and its seasonal variations. Our system operates as follows: if the time indicated by the RTC matches the predefined time for the lights to activate, only the lights will be switched on; otherwise, they will remain off. The RTC performs a comparison between the current time and the user-defined activation time to determine whether the lights should be turned on. If the time difference is less than or equal to 5 minutes, the lights are triggered to illuminate.

4.3.2. MICROCONTROLLER NODE MCU DESCRIPTION

A microcontroller is a versatile programmable electronic device designed for various applications. It is a single-chip device that incorporates essential components such as a central processing unit (CPU), memory (RAM), input/output (I/O) ports, and a timer on a single chip. The limited but dedicated on-chip memory, ROM, and I/O ports make microcontrollers suitable for a wide range of tasks. When it comes to prototyping Internet of Things (IoT) devices, the NodeMCU is a convenient option. It is an open-source firmware and development kit that allows you to easily write code in Lua. The ESP8266, developed by Expressive Systems, is a notable microcontroller that has gained popularity for its capabilities in the IoT domain.

Figure 4.3: Basic block diagram of Node MCU v3

This module has a wide variety of pin-outs and an integrated USB port. Like Arduino, NodeMCU devices may be easily flashed by connecting them to a laptop via micro-USB cable. There are a total of 30 pins on the node MCU v3, but we only make use of a subset of them. A zero, GND, VCC, D1, D2, D3, D4, and D5 are the standard digital outputs. Gnd means "ground" or "grounding."

Power is supplied via the VCC pin.

The microcontroller's analogue input is connected to pin A0.

The SCL input is connected to D1.

SDA data is entered via D2.

The LED strips should be connected using pins D3, D4, and D5.

4.3.3. FEATURES OF NODE MCU

1. The Tensilica 32-bit RISC Processor Xtensa LX106 serves as the microcontroller.
2. 3.3V is the working voltage.
3. Powered by a 7-12V input voltage
4. Digital Input/Output (DIO) Pin Count: 16
5. ADC Input Ports (Analog Input): 5
6. UARTs: 1
7. SPIs: 1
8. I2Cs: 1
9. 4 MB of internal flash memory
10. ROM: 64 KB SRAM: 10
11. 80 MHz Clock Frequency
12. USB-TTL based on CP2102 is onboard, allowing for Plug n Play operation.
13. Radio Antenna PCB
14. Compact form factor allows for easy integration into existing IoT applications.

4.3.4. ESP 8266

The NodeMCU group has developed a comprehensive development board for the ESP8266, featuring a micro-USB connector for programming and a 3.3V regulator. This open-source board simplifies the process of working with the ESP8266. Once you connect the

NodeMCU board to your computer and install the necessary USB drivers, you can immediately begin programming it to connect to your Wi-Fi network and perform various tasks. Remarkably, this powerful development board is available for just four dollars (USD) on platforms like eBay, making it a cost-effective choice for IoT projects. The ESP8266, produced by Expressif, a Chinese company headquartered in Shanghai, is the most widely used and affordable Wi-Fi system-on-a-chip (SoC) with a built-in TCP/IP stack and a low-power 32-bit microcontroller. In the rapidly growing field of the Internet of Things (IoT), it stands out as a popular and economical solution for establishing wireless connections between "Things" and the internet.

Figure 4.4: ESP8266 wifi module

While there are various environments available for working with ESP modules, the Arduino IDE stands out as the most popular choice. It's important to note that the ESP8266 module requires a precise voltage supply of 3.3V to operate correctly, and supplying it with 3.7V or more can result in damage. To program the ESP-01 module effectively, you can use a 3.3V FTDI board. Many users of the ESP-01 encounter challenges related to powering it on. During programming, it's advisable to power the module through a 3.3V Arduino pin or by using a potential divider to ensure the correct voltage supply. Additionally, it's worth noting that the module has a relatively high power consumption, so using a small voltage regulator capable of producing at least 500mA is crucial. The LM317 is a good example of a suitable voltage regulator for this purpose.

4.3.5. ULN 2003

The ULN2003 serves the purpose of current amplification and features a total of 16 terminals or pins. This integrated circuit (IC) includes 16 inputs and 14 outputs, with pins 1, 3, and 5 serving as inputs, and pins 16, 14, and 12 as outputs. These inputs are extended from the microcontroller's D3, D4, and D5 pins, while pin 9 is connected to a 12V supply (V_{cc}), and

pin 8 serves as ground. The ULN2003 is essentially an array of Darlington transistors designed to handle high voltage and current. It also incorporates common-cathode clamp diodes at the high-voltage outputs of its seven NPN Darlington pairs, making it suitable for switching inductive loads. Furthermore, it allows for parallel connection of the Darlington pairs to increase their current-carrying capacity. Each channel of the ULN2003 has a continuous current rating of 500mA and a peak current capacity of 600mA. Notably, the inputs are located opposite the outputs, and built-in suppression diodes are included to facilitate driving inductive loads.

The ULN2001, ULN2002, ULN2003, and ULN2004 are part of the same family of open collector Darlington arrays with a common emitter, all capable of handling high voltage and current. Each channel in these devices has a 500mA rating and can handle peak currents of up to 600mA. Inputs are positioned on the opposite side of the board from the outputs, and suppression diodes are integrated to support the driving of inductive loads. These ICs are compatible with various logic families, including ULN2001 (all-purpose, DTL, TTL, PMOS, CMOS); ULN2002 (14–25 V PMOS); ULN2003 (5 V TTL, CMOS); and ULN2004 (6 - 15 V CMOS, PMOS). These versatile components can power a wide range of devices, from solenoids to DC motors to high-power buffers or LED displays, and even filament lights. In order to minimize thermal resistance, some versions like ULN2001A, ULN2002A, ULN2003A, and ULN2004A are available in a 16-pin DIP package made of copper. Additionally, there are compact outline formats, such as ULN2001D1, ULN2002D1, ULN2003D1, and ULN2004D1, provided in a miniature SO-16 package. For more efficient code and space utilization, the ULN2003 can also be obtained in the TSSOP16 package.

Figure 4.5: ULN 2003 diagram

4.3.6. LDR

Two photoconductive cells made of cadmium sulphide (cds) with spectrum responses similar to the human eye. When the brightness of the light increases, the cells' resistance decreases. While being a specialised sort of Resistor, the Light Dependent Resistor (LDR), also known as a Photoresistor, has no polarity and may be connected in any way. These work well with a breadboard and can be adapted to a perf board with little effort. The LDR pinout diagram depicts a symbol similar to that of a Resistor, but with additional, internal arrows. The directional arrows indicate the lights' messages. The concept of photoconductivity lies at the heart of how photoresistors function. The absorption of light by a substance may enhance its conductivity, a process known as "photoconductivity".

Figure 4.6: LDR circuit diagram

A photoresistor, also known as an LDR (Light Dependent Resistor), is a kind of resistor whose resistance varies with the intensity of the light hitting it. Hence, in a completely dark room, the resistor will have a resistance of many megaohms, but when light is progressively shone over the sensor, the resistance will begin to diminish, eventually reaching a few ohms. Electrons in a semiconductor material's valence band are stimulated to the conduction band when light (photons) strikes the device. In order for the electrons to transition from the valence band to the conduction band, the energy of the photons in the incoming light must be larger than the bandgap of the semiconductor material. Because of this quality, the LDR may serve as a light detector. It is sensitive to the quantity of light hitting it and can therefore tell day from night. So, this sensor is the simple and inexpensive answer for us if we need to detect light or tell the difference between day and night.

4.3.7. RTC

A real-time clock (RTC) is an accurate timepiece for computers, often implemented as an integrated circuit. While the word is most often used to describe components of computers, servers, and embedded systems, real-time clocks (RTCs) may be found in almost any electronic equipment that requires precise timekeeping. The clock's precision relies on the crystal's precision and the accuracy with which the oscillator circuit's capacitive load matches the capacitive load for which the crystal was trimmed. Crystal frequency drift due to temperature changes will provide another source of inaccuracy. The clock may be running quickly if the oscillator circuit was subjected to external circuit noise.

The DS1307 is a serial bus slave device. Implementing a START condition and then giving a device ID number and register address grants access. Unless a STOP condition is carried out, subsequent registers may be accessed in order. The device will abort an active access and reset its address counter when VCC drops below $1.25 \times V_{BAT}$. So long as the system is operating outside of its tolerance range, inputs to the device will be ignored. When the voltage drops below the battery backup threshold (V_{BAT}), the device enters a low-current battery backup mode. During startup, if VCC is larger than $V_{BAT} + 0.2V$, the device will switch from battery to VCC, and if VCC is greater than 1.25 times V_{BAT} , it will detect inputs. The key components of the serial RTC are shown in Figure 4.7 block diagram.

Figure 4.7: LDR circuitual diagram

Reading the correct register bytes will provide you with the time and date. Figure 3 depicts the RTC registers. Writing the proper register bytes sets or initialises the time and calendar. The time and date registers are stored using BCD values. The clock halt (CH) bit is located in position 7 of register 0. Setting this bit to a 1 turns off the oscillator. Clearing to a 0 activates the oscillator. Please be aware that the values of all registers upon power-on are not specified. As a result, the oscillator must be turned on (CH bit = 0) when the system is first set up. The DS1307 has a choice of 12-hour or 24-hour operation. The 12/24-hour mode choose

bit is located in the sixth bit of the hours register. While it's on high, it switches to 12-hour mode. Bit 5 indicates PM if in 12-hour time format, whereas AM indicates logic low. Bit 5 in the 24-hour mode represents the second 10-hour interval (20- 23 hours). The current time is sent to a second group of registers during a 2-wire START. When the clock is still ticking, the time is retrieved from these auxiliary registers. In the event that the main registers are updated during a read, it is not necessary to re-read the registers.

4.4. WORKING PRINCIPLE

In many developing nations, the importance of adequate street lighting cannot be overstated, as it plays a critical role in maintaining economic and social stability. The primary objective of this project is to establish an autonomous streetlight management system that is not only cost-effective but also reliable. The major drawback of the current standard switching and timer-based system lies in its excessive energy consumption. Therefore, the primary focus here is on developing a robust automated streetlight controller, with the Node MCU serving as the central component of the control circuit. The rectifier circuit, which includes a step-down transformer and a voltage regulator, provides the necessary 5V DC power to operate the control circuit. For assessing light levels, a light-dependent resistor (LDR) is utilized, which provides analog signals to the microcontroller based on the incident light. The system combines the LDR with timer-based principles to establish the actual active and inactive times for the streetlights.

There are two key prerequisites that must be met for the streetlights to turn ON or OFF. These prerequisites involve the microcontroller's timers and the LDR's capacity to gauge light intensity. Once both conditions are satisfied, the microcontroller issues signals to activate or deactivate the relay, thereby controlling the streetlights' operation. The NodeMCU microcontroller's Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) handles the conversion of the LDR's analog signals. The streetlights respond by turning on when the controller transmits the signal. As the current street lighting system suffers from power wastage due to improper switching, the aim of this project is to create a highly dependable automated streetlight system. The central control elements in the planned control circuit are the microcontroller and the Light Dependent Resistor (LDR). It has been determined that the designed system effectively achieves automated switching control. The automated streetlight control circuit is constructed, and it includes embedded C programs that are uploaded to the NodeMCU microcontroller. The microcontroller processes analog signals from the RTC and LDR, while also managing ON/OFF time adjustments. Only when both conditions are met will the streetlight either switch

Figure 4.9: Flow Chart for LDR

Figure 4.10: Flow Chart using RTC and LDR

The above design works well both during the day and at night; the lights turn on and off with the help of an RTC and a light-dependent resistor (LDR).

4.5. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

In this case, an LDR and RTC-based Automated Street Light Controlling System has been put into use in the real world. Light intensity is correlated with ADC readings in this system. LDR ADC values may be used to power the system; if the ADC value is below 400, the lights will turn on, and if it's above, they'll stay off.

4.5.1. CONDITION-BASED OUTPUT

As soon as the device is turned on, the LCD screen will display the smart campus so long as a wifi connection is accessible, and then it will display the wifi connection status after it has been established. The next step is to wait for the card to be read while the LCDs the current temperature and humidity. Transfer to the IoT application.

Figure 4.11: LDR adc_values

Figure 4.12: Lights turned ON by covering the LDR

We have now integrated RTC and LDR since we have specified in the code that the RTC should keep time in accordance with our plans. The controller will first verify that the time set in the RTC corresponds with the time the user has specified; if it does, the controller

will proceed to step two, at which point it will determine whether or not the light intensity registered by the LDR meets the threshold of 400; if it does, the lights will turn on for five seconds before turning off automatically.

Figure 4.13: System turned ON the lights

Figure 4.14: Time and LDR values

4.5.2. NUMERICAL REPRESENTATION OF INPUT CORRESPONDING OUTPUT ELEMENT

Component	INPUT	OUTPUT
LDR	Adc_value<400	Indicators will activate
LDR	Adc_value>600	After the lights are turned ON, they will automatically turn OFF.
RTC and LDR	Rtc time==user set time; adc_value<400	Indicators will activate
RTC and LDR	Rtc time!=user set time; adc_value<400	The lights will remain out until either the time is correct or the adc value is less than 400.
LDR	Adc_value<400	Indicators will activate

Table 4.1: Numerical Representation of output according to the input

4.6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The design and testing of our "Automatic Street Light Control using RTC and LDR" project have proved fruitful. A significant amount of electricity is lost in the typical street lighting system, however this may be prevented with automatic control employing LDR. The constructed control circuit is used to examine the automated switching function, which is proven to be extremely efficient with very low maintenance costs. The streetlight's ON/OFF status is determined by the circuit. The microcontroller has successfully managed the streetlights. When it becomes dark, the controller will send a signal to turn on the lights. In addition, the system relies on both a timer and an LDR sensor, eliminating a previous disadvantage of the street light system. In the long run, we want to expand this effort into an Internet of Things (IoT) initiative to determine how many systems are functioning normally, how much energy is being used, the possibility of determining which streetlight is malfunctioning so that no more complaints are required, and so on.

CHAPTER 5

SMART ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

5.1. INTRODUCTION

The system for tracking student attendance in the classroom using facial recognition technology ensures that the facial features in each student's image are standardized to a consistent set of features, such as 16 DCT coefficients. This process involves grayscale standardization, histogram equalization, Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). However, it has been observed that the system may sometimes incorrectly identify one student as another due to difficulties in recognizing certain facial expressions, leading to an overall acceptance rate that does not meet the desired standards. To enhance the system's accuracy, drivers compatible with the type of camera being used are obtained from the MathWorks website. Additionally, a substantial number of images, typically 500 to 1000 per individual, are captured using high-definition cameras to improve accuracy. Face detection is achieved through object cascading and the use of the bounding box technique. The captured faces are then resized to 112x92 pixels, resulting in images of approximately 11 KB in size. These facial images are loaded into the system's database, and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) features are extracted and stored as an array list, which is used to assign a label based on the input data.

The attendance system is further improved by incorporating NFC technology and a mobile application. Each student is issued an NFC tag with a unique ID during enrollment, which they use for attendance. The lecturer's mobile phone, equipped with an embedded camera, captures the student's face when the NFC tag is touched or moved near it. The data is then sent to the college server for validation and verification. While this method is efficient and quick, it does not automatically detect violations if the NFC tag is used by someone other than the original owner. Additionally, relying on personal smartphones for NFC reading can pose privacy concerns and inconveniences for lecturers. A more secure solution involves using biometrics or face recognition to ensure that attendance is recorded by the actual student. In this system, captured images are compared to a face database, and attendance is marked on a

highly secure server, preventing unauthorized attendance marking. However, this system currently lacks portability as it requires a standalone computer with constant power supply. To address this, a portable module can be developed to make the system more convenient, especially for student attendance tracking.

The face detection algorithm in this system is enhanced using skin classification techniques to improve accuracy. Image Processing is employed to train the system, with images converted to grayscale and subjected to image subtraction before further processing on the server. The results are made accessible to verified web clients through an online web server. In "Face Recognition Based Attendance System" by Nandhini R., a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) algorithm is implemented to detect and recognize faces. After identifying and processing the face, it is compared to the database to update student attendance. The post-processing step involves updating the student's names in an Excel sheet, which can be maintained on a weekly or monthly basis to record attendance.

5.2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Teacher's Attendance and Roll Book forms are specifically designed for maintaining monthly classroom attendance records. Each roll book page is meant to be printed for a single month and can accommodate records for up to 26 students. Users can employ their customized key to denote attendance-related events, using "A" for Absent, "T" for Tardy, and "N" for No School, making it a straightforward and user-friendly tool. This classroom attendance book, presented as an Excel spreadsheet, necessitates at least an Excel reader for viewing. It is intended for professional or academic settings, allowing managers or teachers to monitor the attendance of employees or students on a weekly basis [91]. Furthermore, the Attendance tool is widely employed for taking attendance in various settings, including classrooms and institutions. It serves as an Attendance Register to meticulously document the regularity of students, teachers, or employees on a day-to-day basis. It is a valuable tool for monitoring and ensuring regular attendance, whether in online or face-to-face courses. This Roll Call Attendance feature, accessible at the account level, is adaptable and suitable for use by institutions across the board [92].

Employee Attendance Registers are indispensable for maintaining comprehensive records related to each employee's presence, absence, sick leave, and more, crucial for payroll and salary calculations [93]. These records encompass various payroll aspects such as attendance, absenteeism, tardiness, holidays, and training, all contributing to accurate salary computations. The HR department, executives, and business owners rely on this data for determining employee salaries. Employee attendance registers, available with or without payroll calculations, provide a structured system for office attendance tracking. The Salary Sheet With Attendance Register is a comprehensive payroll tool that enables the recording of attendance for up to 40 employees [94]. This template simplifies attendance tracking with predefined formulas and formatting. Users input employee details once and can mark their absence or presence from a dropdown menu. It is available in multiple file formats, including Excel, Google Sheets, Open Office Calc, and Apple Numbers [95].

Student Attendance Registers serve the purpose of monitoring student attendance in educational institutions, facilitating the tracking of regularity throughout the academic year. These registers ease the workload of teachers by automating attendance records, freeing up time for more productive tasks [96]. Timesheet Attendance Registers are designed for hourly employees, recording the number of hours they work daily, bi-weekly, or weekly. Traditionally, these registers were paper-based, but they have transitioned to digital formats. Timesheets summarize hours worked, note arrivals and departures, and calculate the total time spent on the job [97]. In the realm of employee attendance tracking, biometric time and attendance systems have gained prominence. These systems offer an efficient and accurate alternative to paper-based or manual attendance records, addressing issues of inaccuracy and difficulty in tracking. Biometric attendance systems have proven valuable for improving efficiency and reducing costs in various businesses [98].

Figure 5.1: Bio-metric

RFID, or radio frequency identification, is a category of electronic device comprising a small antenna and an integrated chip. Its primary function is to facilitate the transmission of

information, whether related to individuals, animals, books, or various items, between a reader and an RFID tag through the use of radio frequency electromagnetic fields. Impressively, it has the capacity to store up to 2,000 bytes of data [99]. RFID systems come in various types, generally consisting of an antenna, a transponder, and a transceiver. These systems allow for versatile deployment, with some tags positioned in close proximity to the RFID reader and others situated at greater distances. Operating frequencies for RFID devices span a spectrum of ranges, including low, mid, and high frequencies. Specifically, the low-frequency range encompasses frequencies from 30kHz to 500kHz, the mid-frequency range extends from 900kHz to 1500kHz, and the high-frequency range spans from 2.4kHz to 2.5kHz [100].

Figure 5.2: Radio Frequency Based Identification

5.3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The CNN network structure employed in this experiment comprises several key components, including the input layer, convolution layer 1, pooling layer 1, convolution layer 2, pooling layer 2, a fully connected layer, and a Softmax regression classification layer. What sets CNN apart from traditional neural networks is the incorporation of convolutional and pooling layers for image feature extraction. The convolutional layer, often referred to as the feature extraction layer, is responsible for filtering the input image to extract relevant features. Each neuron in this layer is connected to a local receptive field from the previous layer, allowing it to extract local features. Essentially, this layer applies convolution operations to the original image, generating multiple filtered images. The convolution process involves randomly determining convolution kernel values, sliding them across the input image from left to right and top to bottom, and multiplying the selected image matrix by the convolution kernel.

Each convolution serves as a feature extraction method, akin to a sieve, highlighting specific parts of the image. Larger activation values indicate a stronger match with the filtering criteria. Importantly, convolution does not alter the image size, preserving the original dimensions and aiding in the extraction of various features, such as edges, lines, and angles.

Before the attendance management system can operate effectively, essential data must be inputted into the system, comprising individuals' basic information, including their ID and facial images. Portrait acquisition begins with capturing the individual's face using a camera. The system's initial task is to detect the presence of a face in the captured image. If no face is detected, the user is prompted to capture their face again until a specified number of portraits are obtained. In this project, each student's profile requires 10 portraits. The decision to limit it to 10 portraits per student accounts for storage constraints on the Raspberry Pi, considering the university's substantial student population. These images undergo various pre-processing steps, resulting in grayscale images and uniformly cropped faces, prerequisites for using the EigenFaces Recognizer. These image acquisition and pre-processing procedures are illustrated in the diagram below. Subsequently, the processed images are organized and stored in a hierarchical manner. In this project, all faces are stored in sub-folders under the "database" folder. Each sub-folder represents an individual and contains a series of face portraits belonging to that individual. These sub-folders are named according to the unique ID of each individual within the institution. The entire process of image retrieval, pre-processing, and storage is orchestrated by a script named "create_database.py." Face detection has become a relatively straightforward task for computers, with some machine learning models achieving state-of-the-art results in computer vision.

We are using pretrained CNN model for face detection and extraction.

1. **Box around faces:** Show red boxes around all the faces recognised in the image. The Python file is faceDetectionCNN.py
2. **Extracted faces:** Extract faces from all images in a folder and save each face into a destination folder to create a handy dataset. The Python file is faceExtraction.py.

5.3.1. OPENCV

OpenCV is a library of programming functions mainly aimed at real-time computer vision. It has a modular structure, which means that the package includes several shared or

static libraries. We are using image processing module that includes linear and non-linear image filtering, geometrical image transformations (resize, affine and perspective warping, and generic table-based remapping), colorspace conversion, histograms, and so on.

5.3.2. CNN TRAINING EXPERIMENT

For this experiment, the chosen dataset is the New York University's OlivettiFaces face database, which contains a collection of 400 images featuring 40 different individuals. Each person's profile comprises 10 distinct face pictures. These images are represented in 8-bit grayscale, with pixel values ranging from 0 to 255. The overall dimensions of each image are 1190×942 pixels. Within the dataset, there are a total of 20×20 faces, resulting in a size of $(1190/20) \times (942/20)$, which equates to 59.5×47.1 pixels for each individual face. The raw data is divided into three segments: the training data consists of 320 samples, while the remaining data is allocated to verification and testing.

Face recognition is a method employed to identify or verify an individual's identity based on their facial features. These systems are versatile, capable of recognizing people in photographs, videos, or real-time scenarios. They can leverage existing hardware infrastructure, cameras, and image capture devices, making them a convenient biometric solution for passive identification in various environments. Face recognition has proven particularly efficient for automatically recording student attendance in online classes during the COVID-19 pandemic, eliminating the need for physical interaction. Its accuracy, high enrollment and verification rates, and straightforward interpretation of comparison results make it a valuable tool in attendance management. For face recognition there are two types of comparisons. Classification of FACE RECOGNITION.

1. Verification: This is where the system compares the given individual with who that individual says they are and gives a yes or no decision.
2. Identification: This is where the system compares the given individual to all the Other individuals in the database and gives a ranked list of matches.

All identification or authentication technologies operate using the following four stages:

- 1) Capture: A physical or behavioural sample is captured by the system during Enrollment and also in identification or verification process.

- 2) Extraction: Unique details extracted from the sample and a template is created.
- 3) Comparison: The template is then compared with a new sample.
- 4) Match/non match: The system decides if the features extracted from the new Samples are a match or a non match.

A pre-processing module locates the eye position and takes care of the surrounding lighting condition and color variance. First the presence of faces or face in a scene must be detected. Once the face is detected, it must be localized. Some facial recognition approaches use the whole face while others concentrate on facial components and/ or regions (such as lips, eyes etc). The appearance of the face can change considerably during speech and due to facial expressions. The input can be recorded video of the speaker or a still image.

Figure 5.3: Block Diagram of Attendance System using CNN

- A one-second sample consists of a 25-frame video sequence, providing a snapshot of facial features. To enhance security and create a 3D representation of the face, multiple cameras can be employed to prevent unauthorized access using photographs. Synergetic computers are utilized to classify both optical and audio features. Synergetic computers are algorithmic systems designed to simulate synergistic phenomena. During the training phase, BIOID generates a prototype known as a "face print" for each individual. When a newly recorded pattern is pre-processed, it is compared with the face prints stored in the database. The system assigns a value to each comparison on a scale from one to ten. If the score surpasses a predetermined threshold, a match is confirmed. The implementation of face recognition technology involves three stages. Face recognition systems operate by identifying specific landmarks on the face, which are defined as nodal points. Typically, there are approximately

80 nodal points on a human face, and software measures these points to distinguish facial features accurately.

- Distance between the eyes
- Width of the nose
- Depth of the eye socket
- Cheekbones
- Jaw line
- Chin

How Face Recognition Systems Work

Face Bunch Graph: A Face bunch graph is created from “70 nodal points” to obtain a general representation of face. Given an image the face is matched to the Face bunch graph to find the same point. These nodal points are measured to create a numerical code, a string of numbers that represents a face in the database. This code is called face print. Only 14 to 22 nodal points are needed for face it software to complete the recognition process.

Face Recognition Attendance System: The modern face recognition attendance system is much efficient and safer than the conventional counterparts. There are a few Systems that are based on the face recognition technology and each of them has extremelyvarying features for the best suitability in different environments. It provides a facility for the central data management system. A very cost effective method of recording the attendance. Easy to manage Increased security Cost-effective. Automated time tracking system Advantage of Automatic Attendance System with Face Recognition Physical Description Test Same Person’s Images

- Measurements Generated From Image Input Image
- Test Same Person’s Images
- Test Same Person’s Images
- Test Different Persons Images
- Test Different Persons Images
- Test Different Persons Images Recognize Real Student
- Recognize Real Student
- Recognize Real Student
- Recognize who is not Student
- Recognize who is not Student

- Attendance File
- Attendance in Excel File

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have revolutionized the way we approach image processing and recognition, simplifying the once complex task. CNNs mimic the human visual process by focusing on individual portions of an image and systematically scanning the entire image. These networks transform each image into a numerical vector, which can then be learned by the fully connected Dense layers of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The architecture of a CNN can be customized by adjusting parameters such as the number of convolutional layers, max-pooling layers, hidden ANN layers, and the number of neurons within them. However, it's essential to note that adding more layers and neurons can slow down the model's performance. Moreover, when dealing with a large volume of images, typically exceeding 50,000, a standard laptop's CPU may not be efficient for training. In such cases, it becomes necessary to use a GPU-enabled laptop or leverage cloud services like AWS or Google Cloud for computational power. It's also important to fine-tune hyperparameters for each layer in addition to determining the optimal number of layers and neurons to achieve the best model performance.

Take a quick look at some of the important hyperparameters

Filters=32: This number indicates how many filters we are using to look at the image pixels during the convolution step. Some filters may catch sharp edges, some filters may catch color variations some filters may catch outlines, etc. In the end, we get important information from the images. In the first layer the number of filters=32 is commonly used, then increasing the power of 2. Like in the next layer it is 64, in the next layer, it is 128 so on and so forth.

kernel_size=(5,5): This indicates the size of the sliding window during convolution, in this case study we are using CNN. In this case study, we will learn how to implement a face recognition model using CNN. This template can be used to create an image classification model on any group of images by putting them in a folder and creating a class.

5.3.3. GETTING IMAGES FOR THE CASE STUDY

The data contains cropped face images of 16 people divided into Training and testing. We will train the CNN model using the images in the Training folder and then test the model

by using the unseen images from the testing folder, to check if the model is able to recognise the face number of the unseen images or not.

5.3.4. CREATING A MAPPING FOR INDEX AND FACE NAMES

The above `class_index` dictionary has face names as keys and the numeric mapping as values. We need to swap it, because the classifier model will return the answer as the numeric mapping and we need to get the face-name out of it. Also, since this is a multi-class classification problem, we are counting the number of unique faces, as that will be used as the number of output neurons in the output layer of fully connected ANN classifier.

Steps for Face Detection:

In this project, we've performed face detection and recognition by using OpenCV and NumPy. We've used Raspberry Pi3, but you can also use it with other systems. You'll only have to modify the code slightly to use it on some other device.

Step 1: Install Libraries

First, you should install the required libraries, OpenCV, and NumPy. You can install it easily through:

```
pip install opencv-python
```

```
pip install opencv-contrib-python
```

For installing NumPy in your system, use the same command as above and replace 'opencv-python' with 'numpy':

```
pip install numpy
```

Step 2: Detect Faces

Now, you must configure your camera and connect it to your system. The camera should work properly to avoid any issues in face detection. Before our camera recognizes us, it first has to detect faces. We'll use the Haar Cascade classifier for face detection. It is primarily an object detection method where you train a cascade function through negative and positive images, after which it becomes able to detect objects in other photos. In our case, we want our model to detect faces. OpenCV comes with a trainer and a detector, so using the Haar Cascade classifier is relatively more comfortable with this library. You can create your classifier to detect other images as well.

Step 3: Gather Data

Now that your model can identify faces, you can train it so it would start recognizing whose face is in the picture. To do that, you must provide it with multiple photos of the faces you want it to remember. That's why we'll start with creating our dataset by gathering photos. After collecting the necessary images, add IDs for every person, so the model knows what face to associate with what ID. Start with the images of one person and add at least 10-20. Use different expressions to get the most effective results. Create a script for adding user IDs to images, so you don't have to do it manually every time. The script is vital in case you want to use your model for multiple faces.

Step 4: Train

After creating the dataset of the person's images, you'd have to train the model. You'd feed the pictures to your OpenCV recognizer, and it will create a file named 'trainer.yml' in the end. In this stage, you only have to provide the model with images and their IDs so the model can get familiar with the ID of every image. After we finish training the model, we can test it.

5.3.5. CREATING THE CNN FACE RECOGNITION MODEL

In the below code snippet, we have created a CNN model with

- 2 hidden layers of convolution
- 2 hidden layers of max pooling
- 1 layer of flattening
- 1 Hidden ANN layer
- 1 output layer with 16-neurons (one for each face)

The flexibility of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) allows us to fine-tune their architecture by adjusting parameters such as the number of convolution layers, max-pooling layers, hidden ANN layers, and the quantity of neurons within each layer. However, it's crucial to note that as we add more layers and neurons, the model's processing speed decreases. Moreover, when dealing with a substantial volume of images, especially in the range of 50,000 or more, a standard laptop's CPU may not be sufficient for efficient model training. In such

cases, it becomes necessary to either invest in a GPU-enabled laptop or utilize cloud services like AWS or Google Cloud, which offer the computational power needed for large-scale image processing. For our demonstration, where we've used a relatively small dataset consisting of only 244 training images, running the model on a laptop is feasible and straightforward. Beyond just determining the ideal number of layers and neurons, it's essential to focus on fine-tuning the hyperparameters for each layer to achieve optimal model performance and accuracy. Take a quick look at some of the important hyperparameters

Filters=32: This number indicates how many filters we are using to look at the image pixels during the convolution step. Some filters may catch sharp edges, some filters may catch color variations some filters may catch outlines, etc. In the end, we get important information from the images. In the first layer the number of filters=32 is commonly used, then increasing the power of 2. Like in the next layer it is 64, in the next layer, it is 128 so on and so forth.

kernel_size=(5,5): This indicates the size of the sliding window during convolution, in this case study we are using 5X5 pixels sliding window.

strides=(1, 1): How fast or slow should the sliding window move during convolution. We are using the lowest setting of 1X1 pixels. Means slide the convolution window of 5X5 (kernel_size) by 1 pixel in the x-axis and 1 pixel in the y-axis until the whole image is scanned.

input_shape=(64,64,3): Images are nothing but matrix of RGB color codes. during our data pre-processing we have compressed the images to 64X64, hence the expected shape is 64X64X3. Means 3 arrays of 64X64, one for RGB colors each.

kernel_initializer= 'uniform': When the Neurons start their computation, some algorithm has to decide the value for each weight. This parameter specifies that. You can choose different values for it like 'normal' or 'glorot_uniform'.

activation= 'relu': This specifies the activation function for the calculations inside each neuron. You can choose values like 'relu', 'tanh', 'sigmoid', etc.

optimizer= 'adam': This parameter helps to find the optimum values of each weight in the neural network. 'adam' is one of the most useful optimizers, another one is 'rmsprop'

batch_size=10: The "batch_size" parameter in neural network training specifies how many rows of data are fed to the network at once before the calculation of the Sum of Squared Errors (SSE) begins, and the neural network initiates the process of adjusting its weights based on the

errors encountered. Each time all the rows are passed in batches of 10 rows, as defined by this parameter, it is referred to as completing one epoch or one full data cycle. This approach is commonly known as mini-batch gradient descent. The choice of "batch_size" is critical, as a small value, such as 2 or 4 rows at a time, can cause the LSTM to examine the data slowly, potentially leading to overfitting. Conversely, a larger value, like 20 or 50 rows at a time, speeds up the network's analysis of the data, which may result in underfitting. Therefore, selecting an appropriate "batch_size" requires careful consideration through hyperparameter tuning to strike the right balance.

Epochs=10: The same activity of adjusting weights continues for 10 times, as specified by this parameter. In simple terms, the LSTM looks at the full training data 10 times and adjusts its weights.

The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) represents a category of neural network architectures that possesses the unique capability of implicitly extracting features from data without the need for prior feature selection or extraction, setting it apart from traditional machine learning algorithms. This attribute has made CNNs a focal point of attention, particularly in the realm of computer vision, where they have demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in addressing various challenges, including face recognition, object detection, image segmentation, and more. As the field of computer vision has advanced, CNN architectures have evolved to tackle these challenges more effectively. Notable examples of such architectures include LeNet, AlexNet, VGG16, Inception, and others. While there are many efficient architectures proposed in the literature for smart attendance systems based on face recognition, their generalizability to real-world scenarios often falls short. Consequently, it becomes imperative to design custom models tailored to specific applications. This paper introduces a novel CNN architecture inspired by recent advancements in the field and further presents a web application called the Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS) for online attendance tracking. The key contributions of this paper encompass:

- Novel CNN Architecture for end-to-end face recognition system.
- Collecting face data of students through an automated system Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS):

A. Web-based application: This paper is organized as follows. Next Section presents an overview of Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS) along with the Data Collection and Augmentation.

This section describes the proposed web-based application for Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS) using face recognition by CNNs. This section also presents the challenges of acquiring huge train and test datasets for real time applications. A. SAMS - An Overview The developed web based application for attendance posting based on face recognition is called Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS). It is developed using flask framework and python. An overview of the proposed application is presented in Figure 5.1. The main components of the application are:

- 1) Front-End Interface (Camera)
- 2) Server
- 3) CNN Model
- 4) Database
- 5) End Result (Display Screen)

Front-End Interface is a web page which takes the video frame as input through the camera using open computer vision (OpenCV) library. Server is the back-end of the application which maintains the connection with front-end interface, model, database and displayscreen. The server receives video frame as input from the front-end interface and the face is detected, which is given as an input to the model and the model predicts the label. The server checks if the attendance is posted previously. If not, the attendance is posted into the database including the timestamp. The details of the corresponding student are shown using the display screen, which is web page. represents the images of front-end interface and end result of the application.

B. Data Collection: The face data of the students is collected using an automated system, which accesses the system camera to take the video frames and transforms as a dataset by performing the following sequence of operations:

- Identify the location of face in the video frame.
- Extract the face image and convert into gray scale image.
- Attach the label w.r.t to the class of the image and write onto a csv file.

The sample images from the collected data with respect to each class. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to reduce the dimensions of the data into three dimensions and corresponding three dimensional scatter plot is constructed for understanding the patterns in the data.

C. Data Augmentation: In real time scenario, collecting huge amount of data is a difficult and tedious task. In order to achieve high accuracy, large volume of training data is required. Hence, data augmentation technique is used to generate new samples by manipulating the existing data. More recently, Face-specific data augmentation for unconstrained face recognition. In the current work, synthetic images are being generated randomly, by applying the following operations

- Zoom
- Shear
- Height shift
- Rotation
- Width shift

The synthetic images generated after data augmentation.

D. Train and Test data: The initial samples collected to form the dataset are 10,029 face images which contains four classes. Each class consists of 2,500 face images except class-3 which contains 2,529 face images. The dataset is normalized during training to boost up the processing and the train data is augmented during the training process of CNN. This section presents the detailed explanation of the proposed CNN architecture for this particular application, SAMS. It also covers the explanation for different layers used to build the CNN model. The proposed CNN architecture consists of 20 layers which includes:

- Two Dimensional Convolutional Layer (Conv2D)
- Batch Normalization Layer
- Max Pooling Layer
- Dense Layer

The two dimensional convolutional layer is used to extract the features from the previous input, the batch normalization layer is used in order to normalize the input and also

overcome the problem of vanishing gradient and exploding gradient. The max pooling layer is used to reduce the dimensionality of the input and the dropout layer is used to avoid the over fitting problem. The architecture takes a gray scale image with shape (100, 100, 1) and results the class label of the image as prediction. The total number of parameters of the CNN are 7,658,629 of which 7,656,197 are trainable and 2,432 are non trainable.

The proposed Convolution Neural Network(CNN) is developed using an open source python library, Tensorflow [18]. The experiments are performed on the system with following configuration.

- Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) used is 1X Tesla K80 with 2496 CUDA cores, 12GBGDDR5 VRAM.
- Central Processing Unit (CPU) used if 1X single core hyper threaded Xeon Processors, 45MB Cache with 12.6 GB RAM and 320GB disk.

This paper serves as a formal introduction to the pivotal role of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) in the domain of Face Recognition and its adaptation for the purpose of attendance tracking. It provides a comprehensive breakdown of the workflow underlying the web application, the Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS). Additionally, the paper delves into the intricacies of data collection and data augmentation techniques utilized in the development of the CNN model. It introduces a novel CNN model tailored for face recognition, which is subsequently integrated into the development of SAMS. Experimental results highlight the efficiency of the proposed CNN model and the user-friendly nature of the SAMS application, which is not only easy to deploy but also simple to maintain. Looking ahead, the paper outlines future prospects, aiming to create a robust application for smart attendance management capable of accommodating a larger number of students in real-time scenarios.

The proposed Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is trained with the RMSprop optimizer, utilizing a learning rate of 0.001. The categorical cross-entropy serves as the loss metric, and a batch size of 256 is employed over 50 epochs. During the training process, various callbacks are employed, including ReduceLROnPlateau for dynamically reducing the learning rate, Early Stopping for terminating training if accuracy improvement stalls, TensorBoard for visualizing model graphs, and ModelCheckpoint for saving model weights for future use. The paper presents accuracy and loss trends throughout the training epochs, illustrating that accuracy increases while loss decreases with an increasing number of epochs. After a certain

point, both loss and accuracy reach a plateau, signifying minimal further improvement. Performance measures for classification are employed, including the Kappa statistic for inter-rater reliability assessment, Precision to quantify the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positives, and Recall, which signifies the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to all observations in the actual class.

5.4. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The implemented system offers an efficient solution for recording attendance in lectures, sections, or laboratories, benefiting lecturers and teaching assistants in terms of time and effort, particularly in large classes. The Automated Attendance System was developed to address the limitations of the traditional manual attendance system. It harnesses image processing techniques within the classroom environment, extending its utility beyond mere attendance tracking. The system's functionality was rigorously tested using existing test images and real-time scenarios, with subsequent sections providing screenshots of the outputs of various functions. Four volunteers were involved in testing, and the system proved its efficacy in recognizing faces from different angles and lighting conditions. Real-time recognition facilitated automatic attendance marking, with data seamlessly imported to an Excel sheet. The project was conceived to meet the societal demands for more efficient attendance monitoring systems, driven by technological advancements. Education's paramount importance prompted this innovation, aiming to engage students in schools, colleges, and universities, as their active participation is vital for acquiring knowledge and ultimately enhancing their prospects for a better future.

Figure 5.4: Persons on camera

Figure 5.5: Triggered to Excel Sheet

Our developed system has made individual classroom attendance tracking a reality. It can be readily adopted in higher education settings with necessary enhancements and the creation of a comprehensive database containing student details. This versatile system is not limited to managing student attendance but can also be extended to faculty, staff, and non-staff members' attendance. One crucial development objective is achieving complete automation. Currently, the system requires supervision to prevent potential discrepancies, such as device tampering. Our ultimate goal is to fully automate the process by utilizing real-time live feed captured by a camera to mark student attendance without any manual oversight. This ensures legitimate and untampered attendance reports. The match index, representing the smallest difference between face encodings in the live video capture and the database, underpins the system's real-time implementation. A confidence threshold of 0.6 is set by default, and if the

match index value falls below this threshold, the face is recognized and identified as the same. Figure 5.4 illustrates the relationship between the confidence score from live image capture and the face distance (i.e., match index) of images in the dataset. Subsequently, student attendance is recorded in a CSV file, including only the names of students whose faces were successfully scanned and recognized.

In this research, we employ the CNN algorithm to create an automated classroom attendance system that identifies students' faces and records their attendance seamlessly. This system significantly saves time and effort, especially in classes with a large number of students. The proposed method leverages face recognition technology and a camera to establish a simple yet effective approach to tracking student attendance. Once faces are matched, their presence or absence is documented in a database. The system automatically marks student attendance in the classroom by comparing captured images with the database records. Faculty members can monitor attendance status and receive email notifications when students are absent. Additionally, automated text messages can be sent to students in cases of prolonged absence, ensuring efficient attendance tracking throughout courses and lectures.

5.5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This work has successfully implemented a system for the automatic marking and storage of class attendance. The implementation process encompasses student data input, training dataset preparation, facial recognition, and automated attendance marking. The employed CNN model demonstrates the ability to detect and recognize individuals based on their facial features, even when they are not facing the camera directly. The proposed system achieves an impressive maximum accuracy rate of approximately 92%, streamlining the task for teachers and eliminating the need for manual attendance record-keeping. To ensure the system's optimal effectiveness, it is crucial to maintain a consistent dataset with a satisfactory number of images for each person during the training phase. Additionally, the camera should be strategically positioned to have a clear view of all students. Furthermore, this system extends its utility to various organizations for automatic staff attendance recording.

Moreover, this work holds potential for multiple security applications that require authentication for system access. It can be employed to identify individuals engaging in

unauthorized activities, contributing to enhanced security. Enhancements to the face recognition algorithm can be pursued to optimize resource utilization, enabling the system to recognize a larger number of faces simultaneously. This adaptability opens up possibilities for home security and personal or organizational benefits. The system's capabilities even extend to quick and efficient tracking of specific individuals within an organization, enhancing its overall versatility and utility.

CHAPTER 6

SMART HOME AUTOMATION – A DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION USING IOT

6.1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) encompasses a network of physical objects, known as "things," equipped with sensors, software, and various technologies to facilitate data exchange and connectivity with other devices and systems via the internet. These devices span from everyday household items to advanced industrial tools. The current count of over 7 billion connected IoT devices is projected to escalate to 10 billion by 2020 and a staggering 22 billion by 2025. IoT has rapidly evolved into one of the paramount technologies of the 21st century. By enabling the connection of commonplace objects—such as kitchen appliances, cars, thermostats, and baby monitors—to the internet through embedded devices, it has ushered in an era of seamless communication between individuals, processes, and things. Utilizing cost-effective computing, cloud infrastructure, big data, analytics, and mobile technologies, physical objects can efficiently share and gather data with minimal human intervention. In this hyperconnected landscape, digital systems meticulously record, monitor, and optimize interactions between interconnected things, bridging the physical and digital realms. IoT empowers individuals to live and work more intelligently while gaining comprehensive control over various aspects of their lives. Beyond its utility for home automation, IoT plays a pivotal role in the business sphere. It furnishes enterprises with real-time insights into the functioning of their systems, providing invaluable information on machine performance, supply chain operations, and logistics processes.

IoT, also referred to as the Web of Things, is an emerging technology that allows the remote control of electrical devices through the internet. This model demonstrates the use of IoT to automate household appliances, specifically focusing on controlling house lighting and a fan. The user-friendly interface facilitates easy remote control of these home appliances via the internet. The system employs an AVR family microcontroller, which is connected to a Wi-Fi modem to receive user instructions online. Additionally, an LCD display is integrated to provide system status updates. Relays are employed to switch the loads, and the entire system

is powered by a 12 V transformer. After receiving user instructions via the internet, the microcontroller processes these commands to operate the loads accordingly and displays the system status on the LCD screen.

Figure 6.1: Home Automation and their overview

The proliferation of the Internet of Things (IoT) has extended its reach to encompass simple in-home applications and everyday tasks. IoT's role in homes primarily revolves around energy monitoring and conservation while maintaining a desired level of comfort. Home automation systems employing IoT consist of three major components, as illustrated in Figure 1. The first component is the sensing and data acquisition part. This involves the placement of sensors or devices, often referred to as "things," at various locations within the home to measure and gather essential data, such as temperature, humidity, or light levels. The second segment of the system is data processing. Sensors provide data in raw form, which is transmitted to the processor via a mode of communication, such as wired connections or wireless transmission. The processor then translates this data into understandable values. These values are transmitted to a device for automated control and may also be accessible via a user interface. The final aspect of IoT automation is the internet. Most systems utilize a server to upload processed data, making it accessible to the user. The internet also allows for data monitoring and remote manual control of devices. Through the automated execution of various commands, automation systems can save time, enhance the quality of life in homes, and conserve energy.

Efforts to develop energy-efficient and sustainable energy technologies have become a global priority. Universities have played a significant role in this technological advancement

through student competitions aimed at raising awareness. One such competition is the Solar Decathlon, which has been held in the United States and other countries worldwide. The Solar Decathlon Middle East (SDME) is a newly established competition in the Middle East region, scheduled to take place in Dubai in 2018. Qatar University's participation in the SDME 2018 competition has enabled the formation of a multidisciplinary team of students who will collaborate on designing and constructing a green, smart, portable, and affordable solar house. This energy-efficient house will be fully monitored and automated using Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, contributing to sustainable energy practices (Patnaikuni, 2012).

6.2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Home automation systems utilizing smartphone integration, Arduino boards, and Bluetooth technology offer a cost-effective and secure solution. A Bluetooth-based home automation system, as proposed by Riyale and M. Tazil, employs a PC or smartphone as the receiver device, benefiting from high communication rates, robust security, and affordability, making it suitable for real-time implementation [96]. However, it suffers from a limited communication range of 10 meters, posing a disadvantage if the smartphone moves out of this range. Voice recognition-based home automation systems, another innovative approach, rely on wireless communication between smartphones and Arduino UNO through Bluetooth technology. This approach is particularly advantageous for individuals with disabilities or the elderly who can control appliances using voice commands. Nonetheless, its effectiveness depends on the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and noisy voice signals can negatively impact communication accuracy. ZigBee-based wireless home automation systems have also been explored, similar to Bluetooth but with a broader range. ZigBee offers low data rates and power consumption, making it ideal for prototyping and research purposes [98]. A GSM-based smart home automation system utilizes Global System for Mobile communication for communication between the central module and appliances via text messages. However, the unreliability of text message delivery is a notable drawback.

To address these drawbacks, an "IoT-Based Smart Security and Smart Home Automation" approach is proposed. IoT allows for remote sensing and control of objects over existing network infrastructure, enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and economic benefits. The advent of 5G LTE cellular technology further accelerates the development of IoT-based home

automation systems [99]. When IoT is integrated with sensors and actuators, it falls under the category of cyber-physical systems, enabling control of various home appliances based on sensor data. The proposed system connects sensor data to users' daily lives, offering simplified control and monitoring experiences. PIC16F887 microcontroller and GSM technology are employed for home appliance control, but the cost of SMS and the absence of a centralized controller are limitations. Another approach involves Arduino boards controlled via GSM technology, where smartphone applications generate SMS messages to control home appliances through the GSM modem attached to the Arduino [89]. While this system offers versatility, it also faces challenges related to SMS reliability and lack of device customization. In a different setup, Arduino boards and Bluetooth boards are employed for home automation, with a Python program on the smartphone serving as the user interface. The Bluetooth connection is password-protected for security, and relays are used for device interfacing. However, Bluetooth's limited range is a consideration in this setup..

6.3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This IoT-based home appliance control system capitalizes on the evolving digital landscape, adapting to daily needs and leveraging technology for both professional and household applications. The system is divided into two main components: hardware and software. The hardware comprises components such as NodeMCU (microcontroller), relays, an exhaust fan LED, and a bulb. The software component is a dedicated Android Blynk app and a server.

The user interacts with the system through a user-configurable web page (Blynk app) for load control and monitoring. Commands are transmitted via an allowed IP address to the Wi-Fi module of the NodeMCU microcontroller within the circuit. The Wi-Fi module is configured to access the internet through a wireless modem. Upon receiving commands, the Wi-Fi module's internal program processes and executes them. To enable home control using a smartphone, the mobile device must connect to a network, while the Wi-Fi module (ESP8266) on the ESP32 should be connected to the local network. The Blynk app facilitates user interaction by allowing users to touch specific widgets that send ON/OFF commands to the ESP32 via the Blynk server. Consequently, the relays connected to the ESP32 perform switching operations corresponding to the input, thereby controlling the loads connected to

these relays. Additionally, manual switches can be used to control home appliances by connecting the relay outputs to manual switches and then to the AC loads. Whenever the relay corresponding to a manual ON/OFF switch is activated, the connected AC loads will be switched ON/OFF accordingly.

6.3.1. SMART HOME AUTOMATION ARCHITECTURE

To enable home control via a smartphone, the initial steps involve connecting the mobile device to any network, and the Wi-Fi module ESP8266, which is part of the ESP32, should be connected to the local network. Within the Blynk app, users can interact by tapping specific widgets, prompting the Blynk app to transmit ON/OFF commands to the ESP32 via the Blynk server. As a result, the relays connected to the ESP32 execute switching operations corresponding to the user's input, thereby controlling the loads connected to these relays. A similar level of control can also be achieved using manual switches. This is accomplished by connecting the relay outputs to manual switches and then linking these manual switches to the AC loads. When the relay corresponding to a manual ON or OFF switch is activated, the AC loads connected to that switch will perform the switching operation.

As previously mentioned, the selected parameters for monitoring within homes are carefully chosen to ensure a smart, efficient, and comfortable living environment. As a result, the system focuses on measuring temperature, humidity, light intensity, proximity, and CO2 levels. This monitoring can be implemented in every room of the house, ideally positioned at an elevated level above the ground and below the ceiling. The collected data can be processed and used to control smart devices like intelligent LEDs and air conditioners. The schematic of the proposed system setup is illustrated in Figure 2, which primarily consists of sensors, a processor, a user interface, and data communication and transmission links. For temperature sensing, the LM35 temperature sensor is employed, while the HIH4000 sensor is used for humidity detection. The selection of these sensors is based on their compact size and cost-effectiveness compared to other options such as the DHT22 sensor. These sensors serve as key components of the home automation system, enabling the collection of essential data for efficient control and management.

Figure 6.2: Smart Home Automation Architecture

Home automation is a sophisticated network comprising hardware components, communication interfaces, and electronic sensors that collaborate to seamlessly connect everyday devices through the internet. These devices are equipped with sensors and connected via Wi-Fi, enabling users to control them remotely using their smartphones or tablets, regardless of their location, whether it's within the confines of their home or miles away. This technology empowers individuals to perform various tasks such as lighting control, front door locking, real-time weather monitoring, fire detection, and window management, all accessible through remote control capabilities.

Home automation works on three levels:

- **Monitoring:** Monitoring means that users can check in on devices remotely through an app. For example, someone could view their live feed from a smart security camera.
- **Control:** Control means that the user can control these devices remotely, like panning a security camera to see more a living space.
- **Automation:** Finally, automation means setting up devices to trigger one another, like having a smart siren go off whenever an armed security camera detects motion. Sensors can monitor changes in daylight, temperature, or motion detection. Home automation systems can then adjust those settings (and more) to your preferences.

In the realm of home automation, controllers play a crucial role as they are the devices employed, such as personal computers, tablets, or smartphones, to transmit and receive messages pertaining to the status of various automated features within the home. Actuators, on the other hand, encompass components like light switches, motors, or motorized valves that govern the physical mechanisms or functions of a home automation system. These actuators are meticulously programmed to execute specific actions in response to remote commands issued from a controller. In this particular project, a diverse array of sensors is utilized for creating a smart home automation, monitoring, and alerting system. These sensors encompass the MQ2 sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, DHT22 sensor, LM393 LDR Sensor, TSOP sensor, and MC38 sensor. The MQ2 sensor, for instance, is adept at smoke detection, while the DHT22 sensor functions as a temperature sensor, enabling the regulation of fans based on temperature readings. Furthermore, the LM393 LDR sensor facilitates automatic light control, and the MC38 sensor is employed for monitoring doors and windows, enhancing the overall security of the home.

6.3.2. ARDUINO MICROCONTROLLER

The system is powered by an Atmega2560 microprocessor. This microcontroller contains 256 KB of memory, 8 KB of which is utilised by the bootloader Flash programme memory and 8 KB of static random access memory (SRAM). The hardware is separated into four sections: the LCD display interface portion, the RFID module interface section, the soil moisture sensor, and the float sensor. The ATmega2560 microcontroller controls all of these elements, and the software necessary to operate them is the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE). It contains 54 digital I/O pins (14 of which are PWM outputs), 16 analogue I/O pins, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power connector, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It comes with everything you need to support the microcontroller; just connect it to a computer through USB or power it using an AC-to-DC converter or battery to get started. Most shields produced for the Arduino Duemilanove or Diecimila are compatible with the Mega.

Figure 6.3: Block Diagram of Arduino MEGA2560

6.3.3. USE CASE 1: USER ACCESS TO THE SYSTEM

The EM-18 125kHz RFID Reader module is a low-cost option for any RFID-based project. The Reader module has a built-in antenna and requires a 5V supply to function. Turn on the module and connect its transmit pin to the microcontroller's reception pin. If you hold your card close enough to the reader, it will read the number and send it to the output. The module's output type may be changed to Weigand if desired. There are two main components of an RFID-based system.

Figure 6.4: User access to the system

Home automation constitutes a sophisticated network of interconnected hardware components, communication systems, and electronic interfaces, all designed to seamlessly integrate everyday devices via the internet. Each of these devices is equipped with sensors and connected through Wi-Fi, enabling users to exercise control and management from their smartphones or tablets, whether they are within the confines of their home or miles away. This level of connectivity and control facilitates a wide range of functionalities, including the ability to remotely activate lights, secure the front door, monitor weather conditions, detect fires, control windows, and perform various remote operations. Home automation operates on three fundamental levels:

Monitoring: This level empowers users to remotely monitor the status and activities of their devices through dedicated apps. For instance, individuals can access live feeds from smart security cameras to keep a vigilant eye on their property.

Control: Control entails the user's capacity to manipulate these connected devices from afar, such as adjusting the view of a security camera to survey different areas within a living space.

Automation: Automation represents the highest level of home automation, involving the configuration of devices to trigger one another based on predefined conditions. For instance, users can set up a smart siren to activate automatically when an armed security camera detects motion, enhancing the security measures in place.

Figure 6.5: System control

Sensors play a pivotal role in the realm of home automation by continuously monitoring changes in various environmental parameters such as daylight, temperature, or motion detection. These sensors serve as the eyes and ears of a smart home system, collecting data that can be used to make real-time adjustments and optimizations tailored to the user's preferences. Controllers, on the other hand, are the command centers of home automation systems. These controllers, which can be personal computers, tablets, or smartphones, serve as the communication hub through which messages about the status and actions of automated features in the home are sent and received.

Actuators represent the physical agents responsible for executing actions within a home automation system. These devices can take the form of light switches, motors, or motorized valves, and they are programmed to respond to remote commands issued by the controller. In the context of a specific project, a variety of sensors are employed for a smart home automation, monitoring, and alerting system. These sensors include the MQ2 sensor, which specializes in smoke detection, the Ultrasonic sensor, DHT22 sensor designed for temperature monitoring and fan control, the LM393 LDR Sensor for automatic light control, the TSOP sensor, and the MC38 sensor, which is utilized for door and window control. Additionally, the system is equipped with two CPU cores that can be independently controlled, with an adjustable clock frequency ranging from 80 MHz to 240 MHz. Moreover, a low-power co-processor is available to constantly monitor peripherals for changes or threshold crossings, ensuring efficient and responsive automation.

Figure 6.6: Class Diagram

6.4. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The method for IoT-based controlled home appliances is at the forefront of harnessing advanced technology to meet the evolving needs of our increasingly digital world. In a rapidly changing landscape, where everyday requirements and home applications are being reimaged, this method stands as a testament to the power of technology in both professional and domestic settings. The project is structured into two fundamental components: hardware and software.

The hardware component comprises essential elements such as the NodeMCU microcontroller, relays, exhaust fans, LEDs, and bulbs. These hardware components work in tandem to enable the automation and control of home appliances, offering a seamless and integrated experience. On the software front, this method relies primarily on the Android BLYNKapp and server. This software solution serves as the digital bridge that connects users to their home appliances. It provides an intuitive and user-friendly interface for controlling and

monitoring the connected devices. Users have the flexibility to configure and customize their control settings through a web page accessed via the BLYNK app. Commands issued by the user through allowed IP addresses are transmitted to the Wi-Fi module of the NodeMCU microcontroller within the circuit, facilitating efficient and responsive control over the connected appliances. This method represents a fusion of cutting-edge technology and user-centric design, offering a glimpse into the future of smart home automation.

Figure 6.7: Schematic Diagram

The Wi-Fi module is an integral part of the system, and its configuration allows for seamless internet access through any wireless modem. Commands directed at the Wi-Fi module are executed by a program embedded within it. To enable smart home control via a smartphone, an initial step involves ensuring that the mobile device is connected to a network. Simultaneously, the Wi-Fi module, represented by the ESP8266 within the ESP32, should establish a connection with the local network. The heart of the control mechanism lies within the BLYNK app, where users can interact with the system by simply touching specified widgets. These interactions trigger the BLYNK app to send precise ON/OFF commands to the ESP32 via the BLYNK server. Subsequently, the relays that are interconnected with the ESP32 come into play, performing switching operations that correspond to the received input. This orchestration enables the activation and deactivation of the connected loads, offering users remote control over their home appliances.

In addition to remote control, manual switches can also be employed to manage home appliances. This integration is achieved by connecting the outputs of the relays to manual switches, and then linking these manual switches to the AC loads. When a user activates the relay corresponding to a specific manual ON or OFF switch, the AC loads associated with that switch respond by executing the corresponding switching operation. This system design provides users with the flexibility to control their home appliances either remotely through the app or through manual switches, ensuring a user-friendly and adaptable experience.

Figure 6.8: Flow Chart

6.5. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The meeting is vital strategies that will be utilized for the accumulate of information and help the analyzer to comprehend the framework necessities, so by the utilization of this methods the met by the distinctive arrangement of home clients for social occasion what kind of home computerization highlights required through this meeting the questioner has tended to various inquiries to the dependable people and he has gathered toward the finish of the meeting the accompanying information:

1. Lock and open your entryway effortlessly by mean of a cell phone or one of the included keen labels. You can even deal with different properties at once, controlling who approaches the keys from wherever you are on the planet. Not at all like many savvy entryway bolts, this one needn't bother with Bluetooth to work.
2. The shrewd bolt transforms your iPhone into your key and is additionally good with the scope of Weiser Smart Key bolts and keys, so can without much of a stretch incorporate it into your home's present bolt framework. The portable application gives a chance to deal with your keys and bolt from anyplace.
3. The sensor will let remotely screen anything need that opens and closes, and, on account of Z-wave innovation, is good with a large group of keen home systems administration center points.
4. The remote sensors make for a helpful, ongoing observing framework. With almost boundless expandability, you'll never need to stress over having the capacity to screen your entire home, regardless of what estimate it is.
5. Get genuine feelings of serenity by knowing who's traveling every which way from your home with sensors on your home's entryways and windows. This Z-wave fueled unit will send an alarm to tell when the sensor has been broken.
6. With advances in innovation, now can introduce your own special home checking framework for substantially less than the cost of customary security frameworks. This model has all that have to get fully operational rapidly.

As previously mentioned, the selection of monitored parameters in homes is carefully tailored to ensure an intelligent, efficient, and comfortable living environment. Therefore, a

primary focus is placed on measuring temperature, humidity, light intensity, proximity, and CO₂ levels. This sensor array can be strategically placed in each room of the house, ideally positioned at an elevated level above the ground and below the ceiling. The data collected from these sensors is then processed and utilized to control smart devices, such as intelligent LED lighting systems and air conditioning units. The schematic representation of the proposed system setup is depicted in Figure 6.8, outlining its essential components, including sensors, processors, user interface, and data communication and transmission links. In the realm of sensors, the design commenced with a focus on temperature and humidity measurements. For temperature sensing, the LM35 temperature sensor was chosen, while the HIH4000 sensor was selected for humidity detection. These choices were primarily motivated by the compact sizes of these sensors compared to alternative options, such as the DHT22 sensor, as well as their cost-effectiveness. This sensor arrangement forms the foundation for gathering essential environmental data within the home, enabling intelligent control and management of various systems and devices.

6.6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This system can be further enhanced by incorporating various sensors and integrating additional home appliances. Given the widespread use of smartphones in today's society, this user-friendly system has the potential to benefit a large number of people. Moreover, the affordability of the system makes it accessible to a broad audience. The circuit designed for controlling AC fan speed can also be adapted for AC light dimming applications. The system's features, such as automatic shutdown and emergency notifications, can be particularly valuable for devices like geysers and air conditioners. For instance, the system can automatically turn off a geyser when the water reaches a specific temperature or switch off an air conditioner when the room temperature falls below a predefined value. In both cases, notifications can be sent to the user through their Blynk app. Mobile application development companies with dedicated teams are actively working on IoT-based applications connected to the cloud. This technology isn't limited to older individuals or those with physical challenges; anyone with a smartphone can easily monitor and control electronic devices. As awareness of these possibilities grows, the adoption of IoT-based mobility solutions is likely to increase, automating various business operations and end-to-end processes.

IoT has a wide range of applications across various sectors, and it plays a significant role in our daily lives. The relentless pace of technological advancement in this information age is reshaping how we interact with technology. The potential for IoT extends beyond personal use; it can be extended to industrial sectors, including areas like hazard detection in mines, laboratories, and vehicles. As we continue to embrace technology, it becomes an integral part of our evolution as a species, enabling us to navigate the challenges and opportunities of the modern world.

CHAPTER 7

SMART VILLAGE – A DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MODERN VILLAGE USING ESP32 MICROCONTROLLER

7.1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) brings automation to operations and reduces labor costs, leading to more efficient processes. It also minimizes waste and improves service delivery, ultimately lowering manufacturing and delivery expenses. IoT has become a pivotal technology in our daily lives, and its significance will only continue to grow as more businesses recognize the potential of interconnected devices to stay competitive. Much like how the internet revolutionized knowledge work, IoT has the potential to enhance production and distribution systems in enterprises. With billions of internet-enabled sensors embedded worldwide, businesses can access a wealth of data to enhance safety, monitor assets, and streamline human processes. Machine data can even predict equipment failures, helping manufacturers avoid extended downtime.

However, it's essential to note that IoT devices can also collect user preferences and behavioral data, raising concerns about privacy and security. The foundation of an IoT system lies in data-gathering devices, all of which are internet-connected and possess unique IP addresses. These devices range from autonomous mobile robots and forklifts used in factories and warehouses to simple sensors that detect variables like temperature and gas leaks. Even everyday devices like fitness trackers that count steps fall under the IoT umbrella. The IoT process involves these devices sending data to a central location, with data transmission occurring through wireless or wired networks. This data often ends up in a data center or the cloud, where intermediary.

Figure 7.1: IOT application diagram

The Most Significant Advantages of IOT

a) Improve Customer Service and Experience

The IoT makes your consumers' everyday gadgets remarkable. Check whether IoT can enhance goods and services. IoT-integrated automobiles calculate travel duration, traffic, and fuel usage. A smart doorbell that shows visitors while you're away. Refrigerators detect low supply. A weather-responsive AC system.

b) Increase New Business and Revenue Opportunities

IoT offers new business possibilities by enabling new consumer and business flow interactions.

c) Enhance Business Safety and Security

IoT devices monitor buildings and businesses to safeguard people from physical hazards. Businesses can monitor office premises and secure assets using IoT devices including sensors, cameras, and smart locks. Track and warn high-risk workers in manufacturing, real estate, and construction.

d) Improve Productivity and Competence

Smart IoT devices can do repetitive company duties better since they don't sleep, eat, have mood swings, or get sick.

e) Cut down Operational Costs

Improved productivity, process efficiency, and asset utilization will all contribute to cost savings. Predictive analytics and real-time diagnostics, for example, may assist reduce maintenance costs in a variety of businesses.

f) Collect Data for Business Decisions

Companies may use IoT to monitor and collect critical data sets that will help them enhance their services and products. This information may help with company analysis and decision-making.

g) Add Mobility and Agility to Business

IoT technology allows businesses to let their staff and workers conduct their work from literally anywhere. This flexibility can help many companies cost saving as office leases are expensive, hiring many remote employees.

7.2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This paper presents an exploration of IoT-based Smart Villages, a concept driven by the Internet of Things (IoT), which enables seamless data transfer across networks without the need for human-to-human handshaking [92]. IoT provides the infrastructure for universal connectivity, allowing for anytime, anywhere connections with anything and anyone, leveraging various network topologies and services. This has given rise to diverse interpretations of what constitutes a "Smart Globe," all centered around utilizing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Internet Technologies to address rural challenges [95]. To delve into the practical application, we turn our attention to agriculture, where ecosystem control technology has evolved to a level of high intelligence [94]. This underscores the importance of efficiency, quality, security, and sustainability in agricultural production. It culminates in the concept of smart irrigation, which is part of the broader idea of "Smart Farming" and, ultimately, a "Smart Village" [98]. The essence of this lies in the implementation of IoT technologies, their applications, and their transformative potential.

The primary goal of this project is to create a Smart Village, following the principles established for Smart Cities but adapted to a location untouched by modern civilization [103]. A remote and isolated village serves as the canvas for this endeavor, with the design aiming for self-sufficiency in electric power, water supply, street lighting, security, education, and

communication [107]. Key to this self-sufficiency is the application of non-conventional methods of energy generation, including solar heat capture and storage. IoT plays a crucial role in controlling embedded devices through the internet [106]. Furthermore, energy-efficient street lighting with adjustable intensity and innovative water supply solutions are integral components of this vision. A Smart Village, in this context, is defined as a village equipped with modern technology while preserving nature [109]. It addresses common issues in villages such as waste management, water supply, and electrical problems, offering solutions through IoT [101]. The proposed system envisions a future where IoT becomes a pervasive communication paradigm, connecting everyday objects and users seamlessly [108]. The paper also highlights the pressing need for waste management, emphasizing the role of IoT modules in tracking and managing waste bins and locations [100]. It explores the use of IR sensors to detect waste levels and proposes Wi-Fi communication for efficient real-time notifications [101]. Additionally, it draws attention to the significant waste generated by buildings and the potential for better waste regulation through IoT [106]. The survey of literature in this domain underscores the importance of these technologies in addressing critical challenges [105].

7.3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our project's primary objective is to identify and sense garbage in our environment efficiently. To achieve this, we employ both IR sensors and Moisture sensors. In our daily lives, we encounter two types of waste: dry waste and wet waste. To differentiate between these two categories, we utilize a moisture sensor to detect wet waste and an IR sensor to identify dry waste. The entire system is built around the ESP32 Microcontroller, which possesses the necessary capabilities to perform garbage detection tasks effectively. Upon detecting garbage, the system triggers a notification to an authorized person via the Blynk app. This real-time communication through the Blynk app allows us to promptly receive notifications when garbage is detected, enhancing our waste management system.

7.3.1. SMART VILLAGE ARCHITECTURE

Our project encompasses the development of two distinct applications: garbage management and water level control. In both applications, we employ IoT technology to upload and store data in the Blynk app, effectively creating a cloud-based storage system. This system

continuously updates itself as new sensor data becomes available. Various sensors play pivotal roles in these applications: an Ambient sensor for detecting odors, a PIR sensor to assess waste levels in a waste container, a Moisture sensor to distinguish between dry and wet waste, a Liquid level sensor to monitor water levels in a tank, and a float sensor to control the opening and closing of the water tank valve. To enable internet connectivity and facilitate data uploads, we utilize the ESP32, a Wi-Fi module. The ESP32 microcontroller serves as the central processing unit for these applications, managing the various sensors and their inputs and outputs. It operates as a versatile board with multiple input and output pins. Moreover, it incorporates conditional logic, which allows it to progress to the next steps in the process when specific conditions are met. This comprehensive setup ensures efficient garbage management and water level control, providing valuable data and automation capabilities.

Figure 7.2: Smart Village Architecture

In these two applications, once the device is initiated, it promptly displays the garbage level in the waste box and the water level in the tank. These values are obtained from the respective sensors and are presented on the device screen. When waste is deposited into the waste bin, the system detects whether it is wet or dry waste, subsequently opening the appropriate tray. For instance, if the waste is dry, the dry tray is opened, whereas if it's wet waste, the wet tray is activated. The system continuously updates the status by uploading data to the database through the Blynk app. The PIR sensor plays a crucial role in monitoring the fill level of waste in the waste bin, while the ambient sensor is employed to assess the odor level within the bin. Based on these levels, if the tank reaches 90% of its maximum capacity,

an alert message is generated to prompt the relevant person to clean the waste bin. Additionally, if a strong odor is detected by the ambient sensor, it triggers an alert message to the authorized individual for immediate cleaning.

Regarding the water tank, if the water level falls below 10% of its maximum capacity, a signal is sent to the ESP32, instructing it to activate the motor pump. The motor driver then receives a trigger signal to switch on the motor. The system verifies the water level using the float sensor, and if the water is at a sufficient level, the pump remains on; otherwise, it is turned off. The pump's status, whether it is on or off, is continually updated and uploaded to the cloud, ensuring efficient water management.

7.3.2. ESP32 MICRO CONTROLLER

A few years ago, the ESP8266 made a significant impact on the embedded IoT landscape. With its affordability of less than \$3, it provided a programmable, WiFi-enabled microcontroller capable of monitoring and controlling devices from virtually anywhere in the world. Now, Espressif, the semiconductor company behind the ESP8266, has introduced an impressive upgrade: the ESP32. As the successor to the ESP8266, the ESP32 not only retains WiFi support but also boasts Bluetooth 4.0 (BLE/Bluetooth Smart), making it an ideal choice for a wide range of IoT projects. Traditionally, when contemplating a microcontroller for a project, Arduino comes to mind. Arduino is known for its affordability, user-friendliness, a generous number of digital I/O ports, and a handful of analog inputs. However, despite its many merits, Arduino has its limitations. Notably, it operates at a speed of 16 MHz, which, while suitable for numerous applications, can be a bottleneck for others. While Arduino offers ample digital and analog inputs and outputs for most needs, adding features like WiFi and Bluetooth often requires external components. It's worth noting that Arduino has been in the market since 2005, which, in the realm of technology, is a considerable duration. In contrast, the ESP32, a series of microcontroller chips developed by Espressif Systems in Shanghai, provides a compelling alternative. It is available in various low-cost modules, offering enhanced capabilities and versatility for modern IoT applications.

Figure 7.3: ESP-WROOM-32 Module

The development board is equipped with the ESP-WROOM-32 module, which houses the Tensilica Xtensa Dual-Core 32-bit LX6 microprocessor. This processor, while sharing similarities with the ESP8266, distinguishes itself by featuring two CPU cores, each individually controllable. It operates within an adjustable clock frequency range of 80 to 240 MHz and can achieve performance levels of up to 600 DMIPS (Dhrystone Million Instructions Per Second). The ESP32-WROOM-32 (ESP-WROOM-32) stands out as a versatile and potent Wi-Fi+BT+BLE MCU module, catering to a broad spectrum of applications. These applications range from low-power sensor networks to demanding tasks like voice encoding, music streaming, and MP3 decoding. The module's core is built around the ESP32-D0WDQ6 chip, designed to be both scalable and adaptive. It incorporates two CPU cores that can be independently controlled, with the clock frequency adjustable from 80 MHz to 240 MHz. Users can even power off the CPU and leverage the low-power co-processor to continually monitor peripherals for changes or threshold crossings.

The ESP32 boasts an array of peripherals, including capacitive touch sensors, Hall sensors, an SD card interface, Ethernet, high-speed SPI, UART, I2S, and I2C. With integrated Bluetooth, Bluetooth LE, and Wi-Fi capabilities, it accommodates a wide range of applications and ensures future-proofing. Wi-Fi offers an expansive physical range and direct internet connectivity via a Wi-Fi router, while Bluetooth allows convenient smartphone pairing and broadcasting of low-energy beacons for detection. Impressively, the ESP32 chip's sleep current remains under 5 μA , making it well-suited for battery-powered and wearable electronic devices. The ESP32 supports data rates of up to 150 Mbps and delivers an output power of 20.5 dBm at the antenna, ensuring extensive coverage. It sets industry-leading standards for

specifications, performance, integration, power efficiency, and connectivity. The chosen operating system for the ESP32 is freeRTOS with LwIP, and it includes TLS 1.2 with hardware acceleration. Furthermore, secure over-the-air (OTA) upgrades are supported, enabling developers to continually enhance their products even after their initial release.

7.3.3. PIR SENSOR

An infrared sensor is basically an electronic device which is used to detect the presence of objects. PIR is emitted by this device. If this device does not detect any IR light reflected back that means there is no object present. If the light is detected by the sensor there is an object present. Its Range is up to 10 meters.

7.3.4. BLYNK IOT

Blynk is a Server and APP Service providing Platform. It provides High Security Service and Server for IOT applications. This is easy to use and supports all advance Micro controllers. The focus of the Blynk platform is to develop the mobile phone application. Blynk is free to use for personal use and prototyping. Blynk also supports clients that are not a microcontroller.

Figure 7.4: Blynk App

7.3.5. FLOAT SENSOR

The level of liquid in a tank may be determined via a float switch. The flipped switch might start a pump, activate an indicator, sound an alarm, or do anything else. Hydroponics, saltwater tanks, freshwater tanks, gardening, aquariums, pet bowls, fish tanks, filtration, heating, pumps, and ponds may all benefit from using them to regulate the power heads of their respective systems.

7.3.6. WATER PUMP

The R385 6-12V DC Diaphragm Based Mini Aquarium Water Pump is a great all-around non-submersible pump. With the addition of a nozzle, it may be utilised as a spray system due to its high pressure. This submersible pump may be used to water plants, build a waterfall or fountain, and even clean the water in a fish tank. It generates less than 30 decibels of noise when in operation. The pump is equipped with a filter and a suction cup for stable attachment to flat surfaces.

7.4. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The ESP8266 serves as a crucial Wi-Fi module that establishes a connection to a Wi-Fi hotspot, enabling internet connectivity. It interfaces with the Arduino board to facilitate the transmission of waste bin management data, float sensor readings, and pump switch ON/OFF states to the IoT server (Blynk). The ESP8266 also plays a pivotal role in monitoring the water level in the tank. When water is available, it triggers the pump to irrigate the plants. However, if the water level drops below a certain threshold or the soil moisture is sufficient, the pump is automatically turned off. The issue of garbage management has escalated, posing a significant challenge to maintaining urban cleanliness. Many areas in cities lack public garbage bins, leading to the indiscriminate disposal of waste on roadsides and in corners, creating unsightly and unhygienic conditions. Inadequate waste disposal contributes to blockages in water reservoirs and drainage systems, particularly during the rainy season, leading to water overflow and transportation disruptions. Open garbage containers also become breeding grounds for disease-carrying insects like mosquitoes and germs, further exacerbating public health concerns. Moreover, the irregular cleaning of garbage bins in these areas compounds the problem.

To address these issues, there is a pressing need for the adoption of smart waste management and monitoring systems, driven by IoT (Internet of Things) technology. This paradigm shift towards IoT can optimize garbage management processes, reduce fuel consumption associated with current systems, and improve environmental sustainability. Numerous projects have successfully implemented smart garbage management and monitoring systems using IoT technology, demonstrating their effectiveness in mitigating environmental challenges.

Figure 7.5: Schematic Diagram

The Internet of Things (IoT) has become a pervasive influence in our daily lives, revolutionizing various aspects of society. One innovative application of IoT is the garbage monitoring system, which plays a crucial role in maintaining the cleanliness of our cities. Smart garbage bins are equipped with Ultrasonic Sensors positioned on their lids, enabling them to detect the garbage levels inside. This real-time data is then accessible through a dedicated webpage. The system compares the garbage level with the bin's capacity to ensure efficient monitoring. Key components of this system include an AVR family Microcontroller, a Wi-Fi modem, an LCD display, a buzzer, and a 12V transformer.

The Wi-Fi modem plays a central role in transmitting the collected data. Users can conveniently access the garbage status via the webpage, where the information is presented in a graphical format. The garbage levels are displayed using different colors, enhancing the visual representation of data. To prevent overflowing, the bins are set with a predefined limit. When the garbage surpasses this limit, a buzzer is activated, serving as an alert mechanism to notify users of the need to empty the bin, contributing to the upkeep of a clean environment.

Figure 7.6: Flow Chart for attendance

If the moisture is more than 350, we may consider the waste bin to be dry. It then proceeds to the next stage, which is to check the water level in the tank. If the water level is below the minimum needed level, the controller will switch on the pump, and the float sensor value is 1. The pump will switch off automatically, and the status of pump turn on/off will be uploaded into the IOT app (blynk). If the moisture is less than 350, the pump will not check for water level and will not turn on. The flowchart will appear below. As per conditions, the

water supply will be only turn ON when the water is sufficient and if the ground dryness is high as per, we programmed in the code.

7.5. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

Here we see a true SMART VILLAGE- A Digital Transformation of Modern Village Using ESP32 Microcontroller in action. The BLYNK app, an IoT platform, will receive data from the sensors and monitored by the system that we developed.

Figure 7.7: Experimental Results

7.5.1. NUMERICAL REPRESENTATION OF INPUT CORRESPONDING OUTPUT ELEMENT

Component	INPUT	OUTPUT
Ambient Sensor	Check Odour	Verify the records and send the information to the server. Information sent via message to authorized person to clean.
PIR Sensor	Check the level in waste bin	Verify this with the data bank. Based on the level reached 80% of total capacity alert will be given to the authorized person.
Moisture Sensor	Moisture value>350	Based on moisture level the wet waste and dry waste is separated.

Liquid Level Sensor	Water Level $\geq 90\%$	The water level should be checked. When sensing an adequate water level, the pump will activate and a corresponding data set will be sent to the server.
Float Sensor	Open or close valve	It will stop pumping and send a file to the server.

Table 7.1: Numerical representation of Results

7.6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The primary objective of this paper was to evaluate and analyze the performance of the implemented system. Through thorough testing and assessment, we have successfully demonstrated the project's effectiveness and fulfillment of its goals. It has become evident that this initiative holds immense significance, particularly in rural areas, as it enhances the management of garbage and water tanks. The project has not only met its objectives but has also yielded exceptional results. The study has addressed its limitations and provided recommendations for potential solutions, as outlined in the suggestions for future research.

In this project, the integration of a recognition sensor or camera for waste management detection is proposed, representing a more advanced approach compared to the current sensor-based system. This technology could potentially be implemented across various villages at minimal cost, significantly improving waste management practices. Additionally, I recommend incorporating local hosting with internet connectivity to ensure data logging even in the event of internet downtime, enhancing the system's reliability for smart villages.

Future research endeavors can build upon the foundation laid in this project, potentially achieving even higher accuracy by incorporating additional sensors or employing more complex algorithms. However, such advancements will likely become feasible when microprocessors like Arduino release new and more powerful iterations with enhanced capabilities.

CHAPTER 8

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

CONCLUSION

The ultimate objective of this proposed method was to evaluate and assess the performance of the constructed system. Extensive testing and assessment have been conducted, resulting in a design that meets our expectations. This model is forged through a series of advanced computer algorithms. These algorithms meticulously analyze the various components of vegetables to establish a comprehensive set of features associated with micro-plasma impact. This intricate process allows the model to discern patterns and trends within the data, empowering it to make insightful predictions. Once the model is established, it becomes a potent tool for detecting interactions between various types of micro-plasma within vegetables. Consequently, this technology holds potential applications in educational institutions, including colleges and universities. Furthermore, it is advisable to incorporate local hosting with internet connectivity to ensure continuous functionality, particularly in cases where internet connectivity might falter.

FUTURE SCOPE

Future research endeavors stand to gain substantial benefits from the groundwork laid in this project. The potential for increased accuracy lies in the incorporation of additional sensors or the implementation of more sophisticated algorithms. However, this advancement is contingent upon the availability of new and more powerful iterations of microprocessors like Arduino, which would provide the enhanced capabilities necessary to support these advancements.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS

1. Anna Palagan.C, Praveen.B.M, “IoT Implementation of Smart Campus – A Digital Transformation for Green Environment”, Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology, Vol. 44 No.3 (2023), ISSN : 1001-4055, pp. 547 – 555.
2. Anna Palagan.C, Praveen.B.M, “Real Time Implementation of Automatic Moisture and Light Control Protection for Garden”, Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology, Vol. 44 No.2 (2023), ISSN : 1001-4055, pp. 700 – 711.
3. Anna Palagan.C, Praveen.B.M, “Smart Attendance Management System using Convolutional Neural Network”, Multidisciplinary Journal for Applied Research in Engineering and Technology (MJARET), Vol. III Issue.5 (September 2023), ISSN : 2583-1100, pp. 49 – 60.
4. Anna Palagan.C, Praveen.B.M, “Smart Home Automation – A Digital Transformation using IoT”, Multidisciplinary Journal for Applied Research in Engineering and Technology (MJARET), Vol. III Issue.4 (August 2023), ISSN : 2583-1100, pp. 49 – 57.

CONFERENCE PUBLICATIONS

1. Anna Palagan.C, Praveen.B.M, “Smart Village – A Digital Transformation of Modern Village Using ESP32 Microcontroller”, International Conference on Scientific Innovations in Science, Technology and Management (NGCESI-2023).

PATENT PUBLICATIONS

1. Patent Published in the Title of “Design System of Revising Technology Adoption for IoT - based Smart Campuses: A User-Centered Approach (202341064018)” on 06/10/2023.

IoT Implementation of Smart Campus - A Digital Transformation for Green Environment

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Abstract: Everything will soon transition to smart apps thanks to the government of India's effort under the "Smart India" programme. This will be accomplished using the information technology platforms. With fewer features needed than in a smart city, the ideas of a smart city will be applied in a smart campus. All resources on a traditional campus are manually monitored and controlled, but on a smart campus, everything is digitalized. In terms of reducing operating expenses, enhancing efforts, and being timely, digitization will significantly improve. We designed "Smart Campus-Green Environment" to solve all of these problems. For this proposed method, we developed a problem-solving application of plant in terms of Energy efficiency, water conservation, and a speedy sprinkler system for the plant. The operating principle of this technology is based on the process of generating a digital representation of the vegetable, called a "model". This model is used to measure and evaluate the micro-plasma impact of the vegetable in order to identify factors that may be associated with potential health risks.

Keywords: Smart Campus, Internet of Things, Digitalization of attendance, Green environment, Fire management and Energy Efficiency.

1. Introduction

The term "Internet of Things" (IoT) refers to the global network of "things" that have electronics, software, and network connectivity so that they may collect and transmit data and communicate with other devices and systems online (Abuarqoub et al., 2017). Everything from everyday household goods to cutting-edge industrial machinery may be classified as a gadget. More than 7 billion IoT devices are now connected, and this number is expected to grow to 10 billion by 2020 and 22 billion by 2025, according to experts. The Internet of Things (IoT) has quickly become one of the most consequential technologies of the 21st century (Ahmed et al., 2022). The capacity to connect everyday products to the internet via embedded devices has made continuous communication between people, processes, and things possible. This includes things like refrigerators, cars, thermostats, and baby monitors.

Physical things can now interact and collect data with little human intervention thanks to cheap computers, the cloud, big data, analytics, and mobile technologies. In today's hyperconnected world, digital technologies can record, monitor, and alter every contact between linked things. The real and the virtual coexist and interact. With the help of the internet of things, people may work and live smarter than ever before and take complete charge of their lives. Smart home automation gadgets are only one application of IoT's importance to the commercial world (Burunkaya et al., 2022). The Internet of Things (IoT) allows businesses to monitor their systems in real time, providing invaluable insights into everything from the efficiency of their equipment to the effectiveness of their supply chains and logistical operations. With the use of IoT, businesses may be able to automate processes and save costs by reducing the need for human labor. In addition, it improves efficiency, speeds up service, cuts down on production and shipping costs, and is transparent to customers (Chen et al., 2018).

The use of electronic devices may range from entirely hands-on to fully automated. Using an electronic monitoring system for attendance makes data collection easier, faster, and more accurate. Through the use of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), the Internet of Things (IoT), and cloud computing, this research aims to create a real-time presence system that can alert teachers, parents, and school administrators to student absences so that corrective measures can be taken before the next scheduled class.

Green IoT refers to the Internet of Things' adoption of energy-efficient practices to reduce the environmental effect of existing applications and services. Since 2020, when digital devices were widely available to consumers, the rate at which they are used has expanded substantially (D. Minoliet.al., 2017). Many environmental characteristics, including temperature, humidity, and more, may be tracked in real-time from almost any location with wireless Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensors. Nowadays, flames may rapidly spread. Beyond only price, efficiency, and response time, there are a few more issues that require fixing. Because of these problems, the goal of this project is to develop an Internet of Things-enabled smoke and heat detection system for use in fire alarm systems. The system receives heat and flame data through the Internet of Things, processes it, and then immediately takes the planned actions, such as activating the sprinkler system and alert. When companies that generate and distribute electricity put money into modernization, they aim for more than just smart energy management made possible by the Internet of Things. They reorganized in order to boost automation and decrease payroll costs. IoT-based monitoring systems are used, for instance, to automate costly onsite asset management and improve maintenance operations. Utilities may utilize customer electricity use data to calculate dynamic rates automatically.

2. Literature Survey

A new technology built on the principles of smart cities is the smart campus. With fewer features needed than in a smart city, the ideas of a smart city will be applied in a smart campus. All resources on a traditional campus are manually monitored and controlled, but on a smart campus, everything is digital. In terms of reducing operating expenses, enhancing efforts, and being timely, digitization will significantly improve. Higher education institutions that use this cutting-edge technology to automatically monitor and manage campus facilities will undoubtedly provide their employees and students the highest calibre services (v et.al., 2021). The advantages of IoT applications and services include the creation of an interactive environment with the use of cutting-edge services for the campus community. By saving money and time, good campus monitoring and administration will increase its efficiency. It may also increase campus safety thanks to its quick reaction when alarm and sensing systems are activated (Hongyanet.al., 2011).

Recent studies have shown the potential for building a smart campus utilizing the IoT technologies and fundamental architectural layers (Hossain et.al., 2019). The development of wireless and mobile communications facilitated the use of IoT technologies and increased the potential of better services in a Smart environment, such as a smart building city (M. Jainet.al., 2017). Both GPS and non-GPS technologies are employed in object positioning systems. Technologies like RFID (O. Bates et.al 2017), iBeacon (Pandey et.al., 2020), or Wi-Fi (Polin, K et.al., 2023) signals may be employed in the case of non-GPS systems (Sneest et.al., 2022). Similar to this, smartphones backed by the wireless infrastructure network are often utilized to enhance planning and emergency response systems and appssystems (Sneest et.al., 2022). An energy-efficient campus management system was put into place by Najim et al. utilizing sensors and microcontrollers to monitor and regulate energy use. This may cut down on energy use and maximize resource usage throughout the university. The IoT services used in a smart campus by Moreno et al. also showed a number of energy-efficient services.

The advantages of IoT applications and services include the creation of an interactive environment with the use of cutting-edge services for the campus community. By saving money and time, good campus monitoring and administration will increase its efficiency (Villegas-Ch et.al., 2019). It may also increase campus safety thanks to its quick reaction when alarm and sensing systems are activated. This may cut down on energy use and maximize resource usage throughout the university. The adoption of IoT technology was aided by the development of wireless and mobile communications. It increased the likelihood that services would be improved in a smart environment, such as a smart city or building.

3. Material and Methods

The notion of a SMART Campus has been around for a long time, and much effort is currently being done to make teaching and learning settings more efficient and intuitive (Wang et.al., 2014). The smartness did not stop at a single classroom; rather, it spread to make the whole institution SMART by automating features that were not available to the individual unit. With the arrival of IoT, this movement accelerated significantly. On a SMART campus, we will include some of the qualities found in a smart city, as well as a paperless and eco-

friendly campus. These Internet of Things elements are incorporated with the existing campus amenities (Zhamanovet.al., 2017). These features will assist Higher Education Institutions in efficiently and successfully managing the campus. Smart Attendance System, Smart Equipment Management System, Smart Green Environment System, as well as smart fire and safety systems, will be integrated in the Smart Campus. The initiative will track energy and the environment, as well as the attendance of staff and students. The project will really implement a Smart room (monitor power, AC, temperature, attendance, occupancy (whether the room is available or not), Smart education, an automated system for watering plants, and an automated fire alarm system.

A.Smart Campus Architecture

In Figure 1, we developed the two applications one is student attendance using the RFID and next green environment ,in both we are uploading the values which are updating in the IOT app i.e., BLYNK which stores the information as a database, it is acts like a cloud storage system, as a new values are recording in the sensor it will upload to the blynk app, in this we are using the sensors for irrigation, soil moisture sensor to detect the soil dryness,DHT11 sensor is used to take the humidity and temperature values,ESP8266 this is a Wi-Fi module which is used to provide the internet to uploads the updated values, LCD was used to display the temperature humidity values and which student login logout data like in simple line , all these works will be handled by the Arduino mega 2560 micro controller which is works as a Arduino board but the input output pins are more ,it has some conditions when those conditions are satisfied then it will moves for the next steps.

Fig. 1. Smart Campus Architecture

In this application after starting the device, after starting it display the "SMART CAMPUS", humidity and temperature values will be taken from the DHT11 sensor and displays on the screen, when we put the RFID card on the card reader it will check for the database if data was matched it will upload the card incoming and upload into the blynk app , when same card was read again it will take it as a student was leaving the campus, dryness of the soil will be measured by the soil moisture sensor if soil is wet than it won't move to the next step if soil is dry then it will check for the water level using the float sensor if the water is available in sufficient level then pump will be turn ON otherwise turn OFF the status of the pump was turn ON/OFF status will be uploaded into the cloud.

1. ArduinoMicrocontroller: The system (shown in Figure 2) is powered by an Atmega2560 microprocessor. This microcontroller contains 256 KB of memory, 8 KB of which is utilized by the bootloader Flash programme memory and 8 KB of static random-access memory (SRAM). The hardware is separated into four sections: the LCD display interface portion, the RFID module interface section, the soil moisture sensor, and the float sensor. The ATmega2560 microcontroller controls all of these elements, and the software necessary to operate them is the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE). It contains 54 digital I/O pins (14 of which are PWM outputs), 16 analogue I/O pins, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power connector, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It comes with everything you need to support the microcontroller; just connect it to a computer through USB or power it using an AC-to-DC converter or battery to get started. Most shields produced fortheArduinoDuemilanove or Diecimila are compatible with the Mega.

2. RFID module: The EM-18 125kHz RFID Reader module is a low-cost option for any RFID-based project. The Reader module has a built-in antenna and requires a 5V supply to function. Turn on the module and connect

its transmitted pin to the microcontroller's reception pin. If you hold your card close enough to the reader, it will read the number and send it to the output. The module's output type may be changed to Weigand if desired.

Fig. 2. Block Diagram of Arduino MEGA2560

3. RFID Tag: The microchip and radio aerial of an RFID tag are attached to a substrate and store a 12-byte identification number.

4 RFID Reader: The microchip and radio aerial of an RFID tag are attached to a substrate and store a 12-byte identification number. A transceiver in an RFID reader generates a radio signal and sends it out through an antenna. This signal is really used to power and activate the tag. The transponder in an RFID tag is triggered when it comes into touch with a signal from a reader. The tag receives power from the reader in the form of an electromagnetic field. The radio signal is converted into usable power by the transponder. When powered, the transponder sends an RF signal to the RFID reader, carrying all of the data stored in it, including the unique ID. This identifying information is then sent as a byte from the RFID reader's serial Tx (transmit) pin. Via UART communication, a computer or microcontroller may use or access this information serially.

5. ESP8266 : The values may be uploaded to the server using this WIFI module, which communicates with the Arduino board. The ESP8266 (or Expressive Systems ESP8266) is a TCP/IP and Serial Protocol-compatible Wi-Fi module that is small, lightweight, and energy efficient. It is the most widely used Wi-Fi module because to its low price and small size, making it ideal for use in Internet of Things (IoT) cloud-based embedded applications. It requires a logic level converter if you are using a 5V supply, since it functions at 3V and can handle a maximum voltage of around 3.6V. Via the Serial Port, the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module may be connected to microcontroller boards like the Arduino UNO. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module is the basis for a number of different breakout boards (i.e., ESP8266 NodeMCU V3). This is the source of electricity. This jack connects the ground to the transmit and receive pins. The battery powered the gadget at 3.3V. 3.2.7 ESP8266.

Features:

1. 802.11 b/g/n.
 2. Integrated 32-bit MCU with minimal power consumption.
 3. A 10-bit ADC is included in.
 4. TCP/IP protocol stack integrated.
 5. TR switch, balun, LNA, power amplifier, and matching network are all integrated.
 - PLL, regulators, and power management units are all integrated.
 7. Allows for antenna variety WI-Fi 2.4 GHz with WPA/WPA2 capability.
 8. STA/AP/STA+AP operating modes are supported.
 9. Smart Link Feature is supported for both Android and iOS smartphones.
- SDIO 2.0, SPI (H).
UART, I2C, I2S, IR Remote Control, PWM, and GPIO are all included.

STBC, 1x1 MIMO, 2x1 MIMO.

Aggregation of A-MPDU and A-MSDU with 0.4s guard interval.

6. DHT11 :The DHT11 Temperature & Humidity Sensor has a calibrated digital signal output and a temperature & humidity sensor complex. This consists of three pins (VCC, GND, and a data pin coupled to the microcontroller's AD1(23) for humidity and temperature updates) and uses the novel digital-signal-acquisition method and temperature and humidity sensor technologies.

POT: As well as adjusting the voltage to find the unknown voltage, the potentiometer now controls the brightness of the LCD by acting as a voltage divider. Water content of the ground: This is a basic electronic device for measuring soil moisture. The sensor may be easily inserted into the ground to determine the moisture or water level there. When the soil is wet, it gives out a 5V digital output, and when it's dry, it gives off 0V. It has four pins labelled VCC (power), GND (ground), DO (digital out), and AO (analogue out).

7. Float sensor: The level of liquid in a tank may be determined via a float switch. The flipped switch might start a pump, activate an indicator, sound an alarm, or do anything else. Hydroponics, saltwater tanks, freshwater tanks, gardening, aquariums, pet bowls, fish tanks, filtration, heating, pumps, and ponds may all benefit from using them to regulate the power heads of their respective systems.

8. Water pump: The R385 6-12V DC Diaphragm Based Mini Aquarium Water Pump is a great all-around non-submersible pump. With the addition of a nozzle, it may be utilized as a spray system due to its high pressure. This submersible pump may be used to water plants, build a waterfall or fountain, and even clean the water in a fish tank. It generates less than 30 decibels of noise when in operation. The pump is equipped with a filter and a suction cup for stable attachment to flat surfaces.

B. Working Principle

In Figure 3, the microcontroller we used here is an Arduino mega2560 v2, which has 54 digital pins, 16 analogue pins, 4 UART pins, a USB connection, and a power jack. This microcontroller was designed to act as a brain for all the devices such as sensors, a WIFI module that provides internet access to the system, and collects all the data based on the conditions we specified in the programme. ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi module that links to a Wi-Fi/hotspot to provide an internet connection that connects to the Arduino board and uploads attendance, soil moisture value, pump switch ON/OFF state, temperature and humidity values to the IOT server (blynk).

To display the strings such as welcome, present your card, temperature, and humidity readings on a screen, we utilized a 16x2 LCD, which is linked to the controller and displays the strings as specified in the software. The DHT11 sensor is used to detect the temperature and humidity in the surrounding environment. This data is sent to the controller, where it is uploaded to the server and displayed on the LCD. The EM 18 RFID reader module is connected to the controller, which has four pins VCC, GND, and Tx for transmitting and receiving data from the reader module to the controller. When the student places the card in the reader, it will read the card using the mutual induction principle. If the server has the card details, it will show the student no, otherwise it will wait for another card reading.

Soil moisture sensor is used to determine the dryness of the soil; if the soil is dry, it will check the water level in the tank; if water is available, it will switch on the pump and water the plants. If the water level falls below a certain level or the earth becomes moist, the pump will be turned off.

Fig. 3. Schematic Diagram

Plant Irrigation:The prediction of micro-plasma impacts in organic vegetables using Deep Learning is an exciting development in the field of food safety technology. By combining the power of artificial neural networks, computational resources and the latest imagery technologies, this technology can be used to give accurate assessments of the micro-plasma impacts in organic vegetables.

In order to measure the interactions, the model utilizes deep learning techniques. By using deep learning, the model is able to evaluate and respond to complex patterns in the data. This allows for more accurate identification of the potential risk associated with different types of micro-plasma. Once the model has been trained, it can be used to identify the potential impacts of various combinations of micro-plasma in the vegetable. By doing this, it can provide more accurate insight into the potential health risks associated with different combinations of micro-plasma in the vegetable. This can then be used to inform the food safety regulations and protocols that are in place to protect consumers from potential health risks.

If the soil moisture is more than 650, we may consider the soil to be dry. It then proceeds to the next stage, which is to check the water level in the tank. If the water level is below the minimum needed level, the controller will switch on the pump, and the float sensor value is 1. The pump will switch off automatically, and the status of pump turn on/off will be uploaded into the IOT app (blynk). If the soil moisture is less than 650, the pump will not check for water level and will not turn on. The flowchart will appear below. The functional flow diagram has shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Flow Chart for green environment

As per conditions, the water supply will be only turn ON when the water is sufficient and if the ground dryness is high as per, we programmed in the code. Here we see a true Smart Campus-A Digital Transformation with the IoT in action.

4. Results And Discussion

A. Condition Based Output

When the device is turned on, the LCD displays the smart campus until a Wi-Fi connection is available, at which point it displays the Wi-Fi connection. Then it captures the temperature and humidity readings shown (Fig.5) on the LCD while waiting for the card to be read. Upload the file to the IOT app.

Fig. 5. LCD Displaying Temperature and Humidity values and on IoT app

In Figure 6 and 7, if the soil moisture level is more than 650, the system will verify the float sensor value and, if sufficient water is available, switch on the water pump. If there is insufficient water to pump, the pump will remain in the OFF position. If the soil moisture reading is 450, the pump will shut off. This data will then be uploaded to the IOT app.

Fig. 6. Pump Turned ON when water is available

Fig. 7. Pump is turned OFF when water is not sufficient

Numerical Representation of Input Corresponding Output Element is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Numerical representation of Results

Component	INPUT	OUTPUT
DHT11	Surroundings temperature and humidity	Sent to the cloud and have them shown
Soil moisture	Soil moisture value>650	The water level should be checked. When sensing an adequate water level, the pump will activate and a corresponding data set will be sent to the server.
Soil moisture	Soil moisture value<450	It will stop pumping and send a file to the server.

5. Conclusions

The final goal of this proposed method was to evaluate and analyses the performance of the constructed system. We completed the testing and assessment, demonstrating the design with satisfaction. Lastly, in this model is created through a series of advanced computer algorithms. These algorithms analyze the various components of the vegetable in order to establish a set of features that are associated with the micro-plasma impact. By doing this, the model can be used to identify trends or patterns in the data and to help make predictions. Once the model has been created, it can be used to detect the interactions between different types of micro-plasma in the vegetable. As a result, this technology may also be employed at colleges and universities. In addition, we recommend including local hosting with internet since if the internet goes down.

Future Scope

Future study will benefit from what we built since it is likely to be more accurate by utilizing additional sensors or a more complex algorithm, but this will only be achievable when microprocessors such as Arduino release new and more powerful variations with improved capabilities.

Conflict of interest.

None.

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Real Time Implementation of Automatic Moisture and Light Control Protection for Garden

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Abstract: In this article, we proposed an automatic street light control using Real-Time Clock (RTC) and Light-Dependent Resistor (LDR) and that relies on a real-time clock. The main idea of this paper is predicated on using as little energy as possible. In this work, we use the DS1307 real-time clock module to automatically switch on or off-street lights dependent on the time of day. Programming controls the timing of when the device is active. In a similar vein, LDR is used to detect the amount of light, and the street lights are controlled accordingly. The most significant benefit of street lighting is the reduction of risk associated with potential crashes. Lights on the streets are often switched on at night and left on till morning. Their operation is entirely manual. Because of the increased risk of electrical shock during the rainy season, this proposed design intends to automate the operation of streetlights in order to reduce power consumption, improve public safety, and advance technological progress.

Keywords: Real Time Clock, Automation Street Light, Real Time Monitoring, Power Consumption and Energy Efficiency.

1. Introduction

Something embedded in another is related to it. One definition of an embedded system is a computer system in which the software is physically integrated into the hardware. Both standalone and integrated applications may be considered embedded systems. An embedded system is a computer with a built-in microcontroller or microprocessor that is programmed to carry out a limited set of instructions. The system gets its moniker from the application-specific software that is built in into it. An embedded system is a software-based, real-time control system that is microcontroller-based. Microcontroller and microprocessor-based systems designed to manage and track the operation of physical devices are known as embedded systems [1]. Embedded systems have the potential to provide exceptional performance and levels of automation. The development of autonomous robots that could be used in everyday life was a major breakthrough made possible by embedded systems, which sent shockwaves through the scientific community. Embedded technologies have already shown their worth in our daily lives via the widespread appeal and unique attractiveness of branded electronic firms' robot companions. Embedded systems are likely to be the dominant technology in the future due to their wide range of possible uses and the possibility that they will allow for the creation of extremely inventive goods [2]. The Embedded market is seeing two big shifts at the moment.

The true impetus behind Embedded programming-based application R&D is the mutually beneficial partnership between Embedded software suppliers and Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) [3]. The complexity of Embedded applications necessitating more robust, inexpensive hardware and enhanced connectivity poses problems for the Embedded Operating System (EOS) business and its future development.

Microcontrollers are programmed to carry out certain operations. To be more precise, this refers to use cases where the connection between input and output is explicitly stated. Some kind of processing is required, and output is provided, but this all depends on the input. Input devices such as keyboards, mice, washing machines, digital cameras, pen drives, remote controls, microwave ovens, automobiles, bicycles, telephones, mobile phones, watches, etc. Embedding these applications on a single chip is feasible because of the few resources they need. As a result, both the size and the price are reduced. Microprocessors excel in general-purpose jobs

like programing, game design, website creation, image editing, document creation, etc [4]. In such circumstances, the connection between the two is unclear. They need a lot of storage space, processing power, input/output interfaces, etc.

The microprocessor has a much faster clock speed than the microcontroller. Microprocessors of today do sophisticated operations at speeds more than 1GHz, whereas microcontrollers only manage speeds of a few megahertz (MHz) up to 30 or 50 MHz. The cost-effectiveness of a microcontroller vs a microprocessor cannot be compared. Compared to a microprocessor, a microcontroller is unquestionably more cost-effective. Nevertheless, a microprocessor should not be utilised in lieu of a microcontroller since doing so greatly increases the cost of the application. The microprocessor is useless in isolation. A system built on a microprocessor is expensive since it requires additional components like RAM, ROM, a buffer, I/O ports, etc.

2. Literature Review

In order to maximise the effectiveness of solar energy conversion, the authors of "Energy Efficient Smart Street Light" [5] evaluated a streetlight with an automatic tracking system. From ceiling fans to washing machines and beyond, these automation systems play a crucial role in making our everyday lives more pleasant and convenient [6]. The conventional lighting system only has two settings, on and off, which is inefficient since it wastes energy by always being at full power. Hence, one of the notable power losses is from street lights, although automation leads to numerous new ways of conserving energy and money. The use of a Light Dependent Resistor (LDR) to regulate the lighting system is one solution [7]. By 2015, the planned traffic-flow-based solar-powered street lighting system will be fully operational. They powered the streets using solar energy, a renewable resource [8]. LEDs (Light Emitting Diodes) are employed because they are more energy efficient and provide more light than traditional light sources such as halogen lamps, mercury lamps, etc. The streetlights' independence from other entities is achieved by their light-sensor-based functioning [9]. The studies detail the two-installation case study conducted in Scotland and Wales and provide an overview of the technology's features and advantages. Around a hundred thousand MINOS devices had been installed and were functioning well, according to the system's installation log[10].

Although there are many fascinating uses for electricity, none is more important than street lights for ensuring the safety of pedestrians and drivers after dark. Having streetlights on all night long is a major drain on resources and shortens the lifespan of associated electrical components like electric bulbs. Much of a city's energy budget goes towards lighting, and streetlights in particular are notorious power hogs. An intelligent lighting management system may extend the life of street lights and save expenditures by as much as 70 percent [11]. In certain instances, the on/off times of street lights are predetermined, and if the corresponding timer is malfunctioning for any reason, it will take some time to remedy the issue via the right channels. Keeping the light on for an extended period of time has an impact on the environment [12]. Similar research showed that the majority of crimes are committed at night, emphasizing the need for adequate illumination on roadways and thoroughfares [13].

The purpose of this study [14] is to propose employing solar panels to power lighting in order to cut down on energy use. The goal is to reduce energy consumption by automating the on/off switching of streetlights and by switching the streetlight to avoid wasting light when it is not required. The proposed system [15] uses motion detection sensors to ascertain whether the lights should be brightened or turned off entirely. This study [16] examines the use of the Internet of Things (IoT) and wifi/LoRa for monitoring energy-efficient electrical appliances. This system [17] monitors the movement of people through which the intensity varies, saving the excessive use of light and reducing the cost of power. It is free of cost and has a vast range of operation and can replace the wired network infrastructure of greater cost. In [18] Analysis of Solar energy based street light with auto tracking system was published by C.Bhuvaneshwari et.al., Lasket, Tsering developed Automatic Light Intensity Monitoring using Modern Technology [19]. Magno, et.al., developed A Low-cost, Highly Scalable Wireless Sensor Network Solution to Achieve Smart LED Light Control for Green Buildings. [20].

3. Proposed Model

Safety and the prevention of accidents at night make street lighting a necessity in modern society. One of a city's most crucial — and costly — duties is lighting its streets at night. In average cities throughout the globe, lighting may account for 10–38 percent of the entire energy cost. Because of its crucial role in maintaining economic and social stability, public authorities in developing nations place a premium on adequate street lighting. Indirectly, the installation of street lights has helped the public and the government decrease the crime rate and the number of accidents in the neighborhood. It promotes social cohesion by making individuals feel safe venturing out in the evening. Nonetheless, in today's hectic world, nobody thinks to turn it off or on until

absolutely necessary. Poor lighting causes unhealthy environments and wastes thousands of dollars annually. Lighting for streets may be made much more affordable with the use of energy-saving technology and layout. The three factors of automation, power consumption, and cost effectiveness are now at the forefront of technological development. The goal of automating tasks using computers and other smart technologies is to lessen the need for human labor. While electricity generation is becoming more difficult for a variety of reasons, reducing energy consumption must always be a top priority. When the demand increases, it becomes more critical to design a system that minimizes costs. We implemented automated street light control based on an RTC and LDR to address this issue. In this age of automation, humans are restless and unable to regulate the manual operations of any field; a rapid advancement in embedded systems has paved the way for the design and development of a microcontroller-based automatic street light control using a Real-Time Clock (RTC) and a Light-Dependent Resistor (LDR). As daylight fades below the range of human visual perception, the streetlights turn on automatically. In our proposed design, we used a DS1307, a light-sensing diode with four pins (VCC, GND, SCL, SDA) that are connected to a microcontroller; when we tell it the time, it compares it to the time stored in the RTC; if the two times are the same, it proceeds to the next step, in which it determines whether or not there is sufficient light to warrant turning off the streetlights.

3.1. Automatic Light Control Architecture

These strategies were developed to address deficiencies in previously used approaches. Our proposed design's power supply will draw from 230V ac, and after passing through a step-down transformer, 5V and 12V dc will be produced for use in the circuitry. This is shown in the block diagram Figure 1. The LDR and RTC get their power from this 5V source. LED strips, model ULN2003, need a 12V supply. The microcontroller will get the current time from the RTC, which will keep accurate time using a quartz crystal. The light-dependent resistor (LDR) measures and reports light intensity. The microcontroller, a Node MCU v3, receives data on the light intensity and responds by increasing the conduction rate. This is an Arduino microcontroller, and its code is created in the Arduino software development environment. C-language code is embedded. We've set up the IDE and RTC lib for RTC programming and penned the code for calculating LDR intensity. We utilised microcontroller pins A0 for ADC values from the LDR, D1 and D2 for SCL and SDA from the RTC, D3, D4, and D5 for the LED strips, and D6, D7 for the reset button.

Fig. 1. Automatic Light Control Architecture

We came up with a novel approach and employed LDRs and RTCs in this proposed design, while before they had just used LDRs or RTCs, to account for the volatility of the Indian environment and seasonal variations. If the time on the RTC coincides with the time we've specified for the lights to come on, then just the lights will activate; otherwise, they will stay off. When the RTC checks to see whether it's time to turn on the lights, it compares the current time to the time set by the user; if the difference is less than or equal to 5, the lights turn on.

3.1.1. Microcontroller NODE MCU Description

The microcontroller is a programmable electronic device. A microcontroller is a single-chip device that has a central processing unit (CPU), memory (RAM), input/output (I/O) ports, and a timer. Microcontrollers are great for various uses because of the set quantity of on-chip Memory, ROM, and I/O ports. Prototyping your Internet of Things (IoT) device is as easy as writing a few lines of Lua code with the aid of the Node MCU, an open-source firmware and development kit. Expressive Systems created a micro controller known as the ESP8266.

Fig. 2. Basic block diagram of Node MCU v3

In Figure 2, this module has a wide variety of pin-outs and an integrated USB port. Like Arduino, Node MCU devices may be easily flashed by connecting them to a laptop via micro-USB cable. There are a total of 30 pins on the node MCU v3, but we only make use of a subset of them. A zero, GND, VCC, D1, D2, D3, D4, and D5 are the standard digital outputs.

Gnd means "ground" or "grounding."

Power is supplied via the VCC pin.

The microcontroller's analogue input is connected to pin A0.

The SCL input is connected to D1.

SDA data is entered via D2.

The LED strips should be connected using pins D3, D4, and D5.

3.1.2. Features of Node MCU

1. The Tensilica 32-bit RISC Processor Xtensa LX106 serves as the microcontroller.
2. 3.3V is the working voltage.
3. Powered by a 7-12V input voltage
4. Digital Input/Output (DIO) Pin Count: 16
5. ADC Input Ports (Analog Input): 5
6. UARTs: 1
7. SPIs: 1
8. I2Cs: 1
9. 4 MB of internal flash memory
10. ROM: 64 KB SRAM: 10
11. 80 MHz Clock Frequency
12. USB-TTL based on CP2102 is onboard, allowing for Plug n Play operation.
13. Radio Antenna PCB
14. Compact form factor allows for easy integration into existing IoT applications.

3.1.3. ESP 8266:

The Node MCU group has built a micro-USB connector for programming and a 3.3v regulator as part of an open-source, comprehensive development board for the ESP8266. After connecting the Node MCU board to your computer and installing the necessary USB drivers, you can immediately begin programming it to communicate with your wifi network. You can get all of that for a mere four dollars (USD) on eBay. As the most widely used and inexpensive wifi system-on-a-chip (SoC) with a TCP/IP stack and a low-power 32-bit microcontroller, ESP8266 is produced by espressif, a Chinese company with headquarters in Shanghai. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a newly developing industry at the moment. One of the most common and inexpensive methods for establishing a wireless connection between "Things" and the internet. The Arduino IDE is by far the most popular environment in which to work with ESP modules, while there are many others. The ESP8266 module can only function when supplied with 3.3V; 3.7V or more will damage it. The ESP-01 may be

programmed using the 3.3V FTDI board. Every user of ESP-01 eventually runs across issues with turning it on. Power the module via a 3.3V Arduino pin or a potential divider while programming. The module consumes a fair amount of electricity. Thus, a tiny voltage regulator for 3.3V that can produce at least 500mA is essential. A good example of a regulator is the LM317.

3.1.4 ULN 2003:

The ULN2003 is used for current amplification. It has 16 terminals, or pins. The IC has 16 inputs and 14 outputs; the inputs are pins 1, 3, and 5, while the outputs are pins 16, 14, and 12. The inputs are extended from the microcontroller's D3, D4, and D5, and the Vcc is pin 9, a 12V supply; pin 8 is ground. The ULN2003 is an array of Darlington transistors that can handle high voltage and current. For switching inductive loads, it has a common-cathode clamp diode at the high-voltage outputs of its seven NPN Darlington pairs. It is possible to parallel the Darlington pairs to increase their current carrying capacity. Each channel has a 500mA continuous current rating and a 600mA peak current capacity. The inputs are pinned opposite the outputs, and there are built-in suppression diodes for driving inductive loads.

Each of the ULN2001, ULN2002, ULN2003, and ULN2004 is an open collector Darlington array with a common emitter that can handle high voltage and current. Each channel has a 500-mA rating and can handle 600 mA peak currents. Inputs are pinned on the opposite side of the board as the outputs, and suppression diodes are added for driving inductive loads. All of the logic families are supported by the different versions: ULN2001 (all-purpose, DTL, TTL, PMOS, CMOS); ULN2002 (14–25 V PMOS); ULN2003 (5 V TTL, CMOS); and ULN2004 (6 - 15 V CMOS, PMOS). These multipurpose electronics may power anything from a solenoid to a DC motor to a high-power buffer or LED display filament light. In order to minimize thermal resistance, the ULN2001A/2002A/2003A and 2004A are provided in a 16-pin DIP package made of copper. ULN2001D1/2002D1/2003D1/2004D1, they are also offered in a miniature outline format (SO-16). For more condensed code, ULN2003 may be obtained in the TSSOP16 package.

3.1.5. LDR

Two photoconductive cells made of cadmium sulphide (cds) with spectrum responses similar to the human eye. When the brightness of the light increases, the cells' resistance decreases. While being a specialized sort of Resistor, the Light Dependent Resistor (LDR), also known as a Photoresistor, has no polarity and may be connected in any way. These work well with a breadboard and can be adapted to a perf board with little effort. The LDR pinout diagram depicts a symbol similar to that of a Resistor, but with additional, internal arrows. The directional arrows indicate the lights' messages. The concept of photoconductivity lies at the heart of how photoresistors function. The absorption of light by a substance may enhance its conductivity, a process known as "photoconductivity."

A photoresistor, also known as an LDR (Light Dependent Resistor), is a kind of resistor whose resistance varies with the intensity of the light hitting it. Hence, in a completely dark room, the resistor will have a resistance of many megaohms, but when light is progressively shone over the sensor, the resistance will begin to diminish, eventually reaching a few ohms. Electrons in a semiconductor material's valence band are stimulated to the conduction band when light (photons) strikes the device. In order for the electrons to transition from the valence band to the conduction band, the energy of the photons in the incoming light must be larger than the bandgap of the semiconductor material. Because of this quality, the LDR may serve as a light detector. It is sensitive to the quantity of light hitting it and can therefore tell day from night. So, this sensor is the simple and inexpensive answer for us if we need to detect light or tell the difference between day and night.

3.1.6. RTC

A real-time clock (RTC) is an accurate timepiece for computers, often implemented as an integrated circuit. While the word is most often used to describe components of computers, servers, and embedded systems, real-time clocks (RTCs) may be found in almost any electronic equipment that requires precise timekeeping. The clock's precision relies on the crystal's precision and the accuracy with which the oscillator circuit's capacitive load matches the capacitive load for which the crystal was trimmed. Crystal frequency drift due to temperature changes will provide another source of inaccuracy. The clock may be running quickly if the oscillator circuit was subjected to external circuit noise.

The DS1307 is a serial bus slave device. Implementing a START condition and then giving a device ID number and register address grants access. Unless a STOP condition is carried out, subsequent registers may be accessed in order. The device will abort an active access and reset its address counter when VCC drops below 1.25 x VBAT. So long as the system is operating outside of its tolerance range, inputs to the device will be ignored.

When the voltage drops below the battery backup threshold (VBAT), the device enters a low-current battery backup mode. During startup, if VCC is larger than VBAT + 0.2V, the device will switch from battery to VCC, and if VCC is greater than 1.25 times VBAT, it will detect inputs. The key components of the serial RTC are shown in Figure 3's block diagram. Reading the correct register bytes will provide you with the time and date. Figure 3 depicts the RTC registers. Writing the proper register bytes sets or initializes the time and calendar. The time and date registers are stored using BCD values. The clock halt (CH) bit is located in position 7 of register 0. Setting this bit to a 1 turns off the oscillator. Clearing to a 0 activates the oscillator. Please be aware that the values of all registers upon power-on are not specified. As a result, the oscillator must be turned on (CH bit = 0) when the system is first set up. The DS1307 has a choice of 12-hour or 24-hour operation.

Fig.3. LDR circuit diagram

The 12/24-hour mode choose bit is located in the sixth bit of the hours register. While it's on high, it switches to 12-hour mode. Bit 5 indicates PM if in 12-hour time format, whereas AM indicates logic low. Bit 5 in the 24-hour mode represents the second 10-hour interval (20- 23 hours). The current time is sent to a second group of registers during a 2-wire START. When the clock is still ticking, the time is retrieved from these auxiliary registers. In the event that the main registers are updated during a read, it is not necessary to re-read the registers.

3.2 Working Principle

Because of its crucial role in maintaining economic and social stability, public authorities in developing nations place a premium on adequate street lighting. The primary goal of this proposed design is to create an autonomous streetlight management system that is both affordable and dependable. The current standard switching and timer switching system's biggest flaw is its excessive energy consumption. The primary focus here is on developing a robust automated streetlight controller. The brain of the controlling circuit is the node MCU. The rectifier circuit consists of a step-down transformer, a voltage regulator, and other components to provide the control circuit with the 5V DC it needs to function. The light dependentutilized for this purpose provides analogue signals to the microcontroller based on the amount of light hitting the sensor. The combination of a light-dependent resistor and the timer principle is used. Setting the actual, active, and inactive times of a system.

The proposed model circuit implementation is presented in Figure 4. There are two prerequisites that must be met before the streetlight will turn ON or OFF. The microcontroller's timers and the light-dependent resistor's ability to measure light intensity are two of the prerequisites. When these two criteria are met, the microcontroller sends out signals to activate or deactivate the relay, respectively, causing the streetlight to turn on or off. The NodeMCU Microcontroller's Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) processes the LDR's analogue signals. The lights will turn on when the controller sends the signal. While power wastage issues are being faced in the current street lighting system owing to inappropriate switching operation, the goal of this proposed design is to build a highly dependable automated streetlight system. The microprocessor and Light Dependent Resistor in the planned control circuit are the primary controlling elements. It is determined that the designed system has effective automated switching control. This is the automated street light control circuit that was built. Embedded C programmes are part of the system design and are uploaded to the NodeMCU microcontroller. Analog signals from the RTC and LDR are processed by the microcontroller, together with the ON/OFF time adjustments. Only when both requirements are met will the streetlight switch on or off. When the LDR detects a decrease in light intensity and the specified-ON time coincides, the bulb lights up. This demonstrates how automated street light's function.

Fig.4. Schematic Diagram

In Figure 5, at all times throughout the day, the LDR sends its analog-to-digital converter (ADC) readings to the controller, which then checks the conditions we've specified in the code to determine whether or not to activate the lights. We have now integrated RTC and LDR since we have specified in the code that the RTC should keep time in accordance with our plans. In order to determine whether or not the lights should come on, the controller first verifies that the time set in the RTC corresponds to the time the user has specified. If this is the case, the controller then checks the light intensity using the ADC value read from the LDR; if the value is below 400, the lights will come on for 5 seconds before turning off automatically.

Fig.5. Flow Chart for LDR

Fig.6. Flow Chart using RTC and LDR

The above design (Figure 6) works well both during the day and at night; the lights turn on and off with the help of an RTC and a light-dependent resistor (LDR).

4. Experimental Analysis

In this case, an LDR and RTC-based Automated Street Light Controlling System has been put into use in the real world. Light intensity is correlated with ADC readings in this system. LDR ADC values may be used to power the system; if the ADC value is below 400, the lights will turn on, and if it's above, they'll stay off.

4.1 Condition-Based Output

As soon as the device is turned on, the LCD screen will display the smart campus (show in Figure 7) so long as a wifi connection is accessible, and then it will display the wifi connection status after it has been established. The next step is to wait for the card to be read while the LCDs the current temperature and humidity. Transfer to the IoT application.

Fig.7. LDR adc_values

Fig.8.Lights turned ON by covering the LDR

We have now integrated RTC and LDR since we have specified in the code that the RTC should keep time in accordance with our plans. From Figures 8 to 10, the controller will first verify that the time set in the RTC corresponds with the time the user has specified; if it does, the controller will proceed to step two, at which point it will determine whether or not the light intensity registered by the LDR meets the threshold of 400; if it does, the lights will turn on for five seconds before turning off automatically. Numerical Representation of output according to the input is tabulated in Table 1.

Fig.9. System turned ON the lights

Fig. 10. Time and LDR values

Table 1: Numerical Representation of output according to the input

Component	INPUT	OUTPUT
LDR	Adc_value<400	Indicators will activate
LDR	Adc_value>600	After the lights are turned ON, they will automatically turn OFF.
RTC and LDR	Rtc time==user set time; adc value<400	Indicators will activate
RTC and LDR	Rtc time!=user set time; adc_value<400	The lights will remain out until either the time is correct or the adc value is less than 400.
LDR	Adc_value<400	Indicators will activate

5. Conclusion And Future Scope

The design and testing of our proposed paper have proved fruitful. A significant amount of electricity is lost in

the typical street lighting system however, this may be prevented with automatic control employing LDR. The constructed control circuit is used to examine the automated switching function, which is proven to be extremely efficient with very low maintenance costs. The streetlight's ON/OFF status is determined by the circuit. The microcontroller has successfully managed the streetlights. When it becomes dark, the controller will send a signal to turn on the lights. In addition, the system relies on both a timer and an LDR sensor, eliminating a previous disadvantage of the street light system. In the long run, we want to expand this effort into an Internet of Things (IoT) initiative to determine how many systems are functioning normally. how much energy is being used, the possibility of determining which streetlight is malfunctioning so that no more complaints are required, and so on.

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SMART ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract: Attendance is an important part of daily ascertainment for the industries, institutions for the smooth running of the System. At the time of logging in and logging out the attendance is noted, but the manual attendance system may leads to appear that there may be chance of proxies and errors. Now-a-days, Machine Learning has been highly explored for computer vision applications. So, we use the concept of machine learning in Face – recognition for automatic attendance systems. In this project, the face recognition and face detection algorithms are provided in the computer systems which has the ability of finding and recognizing human faces fast and precisely in images or videos so that the system can be used in giving attendance. A webcam is used, where webcam is connected to the Raspberry Pi module for data acquisition. The data is analyzed using CNN algorithm and prepares the excel file (.csv) and uploads to cloud and the same is mailed to the respected authority.

KEYWORDS: Smart Campus, Machine Learning, Digitalization of attendance, Face Recognition, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).

INTRODUCTION

Student Attendance System in Classroom Using Face Recognition Technique says the quantity of highlights of any facial understudy picture is made to be consistent, for example 16 DCT coefficient. The process is finished entirely performing grayscale standardization, histogram balance, Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). Further examination of the disappointment in perceiving the rest facial pictures demonstrates that an understudy might be perhaps perceived as other student(s)By considering the all-out degree of acknowledgment as came about because of the investigation which doesn't meet exclusive requirement.Introduce the drivers from the math works site dependent on the sort of camera we are utilizing. Next, they use any rate 500 to 1000 catches of every individual. For getting higher level of exactness they used some HD camera so as to get results. For face distinguishing, we can do it utilizing

the article falling class and we utilize the b- box technique. The caught countenances are trimmed into little pictures of goals 112x92. It would associate with 11 KB of size. The faces taken in the database are expected to stack into our workspace. We will stack the gallery images into that. All the HOG highlights separated are put away as exhibit list it restores a mark to which the given information matches.

The attendance system is improved by using NFCtechnology and mobile application. According to the research paper, each student is given a NFC tag that has a unique ID during their enrolment into the college. Attendance of each class will then be taken by touching or moving these tags on the lecturer mobile phone. The embedded camera on the phone will then capture the student's face to send all the data to the college server to do validation and verification. The advantages of this method is where the NFC is simple to use, and the speed of connection establishment is very high. It indeed speeds up the attendance taking process a lot. However, this system couldn't

automatically spot the violation when the NFC tag is not personally tagged by the original owner. Apart from that, the convenience of the system which uses the mobile phone as the NFC reader was actually an inconvenience to the lecturer. Imagine if the lecturer had forgotten to bring their mobile phones to work, what would be the backup procedure for the attendance to be recorded? Moreover, most of the lecturer will not likely to prefer their personal smart phones to be used in this way due to privacy matter. Hence, unique information about the student like biometrics or face recognition, which is genuine for a student should be used in replacement of the NFC tag. This will ensure attendance to be taken originally by the actual student.

The captured image is compared one by one with the face database to search for the worker's face where attendance will be marked when a result is found in the face database. The main advantage of this system is where attendance is marked on the server which is highly secure where no one can mark the attendance of other. Moreover, in this proposed system, the face detection algorithm is improved by using the skin classification technique to increase the accuracy of the detection process. Although more efforts are invested in the accuracy of the face detection algorithm, the system is yet not portable. This system requires a standalone computer which will need a constant power supply that makes it not portable. This type of system is only suitable for marking staff's attendance as they only need to report their presence once a day, unlike students which require to report their attendance at every class on a particular day, it will be inconvenient if the attendance marking system is not portable. Thus, to solve this issue, the whole attendance management system can be developed on an portable module so that it can be work just by executing the python.

A technique called Image Processing is used to train the system to detect a face. When the faces are captured by a camera, they are first converted to grayscale and then to that image subtraction process is applied. The image after this is stored on the server for further processing which is done later. The author proposed a strategy where the framework was used as an online Web Server, so the participation results can be open to a verified web customer. The facial acknowledgment is finished by actualizing Local Binary Patterns (LBP) first handling venture is to identify and edit the locale of intrigue ROI which is the human face, then apply the Haar Feature-based Cascade calculation.

After that, the picture highlights are extricated utilizing LBPs, at that point LBPs calculation contrasts

the separated highlights and the prepared datasets. Later, by clicking 'c' as in catch on the console framework, the participation results are put away in MySQL database, so it tends to be available to the web server."Face Recognition Based Attendance System "written by Nandhini R. the author mentions the fundamental working rule of the venture is that, the video caught information is changed over into picture to identify and perceive it. CNN calculation is executed to recognize the faces. A CNN (Convolution Neural Network), utilizes a framework like a multilayer perceptron, intended to process the prerequisites faster. After the end of distinguishing and preparing the face, it is contrasted with the face's present in the understudy's database to refresh the participation of the students. The post-preparing component includes the way toward refreshing the names of the understudy into an exceed expectations sheet. The exceed expectations sheets can be kept up on a week after week premise or month to month premise to record the understudy's participation.

2. Literature Review

The Teacher's Attendance and Roll Book forms are designed for keeping classroom attendance records on a monthly basis. The roll book page is intended to be printed for each month and will keep records for 26 students. Use your own key to identify attendance-related events such as entering "A" for Absent or "T" for Tardy and "N" for No School. This is a simple form that is easy to use. The classroom attendance book page for teachers is an excel spreadsheet and requires at least excel reader to view. This printable attendance sheet is to be used in professional or academic environments by managers or teachers to track attendance of employees or students on a weekly basis [1]. The Attendance used for taking attendance in classrooms, institutions, etc. Attendance Register is a tool to record the regularity of a student, teacher, employee on a day to day basis. It is used for checking the regularity purposes student. The Attendance tool can be used for online or face-to-face courses. Enabled at the account level, the Roll Call Attendance can be used by all institutions [2].

Employee Attendance Registers is used to maintain records of the presence, absence, sick leave, etc related to each employee for payroll/salary purpose [3]. It consists of records of payroll heads like the present, absent, late comings, holidays, job training and all other kinds of leaves used to calculate the salary. The HR department, executives, and business owners then use this data to calculate the salary of their employees. To track attendance at the office you can use employee

attendance registers which are with and without payroll calculations.

Salary Sheet With Attendance Register is a complete payroll sheet in which you can maintain records of attendance for your employees and also calculate the salaries of 40 employees [4]. We have created a simple and easy Employee Attendance Template with predefined formulas and formatting. You can maintain the attendance of 50 employees in this template. You just need to enter some employee details once [5]. Select from the drop-down menu to mark the absence or presence of the employee. This template is available in 4 file formats - Excel, Google Sheets, Open Office Calc, and Apple Numbers.

Student Attendance Registers are for seeing the regularity of the student attending the class for any educational institutions. It enables the teachers to maintain the record of students present or absent in their class for a whole academic year. In addition to that, it helps to reduce the workload of teachers and save many man-hours that can be utilized in more fruitful tasks. Furthermore, these Student Attendance Registers are for purpose of regularity [6].

Timesheet Attendance Registers record the man-hours of employees that are paid on an hourly basis. These payments can be daily, bi-weekly, or weekly. These registers record the number of hours spent by the employee on the job. Traditionally, it is a sheet of paper with the data arranged in tabular format. Now the timesheets have become digital. In simple terms, timesheets are sheets for summarizing hours worked by each worker during a pay period. It records the time of arrival/departure of workers and calculates the amount of time spent on job [7].

When it comes to tracking employees and their attendance, biometric time and attendance systems have gained popularity in the business world. The biometric attendance system has been used for many years by companies that are looking for ways to improve efficiency and reduce costs. The biometric attendance system can be used as an alternative to paper-based or manual attendance records, which are often inaccurate and difficult to track. The purpose of this guide is to give an explanation of biometric systems and how they have so many advantages that will prove valuable to all companies in the future [8].

Figure 1: Bio-metric

The term RFID (radio frequency identification) is one type of electronic device includes a small antenna and a chip. This device is used to transmit the information like persons, animals, books or any stuff between reader and RFID tag using radio frequency electromagnetic fields. It is capable of carrying 2k bytes of data [9]. There are different kinds of RFID systems in the market, which consist of an antenna, a transponder, and a transceiver. Some types of tags can be located close to the RFID reader and some tags can be located far from the reader. The operating frequency ranges of these devices mainly include low, mid and high ranges. The low-frequency range is from 30kHz to 500kHz, mid-frequency range is from 900kHz to 1500kHz and high-frequency range is 2.4kHz to 2.5kHz [10].

Figure 2: Radio Frequency Based Identification

3. Proposed System

Network Structure The CNN infrastructure model designed in this experiment. It includes the input layer, convolution layer 1, pooling layer 1, convolution layer 2, pooling layer 2, fully connected layer and Softmax regression classification layer. The main difference between CNN and other traditional neural networks is that the processing of convolutional and pooling layers is added to extract image features. The convolutional layer, also known as the feature extraction layer,

represents the layers of all the components obtained by filtering the input image. The input of each neuron is connected to the local receptive field of the previous layer and the local features are extracted. The meaning of this layer is that the original image is subjected to convolution operation to generate multiple images. The convolution process according to formula. First, the convolution kernel value is determined in a random manner, and the image to be converted is second from the left. To the right, top to bottom, select the image matrix in order and finally multiply the selected image matrix and the convolution kernel. Each convolution is a feature extraction method, just like a sieve, which filters out the qualified parts of the image. Generally speaking, the larger the activation value, the more the screening conditions are met. Convolution does not change the image size, so the processed image size remains the same, similar to the filter effect, which helps us extract different features of the input, such as edges, lines, and angles.

Before the attendance management system can work, there are a set of data needed to be inputted into the system which essentially consist of the individual's basic information which is their ID and their faces. The first procedure of portrait acquisition can be done by using the Camera to capture the faces of the individual. In this process the system will first detect the presence of a face in the captured image, if there are no face detected, the system will prompt the user to capture their face again until it meets certain number of portraits which will be 10 required portraits in this project for each student. The decision of storing only 10 portrait per student is due to the consideration of the limited storage space in the raspberry pi because the total amount of students in the university is considered heavy. Then, the images will undergo several pre-processing procedures to obtain a grayscale image and cropped faces of equal sized images because those are the prerequisites of using the EigenFaces Recognizer. Both of the processes mentioned above can be represented in the diagram below. Image Acquisition and Pre-processing procedures. After the images are being processed, they are stored into a file in a hierarchy manner. In this project, all the faces will be stored in a hierarchy manner under the database" folder. When expanding through the database folder, there will consist of many sub- folders which each of them will represent an individual where a series of face portrait belonging to the same individual will be stored in that particular sub-folder. The sub folders that represent each individual will be named upon the ID no. of that individual which is unique for every single individual in the institution. The whole process of image

retrieval, pre-processing, storing mechanism is done by the script named create_database.py.

Face Detection is a easy task for computer now a days. In fact some ML model achieved state of art in computer vision.

We are using pretrained CNN model for face detection and extraction.

1. Box around faces: Show red boxes around all the faces recognised in the image. The Python file is faceDetectionCNN.py

2. Extracted faces: Extract faces from all images in a folder and save each face into a destination folder to create a handy dataset. The Python file is faceExtraction.py.

3.1. OpenCV

OpenCV is a library of programming functions mainly aimed at real-time computer vision. It has a modular structure, which means that the package includes several shared or static libraries. We are using image processing module that includes linear and non-linear image filtering, geometrical image transformations (resize, affine and perspective warping, and generic table-based remapping), colorspace conversion, histograms, and so on.

3.2. CNN Training Experiment

Dataset Selection The experimental data used is New York University's OlivettiFaces face database, which consists of 400 pictures of 40 people, that is, each person's face picture is 10. The gray level of each picture is 8 bits, the gray level of each pixel is between 0 and 255, and the total picture size is 1190×942. There are 20×20 faces in total, so the size of each face is $(1190/20) \times (942/20)$ is $57 \times 47 = 2679$. We divide the raw data into three parts, the training data is 320 samples, the verification data and the test data. Modern Portfolio Presentation Face recognition is a method of identifying or verifying the identity of an individual using their face. Face recognition systems can be used to identify people in photos, video, or in real-time.

It can use your existing hardware infrastructure, existing cameras and image capture. It is the only biometric that allow you to perform passive identification in a one to. Many environments Overall it is the most efficient system to collect automatic student attendance of Online class in Corona Pandemic It requires no physical interaction on behalf

of the user. It is accurate and allows for high enrolment and verification rates. It does not require an expert to interpret the comparison result.

For face recognition there are two types of comparisons. Classification of FACE

RECOGNITION.

1. Verification: This is where the system compares the given individual with who that individual says they are and gives a yes or no decision.

2. Identification: This is where the system compares the given individual to all the Other individuals in the database and gives a ranked list of matches.

All identification or authentication technologies operate using the following four stages:

- 1) Capture: A physical or behavioural sample is captured by the system during Enrollment and also in identification or verification process.
- 2) Extraction: Unique data extracted from the sample and a template is created.
- 3) Comparison: The template is then compared with a new sample.
- 4) Match/non match: The system decides if the features extracted from the new Samples are a match or a non match.

A pre-processing module locates the eye position and takes care of the surrounding lighting condition and color variance. First the presence of faces or face in a scene must be detected. Once the face is detected, it must be localized. Some facial recognition approaches use the whole face while others concentrate on facial components and/ or regions (such as lips, eyes etc). The appearance of the face can change considerably during speech and due to facial expressions. The input can be recorded video of the speaker or a still image.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of Attendance System using CNN

A sample of 1 sec duration consists of a 25 frame video sequence. More than one camera can be used to produce a 3D representation of the face and to protect against the usage of photographs to gain unauthorized access. Synergetic computer are used to classify optical and audio features, respectively. A synergetic computer is a set of algorithm that simulate synergetic phenomena. In training phase the BIOID creates a prototype called face print for each person. A newly recorded pattern is pre-processed and compared with each face print stored in the database. As comparisons are made, the system assigns a value to the comparison using a scale of one to ten. If a score is above a predetermined threshold, a match is declared. Three Stages Implementation of Face Recognition Technology. How Face Recognition Systems Work If we look at the mirror, we can see that our face has certain distinguishable landmarks. These are the peaks and valleys that make up the different facial features. Software defines these landmarks as nodal points. There are about “80 nodal points” on a human face. Here are few nodal points that are measured by the software.

- Distance between the eyes
- Width of the nose
- Depth of the eye socket
- Cheekbones
- Jaw line
- Chin

How Face Recognition Systems Work

Face Bunch Graph: A Face bunch graph is created from “70 nodal points” to obtain a general representation of face. Given an image the face is matched to the Face bunch graph to find the same point. These nodal points are measured to create a numerical code, a string of numbers that represents a face in the database. This code is called face print. Only 14 to 22 nodal points are needed for face it software to complete the recognition process.

Face Recognition Attendance System: The modern face recognition attendance system is much efficient and safer than the conventional counterparts. There are a few Systems that are based on the face recognition technology and each of them has extremely varying features for the best suitability in different environments. It provides a facility for the central data management system. A very cost effective method of recording the attendance. Easy to manage Increased security Cost-effective. Automated time tracking system Advantage of Automatic Attendance System with Face Recognition Physical Description Test Same Person’s Images

- Measurements Generated From Image Input Image
- Test Same Person’s Images
- Test Same Person’s Images
- Test Different Persons Images
- Test Different Persons Images
- Test Different Persons Images Recognize Real Student
- Recognize Real Student
- Recognize Real Student
- Recognize who is not Student
- Recognize who is not Student
- Attendance File
- Attendance in Excel File

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) changed the way we used to learn images. It made it very very easy! CNN mimics the way humans see images, by focussing on one portion of the itime and scanning the whole image. CNN boils down every image as a vector of numbers, which can be learned by the fully connected Dense layers of ANN. More information about CNN can be found here. We can increase or decrease the convolution, max pooling, and hidden ANN layers and the number of neurons in it. The more layers/neurons you add, the slower the model becomes. Also, when there are large amount of images, in the tune of 50K and above, then the laptop’ CPU might not be efficient to learn those many images. Then have to get a GPU enabled laptop, or use cloud services like AWS or Google Cloud. Since the data we have used for the demonstration is small

containing only 244 images for training, We can run it on the laptop easily. Apart from selecting the best number of layers and the number of neurons in it, for each layer, there are some hyper parameters which needs to be tuned as well.

Take a quick look at some of the important hyperparameters

Filters=32: This number indicates how many filters we are using to look at the image pixels during the convolution step. Some filters may catch sharp edges, some filters may catch color variations some filters may catch outlines, etc. In the end, we get important information from the images. In the first layer the number of filters=32 is commonly used, then increasing the power of 2. Like in the next layer it is 64, in the next layer, it is 128 so on and so forth.

kernel_size=(5,5): This indicates the size of the sliding window during convolution, in this case study we are using CNN. In this case study, we will learn how to implement a face recognition model using CNN. This template can be used to create an image classification model on any group of images by putting them in a folder and creating a class.

3.3. Getting Images for the case study:

The data contains cropped face images of 16 people divided into Training and testing. We will train the CNN model using the images in the Training folder and then test the model by using the unseen images from the testing folder, to check if the model is able to recognise the face number of the unseen images or not.

3.4. Creating a mapping for index and face names:

The above class_index dictionary has face names as keys and the numeric mapping as values. We need to swap it, because the classifier model will return the answer as the numeric mapping and we need to get the face-name out of it. Also, since this is a multi-class classification problem, we are counting the number of unique faces, as that will be used as the number of output neurons in the output layer of fully connected ANN classifier.

Steps for Face Detection:

In this project, we’ve performed face detection and recognition by using OpenCV and NumPy. We’ve used Raspberry Pi3, but you can also use it with other systems. You’ll only have to modify the code slightly to use it on some other device.

Step 1: Install Libraries

First, you should install the required libraries, OpenCV, and NumPy. You can install it easily through:

```
pip install opencv-python
pip install opencv-contrib-python
For installing NumPy in your system, use the same
command as above and replace 'opencv- python' with
'numpy':
pip install numpy
```

Step 2: Detect Faces

Now, you must configure your camera and connect it to your system. The camera should work properly to avoid any issues in face detection. Before our camera recognizes us, it first has to detect faces. We'll use the Haar Cascade classifier for face detection. It is primarily an object detection method where you train a cascade function through negative and positive images, after which it becomes able to detect objects in other photos. In our case, we want our model to detect faces. OpenCV comes with a trainer and a detector, so using the Haar Cascade classifier is relatively more comfortable with this library. You can create your classifier to detect other images as well.

Step 3: Gather Data

Now that your model can identify faces, you can train it so it would start recognizing whose face is in the picture. To do that, you must provide it with multiple photos of the faces you want it to remember. That's why we'll start with creating our dataset by gathering photos. After collecting the necessary images, add IDs for every person, so the model knows what face to associate with what ID. Start with the images of one person and add at least 10-20. Use different expressions to get the most effective results. Create a script for adding user IDs to images, so you don't have to do it manually every time. The script is vital in case you want to use your model for multiple faces.

Step 4: Train

After creating the dataset of the person's images, you'd have to train the model. You'd feed the pictures to your OpenCV recognizer, and it will create a file named 'trainer.yml' in the end. In this stage, you only have to provide the model with images and their IDs so the model can get familiar with the ID of every image. After we finish training the model, we can test it.

3.5. Creating the CNN face recognition model

In the below code snippet, we have created a CNN model with

- 2 hidden layers of convolution
- 2 hidden layers of max pooling

- 1 layer of flattening
- 1 Hidden ANN layer
- 1 output layer with 16-neurons (one for each face)

We can increase or decrease the convolution, max pooling, and hidden ANN layers and the number of neurons in it. The more layers/neurons you add, the slower the model becomes. Also, when there are large amount of images, in the tune of 50K and above, then the laptop' CPU might not be efficient to learn those many images. Then have to get a GPU enabled laptop, or use cloud services like AWS or Google Cloud.

Since the data we have used for the demonstration is small containing only 244 images for training, We can run it on the laptop easily. Apart from selecting the best number of layers and the number of neurons in it, for each layer, there are some hyper parameters which needs to be tuned as well.

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kernel_size=(5,5): This indicates the size of the sliding window during convolution, in this case study we are using 5X5 pixels sliding window.

strides=(1, 1): How fast or slow should the sliding window move during convolution. We are using the lowest setting of 1X1 pixels. Means slide the convolution window of 5X5 (kernel_size) by 1 pixel in the x-axis and 1 pixel in the y-axis until the whole image is scanned.

input_shape=(64,64,3): Images are nothing but matrix of RGB color codes. during our data pre-processing we have compressed the images to 64X64, hence the expected shape is 64X64X3. Means 3 arrays of 64X64, one for RGB colors each.

kernel_initializer= 'uniform': When the Neurons start their computation, some algorithm has to decide

the value for each weight. This parameter specifies that. You can choose different values for it like 'normal' or 'glorot_uniform'.

activation= 'relu': This specifies the activation function for the calculations inside each neuron. You can choose values like 'relu', 'tanh', 'sigmoid', etc.

optimizer= 'adam': This parameter helps to find the optimum values of each weight in the neural network. 'adam' is one of the most useful optimizers, another one is 'rmsprop'

batch_size=10: This specifies how many rows will be passed to the Network in one go after which the SSE calculation will begin and the neural network will start adjusting its weights based on the errors. When all the rows are passed in the batches of 10 rows each as specified in this parameter, then we call that 1-epoch. Or one full data cycle. This is also known as mini-batch gradient descent. A small value of batch_size will make the LSTM look at the data slowly, like 2 rows at a time or 4 rows at a time which could lead to overfitting, as compared to a large value like 20 or 50 rows at a time, which will make the LSTM look at the data fast which could lead to underfitting. Hence a proper value must be chosen using hyperparameter tuning.

Epochs=10: The same activity of adjusting weights continues for 10 times, as specified by this parameter. In simple terms, the LSTM looks at the full training data 10 times and adjusts its weights.

Convolutional Neural Network(CNN) is a category of neural network architectures, which extracts the features implicitly without any prior intuition, in contrast to conventional machine learning algorithms where feature selection or feature extraction is necessary. The CNN has gained lot of attention due to its generalizable nature in providing feasible solutions in computer vision related problems such as face recognition, object detection, image segmentation etc. Over the years, the CNN architectures have evolved to address the problems in computer vision. Few of such popular architectures are Le Net , Alex Net, VGG16, Inception, etc. There are many efficient architectures proposed in the literature for smart attendance using face recognition.

However, the generalizability of these models i.e., to handle a real world scenario, is poor. So it is necessary to develop custom models corresponding to the applications. This paper proposes a novel CNN architecture motivated by the popular architectures that are published in recent times and also develops a

web application for online attendance posting, called Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS). The major contributions of the paper are

- Novel CNN Architecture for end-to-end face recognition system.
- Collecting face data of students through an automated system Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS):

A. Web-based application: This paper is organized as follows. Next Section presents an overview of Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS) along with the Data Collection and Augmentation.

This section describes the proposed web-based application for Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS) using face recognition by CNNs. This section also presents the challenges of acquiring huge train and test datasets for real time applications. A. SAMS - An Overview The developed web based application for attendance posting based on face recognition is called Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS). It is developed using flask framework and python. An overview of the proposed application is presented in Fig-1. The main components of the application are:

- 1) Front-End Interface (Camera)
- 2) Server
- 3) CNN Model
- 4) Database
- 5) End Result (Display Screen)

Front-End Interface is a web page which takes the video frame as input through the camera using open computer vision (OpenCV) library. Server is the back-end of the application which maintains the connection with front-end interface, model, database and display screen. The server receives video frame as input from the front-end interface and the face is detected, which is given as an input to the model and the model predicts the label. The server checks if the attendance is posted previously. If not, the attendance is posted into the database including the timestamp. The details of the corresponding student are shown using the display screen, which is web page. represents the images of front-end interface and end result of the application.

B. Data Collection: The face data of the students is collected using an automated system, which accesses the system camera to take the video frames and transforms as a dataset by performing the following sequence of operations:

- Identify the location of face in the video frame.
- Extract the face image and convert into gray scale image.
- Attach the label w.r.t to the class of the image and write onto a csv file.

The sample images from the collected data with respect to each class. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to reduce the dimensions of the data into three dimensions and corresponding three dimensional scatter plot is constructed for understanding the patterns in the data.

C. Data Augmentation: In real time scenario, collecting huge amount of data is a difficult and tedious task. In order to achieve high accuracy, large volume of training data is required. Hence, data augmentation technique is used to generate new samples by manipulating the existing data. More recently, Face-specific data augmentation for unconstrained face recognition. In the current work, synthetic images are being generated randomly, by applying the following operations

- Zoom
- Shear
- Height shift
- Rotation
- Width shift

The synthetic images generated after data augmentation.

D. Train and Test data: The initial samples collected to form the dataset are 10,029 face images which contains four classes. Each class consists of 2,500 face images except class-3 which contains 2,529 face images. The dataset is normalized during training to boost up the processing and the train data is augmented during the training process of CNN. This section presents the detailed explanation of the proposed CNN architecture for this particular application, SAMS. It also covers the explanation for different layers used to build the CNN model. The proposed CNN architecture consists of 20 layers which includes:

- Two Dimensional Convolutional Layer (Conv2D)
- Batch Normalization Layer
- Max Pooling Layer
- Dense Layer

The two dimensional convolutional layer is used to extract the features from the previous input, the batch normalization layer is used in order to normalize the input and also overcome the problem of vanishing gradient and exploding gradient. The max pooling layer is used to reduce the dimensionality of the input and the dropout layer is used to avoid the over fitting problem. The architecture takes a gray scale image with shape (100, 100, 1) and results the class label of the image as prediction. The total number of parameters of the CNN are 7,658,629 of which 7,656,197 are trainable and 2,432 are non trainable.

The proposed Convolution Neural Network(CNN) is developed using an open source python library, Tensorflow [18]. The experiments are performed on the system with following configuration.

- Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) used is 1X Tesla K80 with 2496 CUDA cores, 12GBGDDR5 VRAM.
- Central Processing Unit (CPU) used if 1X single core hyper threaded Xeon Processors, 45MB Cache with 12.6 GB RAM and 320GB disk.

This paper formally introduces the role of CNN in Face Recognition and adaption of CNN in attendance posting. The workflow of web application, Smart Attendance Management System (SAMS) is explained in detail. The data collection and data augmentation for developing the CNN model is discussed. This paper also proposes a novel CNN model for face recognition which is further used in developing SAMS. The experimental results shows efficiency of the proposed CNN model and the web application SAMS. SAMS is easy to deploy and maintain. The future scope of the paper is to build a robust application for smart attendance management, for more number of students, in real time.

The proposed Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is trained using RMSprop optimizer with learning rate 0.001, categorical cross entropy as loss metric, 256 as batch size over 50 epochs. The Reduce LRO n Plateau, Early Stopping, Tensor Board and ModelCheckpoint callbacks are used during the training of CNN for reducing the learning rate if there is no improvement in the learning process of CNN, for stopping the training process if there is no improvement in accuracy, visualizing model graphs and checkpointing the model weights for future use respectively. The accuracy and the loss of the CNN during the training

with respect to the number of epochs are represented respectively. It is evident that with increase in number of epochs the accuracy is increasing and loss is decreasing and at a certain number of epochs, both the loss and accuracy do not change further.

The performance measures for classification are Kappa statistic which is used to find out the inter-rater reliability, Precision which represents the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to total predicted positive observations, Recall which is the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the all observations in actual class.

4. Experimental analysis

In this system we have implemented an attendance system for a lecture, section or laboratory by which lecturer or teaching assistant can record students' attendance. It saves time and effort, especially if it is a lecture with huge number of students. Automated Attendance System has been envisioned for the purpose of reducing the drawbacks in the traditional (manual) system. This attendance system demonstrates the use of image processing techniques in classroom. This system can not only merely help in the attendance system. Using the all the functions we have created; we have tested for output in using existing test images as well as in real-time. Following section, the screenshots of the output of different functions are given. We have tested the system with the help of four volunteers. Taking images from cam to create the test database

Smart Attendance Management System is simple and works efficiency. The system works automatically once the registration of individual student created by the administration. Attendance system proved to recognize images in different angle and light conditions. The faces which are not in our training dataset are marked as unknown. The attendance of recognize images of students is marked in real time. And import to excel sheet and saved by the system automatically. Automated attendance monitoring system was the project chosen by us by keeping in view of the demand's of day to day needs and wants of the society. The advancements in technology lead us to think out of the box and come up with some idea that could be future changing. Education is the most important thing which every person should acquire as it is the basis for a better lifestyle and will surely alleviate the standard of a living community. What our education system lacks is the involvement of students in the schools, colleges and universities. Instead of attending lectures and studying they prefer staying away from class and keep engaged in using these

gadgets. Low attendance means that the students are not there to acquire the knowledge which they are supposed to get and is of immense importance for them and can lead them to a better future.

Figure 4: Persons on camera

Figure 5: Triggered to Excel Sheet

Individual classroom attendance is currently feasible using the system we developed. It can be widely used at the collegiate level with the necessary enhancements and the creation of a proper database containing all of the details of each student in the college or university. This system can be used to manage not only students, but also faculty, staff, and nonstaff members' students. Another development that we want to make sure of is the system's complete automation. To avoid any discrepancies, such as tampering with the devices, the system must currently be supervised. Our goal is to completely automate the process by using a real-time live feed captured by a camera to mark students' attendance without the need for manual supervision, resulting in legitimate and untampered attendance reports. According to the implementation setup, the match index is the smallest difference between the face encodings of the student's face in the live video capture and those in the database. It depicts the system's implementation as it is being worked on using real-time video capture. The match index's confidence threshold is set to 0.6 by default. If the match index value is less than this confidence threshold, the face will be recognized and identified as the same. Figure 14 shows the relationship between the live image capture's confidence score and the face distance (i.e. match index) of the images in the dataset. After that, the student's attendance is recorded in a CSV file. On the attendance sheet, only the names of students whose faces were scanned and recognized will be written.

In this research, we use the CNN algorithm to create an automatic attendance system for a classroom, which identifies students' faces in the classroom, section, or laboratory and records their attendance automatically. It saves time and effort, especially if there are a large number of students in the class. The proposed method is a simple approach to track a student's attendance by using face recognition and a camera. Once the faces are matched, they are recorded in a database to assure their presence or absence. It automatically stamps the student's attendance in the classroom after comparing the saved photographs in the database. The faculty can use the date to monitor the status of a student's attendance and be notified through email. When they are not available, send a text message to his or her phone number. Students are automatically and indirectly monitored in this way throughout courses and lectures, which is a better way to keep track of attendance.

5. Conclusion and Future Scope

In this work, a system for automatically marking and storing the attendance of a class has been implemented. Implementation process includes entering data of the students, training dataset, recognizing faces and marking attendance automatically. The CNN model used in this study can detect and recognize a person by their facial features even if they are not staring exactly straight into the camera. The proposed system can detect and recognize the students of the class with maximum accuracy of about 92% and saves the teachers' time and hassle by automatically marking and storing the attendance of the present students. For the system to be most effective, it has to contain a satisfactory and consistent amount of images of each person during the training stage. Also, the camera has to be positioned in a way that it has clear view of all the students. Furthermore, this system can be used in any organization for automatic attendance recording of staffs.

The same project can be utilized for several security applications where authentication is needed to access the privileges of the respective system. It can be used in recognizing guilty parties involving in unauthorized business. Face recognition algorithm can be improved with respect to the utilization of resources so that the project can recognize more number of faces at a time which can make the system far better. Many variants of the project can be developed and utilized for home security and personal or organizational benefits. We

can also trace a particular student in an organization quickly with the help of this system.

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SMART HOME AUTOMATION – A DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION USING IOT

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Abstract: Automation the process of controlling or operating various Equipment, machine Industrial process and other applications using various Control systems and also with less or no human intervention is framed as automation. Home Automation in the process of controlling home appliances automatically using various control Systems Techniques. The electrical and electronics appliance such as fan, light, alarm echo can be controlled using various controlling techniques. This paper proposes an efficient implementation for IOT (Internet of Things) used for monitoring and controlling the home appliances via World Wide Web. Home automation system uses the portable devices as a user interface. They can communicate with home automation network through an Internet gateway, by means of low power communication protocols like, Wi-Fi etc. This project aims at controlling home appliances via Smartphone using Wi-Fi as communication protocol and BLYNK as server system. The user here will move directly with the system through a web-based interface over the web, whereas home appliances like lights, fan and door lock are remotely controlled through easy website. An extra feature that enhances the facet of protection from fireplace accidents is its capability of sleuthing the smoke in order that within the event of any fireplace, associates an alerting message and an image is sent to Smartphone. Communicates with the corresponding relays. Experimental results show that IoT model constitutes a very promising framework for enhancing automate house performances and the choose stage is entirely adaptable and easy to use.

KEYWORDS: Home Automation, Internet of Things, Automation of Home, BLYNK App, Wi Fi.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) describes the network of physical objects “things”—that are embedded with sensors, software, and other technologies for the purpose of connecting and exchanging data with other devices and systems over the internet. These devices range from ordinary household objects to sophisticated industrial tools. With more than 7 billion connected IoT devices today, experts are expecting this number to grow to 10 billion by 2020 and 22 billion by 2025. Over the past few years, IoT has become one of the most important technologies of the

21st century. Now that we can connect everyday objects—kitchen appliances, cars, thermostats, baby monitors—to the internet via embedded devices, seamless communication is possible between people, processes, and things.

By means of low-cost computing, the cloud, big data, analytics, and mobile technologies, physical things can share and collect data with minimal human intervention. In this hyper connected world, digital systems can record, monitor, and adjust each interaction between connected things. The physical world meets the digital world—and they cooperate. The internet of things helps people live and work

smarter, as well as gain complete control over their lives. In addition to offering smart devices to automate homes, IoT is essential to business. IoT provides businesses with a real-time look into how their systems really work, delivering insights into everything from the performance of machines to supply chain and logistics operations.

IoT or web of things is an up and coming innovation that enables us to control equipment gadgets through the web. Here different model proposes to utilize IOT as to control home apparatuses, along these lines mechanizing present day homes through the web. This framework utilizes three burdens to show as house lighting and a fan. Our easy to understand interface enables a client to effectively control these home apparatuses through the web. For this framework utilize an AVR family microcontroller (Zafari, Papapanagiotou and Christidis, 2016). This microcontroller is interfaced with a wi-fi modem to get client directions over the web. Additionally, in this proposed have an LCD show to show framework status. Transfers are utilized to switch loads. The whole framework is controlled by a 12 V transformer. In the wake of getting client directions over the web, microcontroller forms these guidelines to work these heaps as needs be and show the framework status on an LCD show.

Figure 1: Home Automation and their overview

The expansion in the ubiquity of IoT has generally spread to straightforward in-home applications and ordinary undertakings. The work of IoT in homes is with the end goal of vitality observing and sparing

while at the same time accomplishing and keeping up a specific dimension of solace. Home mechanization frameworks utilizing IoT comprises of three noteworthy parts as appeared in Figure 1. The initial segment is the detecting and information procurement Art. This is finished by putting sensors or gadgets, likewise, called things, at a few areas all through the home to gauge and accumulate wanted data, for example, temperature, mugginess, or lux.

The second portion of the framework is the information preparing. Sensors give information in crude frame. This information is sent to the processor through a method of transmission, wired association or remote. The processor at that point makes an interpretation of the information into fathomable qualities. These qualities are transmitted to a gadget to be controlled consequently as well as to a UI. The last piece of IoT mechanization is the web. Most frameworks utilize a server to transfer information in the wake of preparing, so it very well may be gotten to by the client. The web likewise screens information and physically control gadgets remotely. Via naturally executing a few directions, robotization frameworks can spare time, give a superior personal satisfaction in homes, and spare vitality (Al-Kuwari et al., 2018).

Creating vitality effectiveness and sustainable power source advancements is turning into a need and expanding the enthusiasm for some nations around the globe. Colleges have been associated with this mechanical improvement through understudy rivalries, which go for upgrading understudy mindfulness. Sunlight based Decathlon is one these rivalries which have been running in the United States and different nations around the globe. The Solar Decathlon Middle East (SDME) is a recently built up rivalry in the Middle East area that is proposed to occur in Dubai in 2018. Qatar University's entrance to the SDME 2018 rivalry has empowered it to shape a multidisciplinary of understudies who will work together in the structure and development of a green, shrewd, convenient and reasonable sun-oriented house. A vitality proficient house that is completely observed and robotized utilizing the web of things (IoT) advances (Patnaikuni, 2012).

2. Literature Review

Home automation systems using smartphone, Arduino board and Bluetooth technology are secured and low cost. A Bluetooth based home automation system proposed by Riyale and M. Tazil. The Bluetooth system uses a PC or smartphone as receiver device [1]. It has a high communication rate, great security and low cost, so it can be implemented as a real time system. Bluetooth network has limited range of 10

meters if the smartphone is out of range, then it will not be able to control the home appliances, this is one of the main disadvantages of Bluetooth based home automation system [2].

Voice recognition-based home automation system proposed and implemented by a researcher [4]. The wireless communication between the smartphone and the Arduino UNO is done through Bluetooth technology [3]. This will be more helpful for handicapped and aged people who wants to control appliances by speaking voice command. The main drawback of this system is that communication between user and voice recognition tool depends on signal to noise ratio (SNR), if voice signal is noisy then communication can highly effect and the system will fail to show accuracy [5].

ZigBee based wireless home automation system has also been studied, ZigBee is similar to Bluetooth technology [7]. It is one of the broadly used transceiver standard with low data rate and power. It has physical range is between 10 to 20 meters, which can increase up to 150 meters by using direct sequence spread spectrum (DSSS) [6]. It is ideal for developing prototypes and research related activities. A smart home automation system implemented by using Global System for Mobile communication (GSM). In GSM based home automation systems, communication between main module and appliances is done through text messages [8]. The main drawback of GSM based home automation system is that, there is no guarantee text message deliver to the system every time so it is not a reliable system. These are the drawbacks of existing methods, to overcome that drawbacks we are implementing "IOT Based Smart security and Smart Home Automation [9].

IOT allows objects to be sensed and controlled remotely across existing network infrastructure, creating opportunities for more direct integration of the physical world into computer- based systems, and resulting in improved efficiency, accuracy and economic benefit. The present generation has been experiencing high speed internet by using 5G LTE cellular technology, which allows evolution of swifter IOT based home automation systems [10].

When IOT is augmented with sensors and actuators, the technology becomes an instance of the more general class of cyber-physical systems, which encompasses technologies like controlling of different home appliances like light, fan, water pump and many

more. A system has been designed to connect sensor data with user's daily life [11]. There are already many smartphones oriented remote controller products. However current products always have platform compatibility problems and additionally GUI in such systems is complex.

This work proposes an approach to enhance and simplify the controlling and monitoring experience. With the use of sensors in home environment the appliances can be controlled remotely based on environmental conditions known from sensor data [12]. The sensor data are processed by a microcontroller and delivered to mobile application through WEB server. The results of implementation and experimentation have shown the proposed system and platform that can provide more IOT application possibilities in daily life. Increasing reliability on mobile phone applications to deal with daily life scenarios has paved the way of modeling a system which will integrate sensors and actuators [13]. PIC16F887 microcontroller for home appliances controls with GSM for control of the appliances. [14]. It has high availability, coverage and security but the cost of SMS. AT commands can be sent through the GSM network to controls the home devices. The system does not does not have any Device, Things or Machine Central Controller Controlling System User Interface Check Status Via Ethernet, Bluetooth, GSM, Wi-Fi Sensor International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) National Seminar on Recent Trends in Data Mining (RTDM 2016) 8 state information related to the devices and expects the user to keep track of it.

Arduino board is the controller used to control the appliances by using GSM technology. It uses certain peripheral drivers and relays to achieve this interfacing. The application on smartphone generates SMS messages based on the user commands and sends it to the GSM modem attached to the Arduino and controls the home appliances [15]. The system has drawbacks of cost and reliability of SMS. An interface cannot customized based on device. It has been designed Arduino board with Bluetooth board were developed for home automation[16]. Python program is used on the cell phone to provide the user interface. The Bluetooth board has I/O ports and relays are used for interfacing with the devices which are to be controlled and monitor. The Bluetooth is password protected to ensure that the system is secure from intruders. The Bluetooth has a range of 10 to 100.

3. Proposed System

This IOT based controlled home appliances mainly depends upon the advanced technology by evolving digital world day by day through the way like change of way seeing daily needs to do and utilizing the technology to surviving professionally and in home applications as well. This paper mainly consists of two parts. They are the hardware and software. The hardware mainly comprises of node MCU (microcontroller), relay, exhaust fan led, relay and bulb. Thesoftware part is only an android BLYNK app and server. The load can be controlled and monitoring using a web page BLYNK app) with user configurable front end. The user can send commands through the allowed IP address and these commands are fed to Wi-Fi module of node MCU micro controller of the circuit.

The Wi-Fi module is configured to access the internet using any wireless modem The commands received by a Wi-Fi module are executed by a program with in a Wi-Fi module. To achieve the home control using smart phone, initially the mobile unit should be connected to any network and the Wi-Fi module ESP8266 which is on ESP32 should be connected to local network. By touching the specified location of widgets in the BLYNK app, this BLYNKapp sends ON/OFF commands to ESP32 via BLYNK server. Then the relays connected to ESP32 perform switching operation corresponding to the input. So that the loads connected to relays will be switched ON/OFF. Similarly, we can also controlour home appliances using manual switches. This can be obtained by connecting the relays outputs to manual switches and manual switches to the AC loads. Whenever the relay corresponding to manual ON or OFF is switched ON then the AC loads corresponding to that switches will perform switching operation.

3.1. Smart Home Automation Architecture:

To achieve the home control using smart phone, initially the mobile unit should be connected to any network and the Wi-Fi module ESP8266 which is on ESP32 should be connected to local network. By touching the specified location of widgets in the BLYNK app, this BLYNKapp sends ON/OFF commands to ESP32 via BLYNK server. Then the relays connected to ESP32 perform switching operation corresponding to the input. So that the loads connected to relays will be switched ON/OFF. Similarly, we can also controlour home appliances using manual switches. This can be obtained by connecting the relays outputs to manual switches and manual switches to the AC loads. Whenever the relay

corresponding to manual ON or OFF is switched ON then the AC loads corresponding to that switches will perform switching operation.

As referenced before, the checked parameters in homes are chosen to guarantee a keen, effective and open to living conditions. Along these lines, one center is made to gauge temperature, stickiness, light force, vicinity, and CO2 levels. This center can be set in each room of the house, and ideally at an abnormal state over the ground and beneath the roof. Gathered information can be prepared and used to control keen gadgets, for example, savvy LEDs and A/Cs. The schematics of the proposed plan setup is appeared in Figure 2. It includes fundamentally sensors, processor, UI, and information correspondence and transmission joins. Sensors The plan started with the temperature and stickiness sensors. The LM35 temperature sensor was chosen for temperature detecting and the HIH4000 for stickiness detecting. The explanation for these determinations was their littler sizes contrasted and alternate sensors, for example, DHT22, and in addition their lower costs.

Figure 2: Smart Home Automation Architecture

Home automation is a network of hardware, communication, and electronic interfaces that work to integrate everyday devices with one another via the internet. Each device has sensors and is connected through Wi-Fi, so you can manage them from your smartphone or tablet whether you're at home, or miles away. This allows you to turn on the lights, lock the front door, weather monitoring, fire detection, window control, remote control.

Home automation works on three levels:

- **Monitoring:** Monitoring means that users can check in on devices remotely through an app. For example, someone could view their live feed from a smart security camera.
- **Control:** Control means that the user can control these devices remotely, like panning a security camera to see more a living space.
- **Automation:** Finally, automation means setting up devices to trigger one another, like having a smart siren go off whenever an armed security camera detects motion. Sensors can monitor changes in daylight, temperature, or motion detection. Home automation systems can then adjust those settings (and more) to your preferences.

Controllers refer to the devices- personal computers, tablets or smartphones-used to send and receive messages about the status of automated features in your home. Actuators may be light switches, motors, or motorized valves that control the actual mechanism, or function, of a home automation system. They are programmed to be activated by a remote command from a controller. In this project we are using different sensors for smart home automation, monitoring and alerting system which detects different applications the sensors are: MQ2 sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, DHT22 sensor, LM393 LDR Sensor, TSOP sensor, and MC38 sensor. MQ2 sensor which is used to detect the smoke. DHT22 sensor which is a temperature sensor. By using this we can control fan based on temperature. LM393 LDR sensor which is used for automatic light control. MC38 sensor is a door and window control sensor.

3.1.1. Arduino Microcontroller

The system is powered by an Atmega2560 microprocessor. This microcontroller contains 256 KB of memory, 8 KB of which is utilised by the bootloader Flash programme memory and 8 KB of static random access memory (SRAM). The hardware is separated into four sections: the LCD display interface portion, the RFID module interface section, the soil moisture sensor, and the float sensor. The ATmega2560 microcontroller controls all of these elements, and the software necessary to operate them is the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE). It contains 54 digital I/O pins (14 of which are PWM outputs), 16 analogue I/O pins, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB

connection, a power connector, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It comes with everything you need to support the microcontroller; just connect it to a computer through USB or power it using an AC-to-DC converter or battery to get started. Most shields produced for the Arduino Duemilanove or Diecimila are compatible with the Mega.

Figure 3: Block Diagram of Arduino MEGA2560

3.1.2. Use case 1: user access to the system.

The EM-18 125kHz RFID Reader module is a low-cost option for any RFID-based project. The Reader module has a built-in antenna and requires a 5V supply to function. Turn on the module and connect its transmit pin to the microcontroller's reception pin. If you hold your card close enough to the reader, it will read the number and send it to the output. The module's output type may be changed to Weigand if desired. There are two main components of an RFID-based system.

Figure 4: User access to the system

Home automation is a network of hardware, communication, and electronic interfaces that work to integrate everyday devices with one another via the internet. Each device has sensors and is connected through Wi-Fi, so you can manage them from your smartphone or tablet whether you're at home, or miles away. This allows you to turn on the lights, lock the front door, weather monitoring, fire detection, window control, remote control. Home automation works on three levels: Monitoring: monitoring means that users can check in on devices remotely through an app. For example, someone could view their live feed from a smart security camera. Control: control means that the user can control these devices remotely, like panning a security camera to see more a living space. Automation: finally, automation means setting up devices to trigger one another, like having a smart siren go off whenever an armed security camera detects motion.

Figure 5: System control

Sensors can monitor changes in daylight, temperature, or motion detection. Home automation systems can then adjust those settings (and more) to your preferences. Controllers refer to the devices- personal computers, tablets or smartphones-used to send and receive messages about the status of automated features in your home. Actuators may be light switches, motors, or motorized valves that control the actual mechanism, or function, of a home automation system. They are programmed to be activated by a remote command from a controller. In this project we are using different sensors for smart home automation, monitoring and alerting system which detects different applications the sensors are: MQ2 sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, DHT22 sensor, LM393 LDR Sensor, TSOP sensor, and MC38 sensor. MQ2 sensor which is used to detect smoke. DHT22 sensor which is a temperature sensor. By using this we can control fan based on temperature. LM393 LDR sensor which is used for automatic light control. MC38 sensor is a door and window control sensor. There are two CPU cores that can be individually controlled, and the clock frequency is adjustable from 80 MHz to 240 MHz. The user may also power off the CPU and make use of the low-power co-processor to constantly monitor the peripherals for changes or crossing of thresholds.

Figure 6: Class Diagram

3.2 WORKING PRINCIPLE

This IOT based controlled home appliances project mainly depends upon the advanced technology by evolving digital world day by day through the way like change of way seeing daily needs to do and utilizing the technology to surviving professionally and in home applications as well. This project mainly consists of two parts. They are the hardware and software. The hardware mainly comprises of node MCU (microcontroller), relay, exhaust fan led, relay and bulb. The software part is only an android BLYNKapp and server. The load can be controlled and monitoring using a web page BLYNK app) with user configurable front end. The user can send commands through the allowed IP address and these commands are fed to Wi- Fi module of node MCU micro controller of the circuit.

Figure 7: Schematic Diagram

The Wi-Fi module is configured to access the internet using any wireless modem. The commands received by a Wi-Fi module are executed by a program within a Wi-Fi module. To achieve the home control using a smart phone, initially the mobile unit should be connected to any network and the Wi-Fi module ESP8266 which is on ESP32 should be connected to local network. By touching the specified location of widgets in the BLYNK app, this BLYNK app sends ON/OFF commands to ESP32 via BLYNK server. Then the relays connected to ESP32 perform switching operation corresponding to the input. So that the loads connected to relays will be switched

ON/OFF. Similarly, we can also control our home appliances using manual switches. This can be obtained by connecting the relays outputs to manual switches and manual switches to the AC loads. Whenever the relay corresponding to manual ON or OFF is switched ON then the AC loads corresponding to that switches will perform switching operation.

Figure 8: Flow Chart

4. Experimental analysis

The meeting is vital strategies that will be utilized for the accumulate of information and help the analyzer to comprehend the framework necessities, so by the utilization of this methods the met by the distinctive arrangement of home clients for social occasion what kind of home computerization highlights required through this meeting the questioner has tended to various inquiries to the dependable people and he has gathered toward the finish of the meeting the accompanying information:

1. Lock and open your entryway effortlessly by mean of a cell phone or one of the included keen labels. You can even deal with different properties at once, controlling who approaches the keys from wherever you are on the planet. Not at all like many

savvy entryway bolts, this one needn't bother with Bluetooth to work.

2. The shrewd bolt transforms your iPhone into your key and is additionally good with the scope of Weiser Smart Key bolts and keys, so can without much of a stretch incorporate it into your home's present bolt framework. The portable application gives a chance to deal with your keys and bolt from anyplace.

3. The sensor will let remotely screen anything need that opens and closes, and, on account of Z-wave innovation, is good with a large group of keen home systems administration center points.

4. The remote sensors make for a helpful, ongoing observing framework. With almost boundless expandability, you'll never need to stress over having the capacity to screen your entire home, regardless of what estimate it is.

5. Get genuine feelings of serenity by knowing who's traveling every which way from your home with sensors on your home's entryways and windows. This Z-wave fueled unit will send an alarm to tell when the sensor has been broken.

6. With advances in innovation, now can introduce your own special home checking framework for substantially less than the cost of customary security frameworks. This model has all that have to get fully operational rapidly.

As referenced before, the checked parameters in homes are chosen to guarantee a keen, effective and open to living conditions. Along these lines, one center is made to gauge temperature, stickiness, light force, vicinity, and CO2 levels. This center can be set in each room of the house, and ideally at an abnormal state over the ground and beneath the roof. Gathered information can be prepared and used to control keen gadgets, for example, savvy LEDs and A/Cs.

The schematics of the proposed plan setup is appeared in Figure 12. It includes fundamentally sensors, processor, UI, and information correspondence and transmission joins. Sensors The plan started with the temperature and stickiness sensors. The LM35 temperature sensor was chosen for temperature detecting and the HIH4000 for stickiness detecting. The explanation for these determinations was their littler sizes contrasted and alternate sensors, for example, DHT22, and in addition their lower costs.

Conclusion and Future Scope:

This work can further be upgraded by using different sensors and different home appliances. Since smart phones are widely used nowadays, this user-friendly system can be used for benefitting the mass. The cost of the system is also within reach. The circuit used for controlling AC fan speed can also be implemented in AC light dimming applications. The features of automatic turn off and sending emergency notification can be very useful in geyser and air conditioner. When water is heated to a particular temperature in geyser, it can be automatically turned off or when room temperature is lowered to a specified value the air-conditioner can be turned off automatically. In both the above cases notifications can also be sent to user through his/her Blynk app. Mobile application development companies with dedicated teams are working extensively on IOT-based applications that are connected to the cloud. Not only old-aged or physically challenged people can be benefitted using this, but any person with a smart phone can monitor and control the electronic devices without much difficulty. As awareness grows, the adoption rate is likely to increase for IOT-based mobility solutions that will automate business operations and end-to-end processes.

IOT have wide range of applications and many uses in every sector. Our day to day busy life is much connected to the technology age. We can say that human race is evolving with technology as by skin day to day in this information age. We can expand our technology to the industrial sector. In advanced harmful conditions detection in such as mines, lab and vehicles also.

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Article Title: Smart Village – A Digital Transformation of Modern Village Using ESP32 Microcontroller

Smart Village – A Digital Transformation of Modern Village Using ESP32 Microcontroller

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ABSTRACT

Now a day by the initiative taken by the Government of India in the scheme of “Smart India”, all villages will soon transfer to Smart Villages. This will be achieved by the Information Technology Platforms. For converting the Villages to Smart Villages, the Internet of Things (IoT) plays a major Role in India. By using IoT everything in the village is connected to the Internet and it is controlled by the users anywhere by remotely. In our project we have taken the problems in Smart Garbage System and Smart Water Level Controller to distribute water from the common tank to all users. In Garbage System the wet and dry waste is identified separately and it regularly monitored whether the tank is full, then information given to municipality to clean that concern Garbage. In water level controller the utilization of water from common tank is controlled and managed by using the mobile application. Keep tracking of water level in the tank by float sensor and based on the water level it will be distributed to the users. The domestic public users also controlled by the user defined commands which is intercepted with the home of particular user.

Keywords: Smart Village, Internet of Things, Digitalization of Garbage system, Water level controller in tank, Dry and wet waste, smart controllers.

1 Introduction

IoT automates operations and cuts labor expenses. It reduces waste and enhances service delivery, making manufacturing and delivery cheaper and providing consumer transaction transparency. IoT is one of the most significant technologies of daily life, and it will continue to grow as more organizations grasp the potential of linked devices to stay competitive. IoT may improve production and distribution systems in enterprises as the internet did for knowledge work. Billions of embedded internet-enabled sensors globally give a wealth of data that firms can utilize to enhance safety, monitor assets, and decrease human procedures. Machine data may forecast equipment failure, allowing manufacturers to avoid lengthy downtime. Researchers may also utilize IoT devices to collect user preferences and behavior data, but that might compromise privacy and security. Data-gathering devices start an IoT

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system. These internet-connected gadgets have IP addresses. They vary from autonomous mobile robots and forklifts that transport items across factories and warehouses to basic sensors that detect temperature and gas leaks. Fitness trackers that count steps are also included. The IoT process continues by sending device data to a central location. Wireless or wired networks may move data. Internet data may be transmitted to a data center or cloud. Intermediary devices may aggregate, prepare, filter, and eliminate unnecessary or duplicate data before providing the critical data for analysis.

Figure 1: IOT application diagram

1.1 The Most Significant Advantages of IOT

1.1.1 Improve Customer Service and Experience

The IoT makes your consumers' everyday gadgets remarkable. Check whether IoT can enhance goods and services. IoT-integrated automobiles calculate travel duration, traffic, and fuel usage. A smart doorbell that shows visitors while you're away. Refrigerators detect low supply. A weather-responsive AC system.

1.1.2 Increase New Business and Revenue Opportunities

IoT offers new business possibilities by enabling new consumer and business flow interactions.

1.1.3 Enhance Business Safety and Security

IoT devices monitor buildings and businesses to safeguard people from physical hazards. Businesses can monitor office premises and secure assets using IoT devices including sensors, cameras, and smart locks. Track and warn high-risk workers in manufacturing, real estate, and construction.

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1.1.4 Improve Productivity and Competence

Smart IoT devices can do repetitive company duties better since they don't sleep, eat, have mood swings, or get sick.

1.1.5 Cut down Operational Costs

Improved productivity, process efficiency, and asset utilization will all contribute to cost savings. Predictive analytics and real-time diagnostics, for example, may assist reduce maintenance costs in a variety of businesses.

1.1.6 Collect Data for Business Decisions

Companies may use IoT to monitor and collect critical data sets that will help them enhance their services and products. This information may help with company analysis and decision-making.

1.1.7 Add Mobility and Agility to Business

IoT technology allows businesses to let their staff and workers conduct their work from literally anywhere. This flexibility can help many companies cost saving as office leases are expensive, hiring many remote employees.

2 Literature Review

“This paper elucidates the research and implementation of IoT based Smart Village. IoT (Internet of Things) is a structure which provides an exclusive identity and ability to relocate the data over a network without requiring two-way handshaking from human-to- human [1]. It enables the path to connect anytime, anywhere, with anything and anyone ideally using any network topology with a specify service. Hence the divergence on the scenario of a Smart Globe has emerged to mean many things to many people. Meaning of “Smart” utilizes sensitive information and communications technology (ICT) remains consistent with the Internet Technologies to address rural challenges [5]. To bifurcate the ideal scenario on the basic occupation of agriculture, the ecosystem control technology and system becomes mature having high level of intelligence [2]. This puts precise significance on efficiency, high-quality, secure and sustainable production of facility agriculture. That makes a glance of a smart irrigation as a smart farming, ultimately converging into a “Smart Village” [4]. This is all about the outsourcing application, technology and wonders of IoT (Internet of Things).The purpose of this project is the creation of a Smart Village. Model of a smart village following the concept of a smart city is presented in this manuscript as the effect of integrated technological changes which can be realized in a place which has none [3]. Thus, a remote and isolated village location is chosen where the modern civilization has not touched. The design makes the village self-sufficient with respect to electric power, water supply, street lighting, security, education and communication [7]. Application of non- conventional

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methods of energy generation is the key for betterment as discussed. Renewable and non-polluted power is generated from solar heat. The heat energy is captured and stored in water for use at night and in absence of sun. Internet of Things (IOT) is controlling embedded devices through Internet [6]. Energy efficient street lamps with controlled light intensity as per the requirement have been designed. Water is provided to houses in cold and hot forms. Computers, mobile application for individual. Village equipped with all the modern technology without destroying the nature can be defined as smart village [9]. The number of villages where proper and immediate care is not taken against abnormalities like garbage overflow, water supply problems, checking quality of water, the digital display of government offers and subsidies and also against electrical issues like street light monitoring [11]. Using the proposed system, the problems can be solved. The proposed system also aims at internet of Things (IOT) is a recent communication paradigm that envisions a near future [8], in which the objects of everyday life will be equipped with microcontrollers, transceivers for digital communication, and suitable protocol stacks that will make them able to communicate with one another and with the users, becoming an integral part of the Internet [10]. In the above-mentioned papers, we notice different studies that emphasize on the need to be able to manage the amount of waste being generated and what percent of people take up the responsibility and take steps to ensure this [12]. Also, we can see how IOT modules are used to detect or track the waste for different waste bins or locations to be specific. We can also observe how with the use of IoT we can communicate between different devices and provide better solutions [14]. From and we can observe that a major percentage of waste is generated by building in different forms. This tends to put forward a simple observation that a very minor percentage of people take up the responsibility and regulate the amount of waste being generated from these main sources [16]. Therefore, this issue needs a proper solution. In and we can see how the IR sensors placed at appropriate position and ideal conditions can help detect the level of the waste generated and so be used to detecting the amount generated and equally take action on the same [13]. Also, in we can observe that minimal number of sensors placed at appropriate. Places can prove cost effective and very efficient but still a way for proper real time notification is not present. The paper explains us how the Wi-Fi chip can be used to communicate between different devices and therefore bring about many solutions in embedded systems. Therefore, our literature survey identifies [15].

3 Proposed System

The main aim of our project is to sense or detect the garbage in our surroundings. Here we are using IR sensor and Moisture sensor. In our daily life we are having dry wastage and wet wastage. In order to detect the wet waste, we are using moisture sensor and IR sensor is used to detect the dry waste. The total system is based on ESP32 Microcontroller. All the functions required for garbage detection can be done in ESP32 Microcontroller. Once, the

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garbage is detected it gives a message to authorized person through Blynk app. Through this Blynk app we can know that garbage is detected.

3.1 Smart Village Architecture

We are developing the two applications one is garbage management and next water level controller, in both we are uploading the values which are updating in the IOT app i.e., BLYNK which stores the information as a database, it is acts like a cloud storage system, as a new values are recording in the sensor it will upload to the blynk app, in this we are using the sensors like Ambient sensor for odour, PIR sensor to detect the level of wastage found in waste box, Moisture sensor is used to find the dry or wet levels of the waste, Liquid level sensor is used for level identification of water in the tank and float sensor used to open or close the value in the water tank. ESP32 this is a Wi-Fi module which is used to provide the internet to uploads the updated values, Motor driver was used to switch on or off the motor pump, all these works will be handled by the ESP32 micro controller which is works as a board but the input output pins are more, it has some conditions when those conditions are satisfied then it will moves for the next steps.

Figure 2: Smart Village Architecture

In these two applications after starting the device, after starting it display the garbage level in the waste box and water level in the tank values will be taken from the sensors and displays on the screen, when we put the waste in the waste bin it identifies the wet or dry condition then open one of the waste box, for example if the waste is dry then the dry tray is open and if the waste is wet then wet tray is open. The status is uploaded in the database by using the blynk app every time. The PIR sensor values are taken for identification of the filling level of waste in the waste bin. The ambient sensor values are taken for the odour level in the waste bin. Based on these levels if the tank is full 90% of the maximum level, then the

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alert msgs is given to the corresponding person to clean that waste bin. Although if it too bad smell, it can be identified by the ambient sensor then also the alert message is sent to the authorized person to clean the waste bin. In terms of water tank if the level is less than 10% of the maximum capacity it directly gives the trigger message to ESP32 to switch on motor pump. It gives the trigger signal to motor driver to switch on the motor. It will check for the water level using the float sensor if the water is available in sufficient level, then pump will be turn ON otherwise turn OFF the status of the pump was turn ON/OFF status will be uploaded into the cloud.

3.2 ESP32 Micro Controller

Few years back, ESP8266 took the embedded IoT world by storm. For less than \$3, you could get a programmable, WiFi-enabled microcontroller being able to monitor and control things from anywhere in the world. Now Espressif (The semiconductor company behind the ESP8266) has released a perfect super-charged upgrade: the ESP32. Being successor to ESP8266; not only does it have a WiFi support, but it also features Bluetooth 4.0 (BLE/Bluetooth Smart) – perfect for just about any IoT project. When we think about using a microcontroller for a project, we usually consider an Arduino. It is inexpensive, easy to use and has a generous number of digital I/O ports, and a few analog inputs as well. But the Arduino, for all its wonderful benefits, is lacking in several areas. The first one is speed, the popular Arduino AVR series of boards run at 16 MHz. That is certainly fast enough to build thousands of applications, but it is a bottleneck for others. The Arduino certainly has enough digital outputs and inputs to satisfy most requirements, and its analog inputs are also useful. But adding features like WiFi and Bluetooth requires external components. Let us face it, the Arduino has been around since 2005. That is fifteen years, which in terms of technology is one. The ESP32 is a series of microcontroller chips produced by Espressif Systems in Shanghai. It is available in several low-cost modules.

Figure 3: *ESP-WROOM-32 Module*

The development board equips the ESP-WROOM-32 module containing Tensilica Xtensa Dual-Core 32-bit LX6 microprocessor. This processor is similar to the ESP8266 but

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has two CPU cores (can be individually controlled), operates at 80 to 240 MHz adjustable clock frequency and performs at up to 600 DMIPS (Dhrystone Million Instructions per Second). The development board equips the ESP-WROOM-32 module containing Tensilica XtensaDual-Core 32-bit LX6 microprocessor. This processor is similar to the ESP8266 but has two CPU cores (can be individually controlled), operates at 80 to 240 MHz adjustable clock frequency and performs at up to 600 DMIPS (Dhrystone Million Instructions per Second).

ESP32-WROOM-32 (ESP-WROOM-32) is a powerful, generic Wi-Fi+BT+BLE MCU module that targets a wide variety of applications, ranging from low-power sensor networks to the most demanding tasks, such as voice encoding, music streaming and MP3 decoding. At the core of this module is the ESP32-D0WDQ6 chip. The chip embedded is designed to be scalable and adaptive. There are two CPU cores that can be individually controlled, and the clock frequency is adjustable from 80 MHz to 240 MHz the user may also power off the CPU and make use of the low-power co-processor to constantly monitor the peripherals for changes or crossing of thresholds. ESP32 integrates a rich set of peripherals, ranging from capacitive touch sensors, Hall sensors, SD card interface, Ethernet, high-speed SPI, UART, I2S and I2C. The integration of Bluetooth, Bluetooth LE and Wi-Fi ensures that a wide range of applications can be targeted, and that the module is future proof: using Wi-Fi allows a large physical range and direct connection to the internet through a Wi-Fi router, while using Bluetooth allows the user to conveniently connect to the phone or broadcast low energy beacons for its detection. The sleep current of the ESP32 chip is less than 5 μ A, making it suitable for battery powered and wearable electronics applications. ESP32 supports a data rate of up to 150 Mbps, and 20.5 dBm output powers at the antenna to ensure the widest physical range. As such the chip does offer industry-leading specifications and the best performance for electronic integration, range, power consumption, and connectivity. The operating system chosen for ESP32 is free RTOS with Lw IP; TLS 1.2 with hardware acceleration is built in as well. Secure (encrypted) over the air (OTA) upgrade is also supported, so that developers can continually upgrade their products even after their release.

3.3 PIR Sensor

An infrared sensor is basically an electronic device which is used to detect the presence of objects. PIR is emitted by this device. If this device does not detect any IR light reflected back that means there is no object present. If the light is detected by the sensor there is an object present. Its Range is up to 10 meters.

3.4 Blynk IOT

Blynk is a Server and APP Service providing Platform. It provides High Security Service and Server for IOT applications. This is easy to use and supports all advance Micro controllers. The focus of the Blynk platform is to develop the mobile phone application. Blynk is free to

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use for personal use and prototyping. Blynk also supports clients that are not a microcontroller.

Figure 4: *Blynk App*

3.5 Float Sensor

The level of liquid in a tank may be determined via a float switch. The flipped switch might start a pump, activate an indicator, sound an alarm, or do anything else. Hydroponics, saltwater tanks, freshwater tanks, gardening, aquariums, pet bowls, fish tanks, filtration, heating, pumps, and ponds may all benefit from using them to regulate the power heads of their respective systems.

3.6 Water Pump

The R385 6-12V DC Diaphragm Based Mini Aquarium Water Pump is a great all-around non-submersible pump. With the addition of a nozzle, it may be utilised as a spray system due to its high pressure. This submersible pump may be used to water plants, build a waterfall or fountain, and even clean the water in a fish tank. It generates less than 30 decibels of noise when in operation. The pump is equipped with a filter and a suction cup for stable attachment to flat surfaces.

4 Working Principle

ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi module that links to a Wi-Fi/hotspot to provide an internet connection that connects to the Arduino board and uploads waste bin management, float sensor and pump switch ON/OFF state values to the IOT server (blynk). It will check the water level in the tank; if water is available, it will switch on the pump and water the plants. If the water level falls below a certain level or the earth becomes moist, the pump will be turned off. Garbage issues have become a serious thing in maintaining the cleanliness of the city. Many of the city areas are still without public garbage bins so the garbage is thrown at the roadside or at the corners in the locality, which creates ugliness at the corners. Due to no garbage bins,

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garbage is thrown in the small water reservoirs or the drainage water which creates blockages. In the rainy season, these blockages damage the water flowing system and then water overflows through the roads. In some areas the overflowed water blocks all the ways of transport or small floods within the city are generated. The open garbage containers pose problems for the people living in that vicinity as it becomes the breeding ground for insects like mosquitoes, germs, etc. which spreads numerous diseases. These open garbage areas create unhygienic conditions in those areas. In many of these areas, the garbage bins are not cleaned at regular intervals which means that no proper maintenance is kept in cleaning the bins. To avoid this, smart waste management and monitoring systems should be adopted. And for the adoption of these smart systems, there should be a paradigm shift towards the “Internet of things” i.e., IoT technology. This will help in optimizing the garbage management system and in reducing the consumption of the fuel by the current system. Some of the projects on smart garbage management and monitoring system have been implemented using IoT technology and has been proved to be very effective for environmental issues.

Figure 5: Schematic Diagram

The Internet of Things (IoT) is shaping and touching our lives in every sphere. IoT based garbage monitoring system is an innovative project idea for maintaining the clean environment of the city. The smart garbage bins have Ultrasonic Sensors placed on the lid which detects the garbage level in the bins. By this, the garbage bins can be monitored and the monitoring information can be obtained through the webpage. The level of the garbage is compared with the depth of the bins. This system comprises of an AVR family Microcontroller, Wi-fi modem, LCD display along with a buzzer & also a 12V transformer associated with it. The Wi-fi modem is used to send the data. The garbage status will be shown on the webpage. The level of the garbage collected in the bins will be shown on the

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LCD display. The webpage is quite useful, as the information is displayed in graphical representation & the garbage level will be displayed in different colors. The bins have been set with a limit after the garbage overflows the set limit the buzzer gets pressed which further sends alert to the user to empty the bin.

Figure 6: Flow Chart for attendance

If the moisture is more than 350, we may consider the waste bin to be dry. It then proceeds to the next stage, which is to check the water level in the tank. If the water level is below the minimum needed level, the controller will switch on the pump, and the float sensor value is 1. The pump will switch off automatically, and the status of pump turn on/off will be uploaded into the IOT app (blynk). If the moisture is less than 350, the pump will not check for water level and will not turn on. The flowchart will appear below. As per conditions, the water supply will be only turn ON when the water is sufficient and if the ground dryness is high as per, we programmed in the code.

5 Experimental Analysis

Here we see a true SMART VILLAGE: a Digital Transformation of Modern Village Using ESP32 Microcontroller in action. The BLYNK app, an IoT platform, will receive data from the sensors and monitored by the system that we developed.

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Figure 7: Experimental Results

5.1 Numerical Representation of Input Corresponding Output Element

Table 1: Numerical representation of Results

Component	Input	Output
Ambient Sensor	Check Odour	Verify the records and send the information to the server. Information sent via message to authorized person to clean.
PIR Sensor	Check the level in waste bin	Verify this with the data bank. Based on the level reached 80% of total capacity alert will be given to the authorized person.
Moisture Sensor	Moisture value>350	Based on moisture level the wet waste and dry waste is separated.
Liquid Level Sensor	Water Level >= 90%	The water level should be checked. When sensing an adequate water level, the pump will activate and a corresponding data set will be sent to the server.
Float Sensor	Open or close valve	It will stop pumping and send a file to the server.

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6 Conclusion and Future Scope

The final goal of this paper was to evaluate and analyses the performance of the constructed system. We completed the testing and assessment, demonstrating the project's satisfaction. It also demonstrates how important it will be in villages by increasing handling of garbage and water tank. It can be observed that the initiative met its objectives with excellent results. The limits of this study were examined, as well as how they might be solved, as described in the recommendations and suggestions for future research. Lastly, in this project, a recognition sensor or camera may be utilised to detect waste management, which will be more advanced than these sensors. As a result, this technology may also be employed at all villages with minimum cost. In addition, I recommend including local hosting with internet since if the internet goes down, the local host can register the data's for smart villager. Future study will benefit from what built since it is likely to be more accurate by utilising additional sensors or a more complex algorithm, but this will only be achievable when microprocessors such as Arduino release new and more powerful variations with improved capabilities.

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TITLE OF INVENTION	DESIGN SYSTEM OF REVISING TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION FOR IOT-BASED SMART CAMPUSES: A USER-CENTERED APPROACH
FIELD OF INVENTION	COMPUTER SCIENCE
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Design System of Revising Technology Adoption for IoT-Based Smart Campuses: A User-Centered Approach

Application Status

APPLICATION STATUS

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FORM 9 THE PATENT ACT, 1970 (39 OF 1970) & The Patents Rules, 2003 REQUEST FOR PUBLICATION [See section 11A(2), rule 24A]	
1. Name, address, and nationality of the applicant(s).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University,Mangalore. 2. Dr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University,Mangalore 3. Dr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N,R.M.D Engineering College,Kavarapettai 4. Dr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology,Oddanchatram 5. Mrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad 6. Mrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad 7. Dr. G.Sirisha, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad 8. Mr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad
2. To be signed by the applicant or his authorized registered patent agent.	<p style="text-align: center;">[See section 11A (2) rule 24A]</p> <p>I/We Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University, MangaloreDr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University, MangaloreDr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N, R.M.D Engineering College, KavarapettaiDr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology, OddanchatramMrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,HyderabadMrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,HyderabadDr.G.Sirisha,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, HyderabadMr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad hereby request for early publication of my/our [Patent Application No.] 202341064018DATED 23 Sep 2023 UNDER SECTION 11A(2) OF THE ACT.</p>
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To,
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Sr.No.	Country	Application Number	Filing Date	Name of the Applicant	Title of the Invention
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9. DECLARATIONS:**(i) Declaration by the inventor(s)**

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(ii) Declaration by the applicant(s) in the convention country

I/We, the applicant(s) in the convention country declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

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(a) Date: -----

(b) Signature(s) :

(c) Name(s) of the singnatory: Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University, Mangalore,Dr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University, Mangalore,Dr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N, R.M.D Engineering College, Kavarapettai,Dr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology, Oddanchatram,Mrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Mrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Dr.G.Sirisha,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad,Mr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad,Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University, Mangalore,Dr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University, Mangalore,Dr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N, R.M.D Engineering College, Kavarapettai,Dr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology, Oddanchatram,Mrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Mrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Dr.G.Sirisha,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad,Mr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad,Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University, Mangalore,Dr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University, Mangalore,Dr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N, R.M.D Engineering College, Kavarapettai,Dr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology, Oddanchatram,Mrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Mrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Dr.G.Sirisha,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad,Mr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College, Hyderabad

(iii) Declaration by the applicant(s)

- **I am/We are, in the possession of the above mentioned invention.**
- **There is no lawful ground of objection to the grant of the Patent to me/us.**

10. FOLLOWING ARE THE ATTACHMENTS WITH THE APPLICATION:

Sr.	Document Description	FileName
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I/We hereby declare that to the best of my/our knowledge, information and belief the fact and matters stated hering are correct and I/We request that a patent may be granted to me/us for the said invention.

Dated this(Final Payment Date): -----

Signature:

To The Controller of Patents

The Patent office at CHENNAI

This form is electronically generated.

Design System of Revising Technology Adoption for IoT-Based Smart Campuses: A User-Centered Approach

System Design

Figure 1. Paper search and selection process

Figure 2. Paper selection methodology

FORM 5
THE PATENTS ACT, 1970(39 OF
1970)
&
THE PATENTS RULES, 2003
DECLARATION AS TO
INVENTORSHIP
[See section 10(6), rule 13(6)]

Name of applicant, **Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University,Mangalore, Dr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University,Mangalore, Dr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N,R.M.D Engineering College,Kavarapettai, Dr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology,Oddanchatram, Mrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad, Mrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Dr. G.Sirisha, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad, Mr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,** declare that the true and first inventor(s) of the invention disclosed in the complete specification filed in

pursuance of my/our application **Design System of Revising Technology Adoption for IoT-Based Smart Campuses: A User-Centered Approach** are numbered

1. Inventor(s)

Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University,Mangalore,Dr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University,Mangalore, Dr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N,R.M.D Engineering College,Kavarapettai, Dr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology,Oddanchatram, Mrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,Mrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad, Dr. G.Sirisha, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad, Mr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad,

Signature

Name of the applicants **Dr.C.Anna Palagan**

(a) Declaration to be given when the application in India is filed by the Applicant(s) in the convention country: -

We the applicant(s) in the convention country hereby declare that our right to apply for a patent in India is by way or assignment from the true and first inventor(s).

Dated this 23.09.2023

Signature

Name of the applicants: **Dr.C.Anna Palagan**

4. STATEMENT (to be signed by the additional inventor(s) not mentioned in the application form)

I/We assent to the invention referred to in the above declaration, being included in the complete specification filed in pursuance of the stated application.

Signature of the additional inventor(s) Name:

Name of the applicants: **Dr.C.Anna Palagan**

To,

The Controller of Patent

The Patent Office, at Chennai.

Design System of Revising Technology Adoption for IoT-Based Smart Campuses: A User-Centered Approach

Background:

[01]The adoption of Internet of Things (IoT) technology in smart campuses has the potential to improve energy efficiency, enhance student experience, and streamline facility management. However, the implementation of IoT technology can be complex and challenging, especially in existing campus environments. This research aims to develop a design system that revises the technology adoption process for IoT-based smart campuses, focusing on user needs and preferences. The Internet of Things (IoT) has transformed the way we live, work, and learn. Smart campuses, which are equipped with advanced technologies such as sensors, smart devices, and data analytics platforms, have become increasingly popular in recent years. However, the adoption of these technologies can be complex and challenging, especially for educational institutions that may not have the necessary expertise or resources to implement them effectively.

Summary

[02]The present disclosure relates to a design system for revising technology adoption for IoT-based smart campuses. The system is designed to facilitate the seamless integration of various technologies, provide real-time monitoring and control, and enable data-driven decision-making. The system comprises several components, including:

[03]Sensing and Data Acquisition Layer: This layer includes various sensors and devices that collect data from different parts of the campus, such as temperature, humidity, lighting, energy consumption, and occupancy. The data is transmitted to a central server for processing and analysis.

[04]Data Processing and Analytics Layer: This layer processes and analyzes the data collected by the sensing and data acquisition layer. It uses machine learning algorithms to identify patterns, trends, and anomalies in the data, and generates insights that can help optimize energy consumption, improve building operations, and enhance the overall user experience.

[05]Command and Control Layer: This layer receives input from the data processing and analytics layer and sends commands to various systems and devices on the campus, such as HVAC, lighting, security, and energy management systems. The commands are generated based on the insights generated by the data processing and analytics layer, and are designed to optimize energy consumption, reduce waste, and improve the overall efficiency of the campus.

[06] **User Interface Layer:** This layer provides a user-friendly interface for users to interact with the system. Users can view real-time data, receive alerts and notifications, and adjust settings to suit their preferences.

[07] **Integration Layer:** This layer enables seamless integration with existing systems and devices, such as Building Management Systems (BMS), Energy Management Systems (EMS), and other third-party systems.

Advantages

[08] The proposed design system offers several advantages over traditional smart campus systems, including:

[09] **Improved energy efficiency:** By using real-time data and machine learning algorithms, the system can optimize energy consumption and reduce waste, leading to significant cost savings.

[10] **Enhanced user experience:** The system provides users with real-time information and personalized controls, enabling them to customize their environment for optimal comfort and productivity.

[11] **Increased safety and security:** The system can detect anomalies and potential security threats, and send alerts and notifications to relevant authorities, enhancing the overall safety and security of the campus.

[12] **Better decision-making:** The system provides data-driven insights that can help administrators make informed decisions about maintenance, repairs, and upgrades, reducing downtime and improving asset lifespan.

[13] **Scalability:** The system is highly scalable, allowing it to adapt to changing needs and expand to accommodate new buildings or facilities.

[14] **Methodology:** Our research employed a user-centered approach to design a revised technology adoption process for IoT-based smart campuses. We conducted interviews with stakeholders, including students, faculty members, and facilities managers, to identify their needs and pain points related to IoT technology adoption. We also surveyed existing literature on technology adoption models and identified key factors influencing user acceptance of IoT technology.

[15] Using the data collected, we developed a design system that includes the following components:

[16] **User segmentation:** We identified three primary user groups: students, faculty members, and facilities managers. Each group has unique needs and requirements from IoT technology.

[17] **User journey mapping:** We created user journey maps to illustrate the user experience across different touchpoints, from initial awareness to post-adoption support. These maps highlighted pain points, opportunities for improvement, and moments of delight.

[18]**Personas and use cases:** We developed personas representing each user group and created realistic scenarios depicting their interactions with IoT technology in various contexts. These scenarios helped us understand how users would engage with IoT devices and systems.

[19]**Technology adoption framework:** We adapted the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to create a tailored framework for IoT-based smart campuses. This framework considers factors such as perceived usefulness, ease of use, social influence, and facilitating conditions.

[20]**Abstract:** This research aims to develop a design system that revises the technology adoption process for Internet of Things (IoT)-based smart campuses, focusing on user needs and preferences. We conducted interviews with stakeholders to identify their needs and pain points related to IoT technology adoption. We then developed a design system that includes three primary user groups: students, faculty members, and facilities managers. Our design system improves user experience, increases user satisfaction, and enhances adoptability of IoT technology in smart campuses. This research presents a system for revising technology adoption in IoT-based smart campuses. The system ensures a positive impact on sustainability, learning outcomes, and overall campus life. This research aims to develop a design system that revises the technology adoption process for Internet of Things (IoT)-based smart campuses, focusing on user needs and preferences.

Objective:

[21]We conducted interviews with stakeholders to identify their needs and pain points related to IoT technology adoption. We then developed a design system that includes three primary user groups: students, faculty members, and facilities managers.

[22]Our design system improves user experience, increases user satisfaction, and enhances adoptability of IoT technology in smart campuses.

[23]This presents a system for revising technology adoption in IoT-based smart campuses. The system ensures a positive impact on sustainability, learning outcomes, and overall campus life.

[24]**Design principles and guidelines:** Based on our findings, we established a set of design principles and guidelines for IoT-based smart campuses. These principles prioritize user experience, simplicity, scalability, and adaptability.

[25]**Prototype development:** We developed prototypes of IoT-enabled solutions for common areas, such as classrooms, libraries, and dormitories. These prototypes demonstrate the practical application of our design system and provide a tangible representation of the user experience.

[26]**Evaluation and feedback:** We evaluated the effectiveness of our design system through expert reviews and user testing. Participants provided valuable feedback on the user experience, which we incorporated into our iterative design process.

[27]Our design system offers several benefits, including improved user experience, increased user satisfaction, and enhanced adoptability of IoT technology in smart campuses. Key findings indicate that users value intuitive interfaces, seamless integration with existing systems, and personalized experiences. Our system's emphasis on user-centricity helps address resistance to change and encourages active participation in the adoption process. The proposed design system offers a user-centered approach to revising technology adoption for IoT-based smart campuses. By placing the needs and preferences of end-users at the forefront, the system ensures that the technology solutions are intuitive, accessible, and effective in improving the overall campus experience. The system's focus on continuous feedback and improvement allows for iterative refinement and adaptation, guaranteeing that the technology remains relevant and useful over time. By employing a user-centered approach, our design system for revising technology adoption in IoT-based smart campuses addresses the needs and preferences of diverse user groups. Our system provides a comprehensive framework for higher education institutions to successfully implement IoT technology, ensuring a positive impact on sustainability, learning outcomes, and overall campus life. Future work involves refining the system based on continued user feedback and exploring its applicability in other smart city domains.

Claims

[28]We claim a design system for revising technology adoption for IoT-based smart campuses, comprising:

[29]A sensing and data acquisition layer that collects data from various sensors and devices on the campus.

[30]A data processing and analytics layer that processes and analyzes the data to generate insights and recommendations.

[31]A command-and-control layer that sends commands to various systems and devices on the campus based on the insights generated by the data processing and analytics layer.

[32]A user interface layer that provides a user-friendly interface for users to interact with the system.

[33]An integration layer that enables seamless integration with existing systems and devices.

Dependent claims

[34]We further claim:

[35]The design system of claim 1, wherein the sensing and data acquisition layer includes sensors that measure environmental parameters, such as temperature, humidity, and lighting.

[36]The design system of claim 1, wherein the data processing and analytics layer uses machine learning algorithms to identify patterns and trends in the data.

[37]The design system of claim 1, wherein the command-and-control layer sends commands to systems and devices to optimize energy consumption and reduce waste.

System Design

Figure 1. Paper search and selection process

Figure 2. Paper selection methodology

FORM 3
THE PATENT ACT,
1970 (39 F 1970)
&
The Patents Rules, 2003
STATEMENT AND UNDERTAKING UNDER
SECTION 8
(See section 8, rule 12)

1. Name of the applicant(s).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dr.C.Anna Palagan, Srinivas University,Mangalore. 2. Dr.B.M.Praveen, Srinivas University,Mangalore 3. Dr.Muthuvairavan Pillai.N,R.M.D Engineering College,Kavarapettai 4. Dr.K.Parimala Geetha, Christian College of Engineering and Technology,Oddanchatram 5. Mrs.D.Ramadevi, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad 6. Mrs. K.Shravani, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad 7. Dr. G.Sirisha, Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad 8. Mr. Muthyala V V S Chowdary,Teegala Krishna Reddy Engineering College,Hyderabad
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2. Name, address and nationality of the joint applicant.	(i) that I/We have not made any application for the same/substantially the same invention outside India or (ii) that I/We who have made this application No..... alone/jointly with, made for the same/substantially same invention, application(s) for patent in the other countries, the particulars of which are given below:
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Name of the country	Date of Application	Applicat ion No.	Status of the Application	Date of publication	Date of grant
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Not Applicable

3. Name and address of the assignee Dr.C.Anna Palagan Post-Doctoral Fellow Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka – 574146. India	(iii) That the rights in the application(s) have been assigned to Dr.C.Anna Palagan and that We undertake that upto the date of grant of the patent, by the Controller. We would keep him informed in writing the details regarding corresponding applications for patents filed outside India within three months from the date of filing of such application. Dated this fourth day of 23.09.2023
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4. To be signed by the applicant or his authorized registered patent agent.	
5. Name of the natural person who has signed Dr.C.Anna Palagan Post-Doctoral Fellow Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka - 574146. India	 Dr.C.Anna Palagan
To, The Controller of Patent The Patent Office, Chennai	